

Quantum-Computation Algorithms

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Abstract

In this research notebook on quantum computation and algorithms for quantum engineers, researchers, and scientists, we will discuss and summarize the application of quantum computing algorithms. The most famous quantum algorithm is for factoring numbers. We begin by describing how this algorithm has an enormous potential impact on the world of public-key cryptography. We began by looking at public-key encryption, and Shor's algorithm, and how Shor's algorithm can efficiently decrypt, for example, the RSA encryption protocol, which is the basis for information security. We discuss the difference between symmetric and asymmetric keys. We look at classical modern cryptography schemes, which are based on one-way functions. How factoring is performed today and why it is so hard on a classical computer. Furthermore, we went into detail about how Shor's algorithm can perform this same task, factoring, or order-finding, more efficiently. We first look at it at an intuitive level, and then went through it in mathematical detail. Next, we describe how quantum key distribution provides a method for regaining secure communications, founded upon the basic principles of quantum physics. Thus, we look at how quantum mechanics can break encryption. However, we are also looking at how quantum mechanics can support the encryption of communication protocols, how we can distribute keys using quantum mechanics. We discuss quantum key distribution (QKD) at some level that distributing these symmetric keys using quantum key distribution is an excellent way to encrypt data. So, we want to have a one-time pad at the disposal to encrypt data, but how do we exchange, or continually refresh that one-time pad? Furthermore, that is the task of QKD. We will discuss two general classes of QKD, one based on single-photon sources and detectors, and the other is based on entangled photons and Bell state measurements. Both rely on quantum concepts, which we will be discussing. For example, entanglement, projective measurement, and the no-cloning theorem are essential, so we are expanding on those concepts in detail. We are also going to discuss the importance of randomness in implementing QKD. Pseudo-random number generators that we have on the computers. They are random, but they are generated by the computers using a seed, and so, they are not truly random, never genuinely random. However, the randomness of projective measurements in quantum mechanics allows us to generate what we believe is true randomness. We will discuss how that is used today and the concept of long-distance quantum repeaters. How can we communicate using QKD over long distances when trying to communicate via photons, and photons can be lost or absorbed on an optical fiber? Moreover, in a practical sense, we can probably communicate without quantum repeaters over a metropolitan scale, length scale, but if we start to say, communicate over hundreds of miles or thousands of miles, or beyond, then we need to regenerate this quantum information somehow. The no-cloning theorem puts severe restrictions on what we can do. We cannot simply amplify the quantum information. We need to develop a quantum repeater, and so, we will discuss that as well. Next, we transition to physicist Richard Feynman's original application for quantum computer simulation of the quantum systems and how this is now arising as the key near-term application area for the

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quantum computation field. Finally, we explore another application area in the optimization, by going in-depth into the quantum search algorithm, and implement the algorithm utilizing a real physical quantum computer by IBM Q Experience.

1 Introduction to Quantum Information and Cryptography

Quantum computing is investigated worldwide, and we have looked at many efforts that are being done in the United States [1]. Many other efforts are going on worldwide, large efforts in the European Union [2]. They have a flagship program that spends about a billion dollars over the next ten years, investigating quantum computing, quantum communication, and quantum sensing [3]. There are national-level efforts, in Sweden and in Finland, Russia, and Japan [4], Canada [5], Australia [6]. Now many of these are funded by their respective governments, and so different governments have different levels of security. Many of the programs are open, and we can read about them in the public literature, but we should not expect that everything we are seeing is everything that is being done. Many of them are pursuing quantum computing, quantum simulation, universal quantum computation, quantum communication, and quantum sensing. However, in detail, we do not necessarily know what they are doing or what their strategies. In this section, we will manifest quantum mechanical effects that enable quantum computers to process information efficiently [7–20]. we build on the fundamentals studies to probe more deeply the applications of quantum computing [21,22] and quantum cryptography [23]. We will not worry about practical issues, like noise at this moment, but rather focused on understanding how these algorithms and protocols work [20]. We will explore the algorithms for cybersecurity, chemistry, and optimization purpose. we want to understand how these algorithms work and their applications. We began by looking at modern cryptography and its use of asymmetric keys, one public, one private, to realize secure public-key cryptography based on one-way functions. We will study in detail one primary example, the RSA cryptosystem [24]. We will discuss that RSA is based on the idea that it is mathematically easy for a classical computer to multiply two large prime numbers, P and Q , and obtain their product N . However. It is a very hard problem for a classical computer to do the inverse, the factor that number N into its constituent primes, P and Q [25]. afterward, we will begin by looking at how Quantum nature can be used to break public-key encryption. We will go into details of Shor’s Algorithm [26], which can efficiently defeat certain important encryption protocols if implemented on a quantum computer. For example, RSA encryption, which serves as the basis for information security today, can be compromised by efficiently performing period finding of modular exponentiation, which is related to prime number factorization. We will look at modern cryptography schemes based on one-way functions. We will look at how factoring is performed and why it is so hard on a classical computer. We will then look at how Shor’s Algorithm can perform the same task in a much more efficient manner, at an intuitive level, and then deep mathematical level into how his algorithm works. Next, we turn to quantum cryptography and discuss how quantum mechanics could enhance communication security through quantum key distribution. We will discuss single-photon generation and detection, and their use in the BB84 QKD protocol. We then look at entangled photons, Bell States, and Bell State measurements [27,28], and their uses in the Ekert91 protocol, quantum teleportation, and random number generation. Then, we transition to quantum simulation [29]. We first discuss Hamiltonians, describe the dynamics of a quantum system, and the simulation of those dynamics using Trotterization [30,31]. We then turn to algorithms, such as phase estimation and variational quantum eigensolvers [32,33], that address problem in quantum chemistry [34,35], another hybrid quantum-classical algorithm are variational quantum fidelity estimation algorithm [36], variational quantum factoring (VQF) algorithm [37]. Next, we will discuss adiabatic quantum computing [38,39], optimization algorithms, the quantum approximate

optimization algorithms (QAOA) [40, 41]. We will also discuss quantum annealing [42–49], and its use of tunneling and relaxation to approach low energy solutions [50]. Although it is not yet known if such processes afford a quantum enhancement, quantum annealers are actively studied in the research, because optimization problems are ubiquitous. Finally, we will investigate Grover’s Search Algorithm [51], and how it works within the quantum circuit model, and then do prototype experimental demonstrations and implement it on the IBM quantum experience [52].

2 Modern Cryptography

We generate and communicate tremendous amounts of digital data every day. Nevertheless, how do we protect this data from eavesdroppers? This section will discuss modern cryptography and how it is used to protect data through encryption. In this section, we will look at modern cryptography schemes and their use in information security today. Every day we generate, accumulate, and communicate tremendous amounts of data. Everything from the personal emails, financial transactions, and medical records, to a corporation’s intellectual property, business strategy, and online sales, to the daily operation and functioning of the government and military organizations. In each of these cases, we expect, even require, that the information is stored and communicated securely such that it is available to ourselves and the intended recipients, but to nobody else. In general, information is protected using encryption. Encryption takes raw data, such as a message, often referred to as plain text, and translates it or encodes it into an unrecognizable message called a cyphertext. It does this by using an algorithm called a cipher. A cipher takes as inputs the plaintext being encoded and a key, typically a numerical bit string in today’s cryptography schemes. The cipher then combines them into an unreadable cyphertext through a prescribed algorithmic protocol based on mathematical operations. Similarly, a decryption key is used with a corresponding decryption protocol to reconstruct the plaintext message. The most common cryptography schemes historically are called symmetric-key cryptography in which the encryption and decryption keys are the same or can be trivially related to one another. Examples include the older data encryption standard, DES, and the more modern advanced encryption standard, AES. The one-time pad that we discussed in section one in the context of quantum key distribution is another example of the symmetric key cryptography scheme. Since symmetric keys are used to both encrypt and decrypt a message, they must remain private. It is not a serious issue, say, a personal computer where we want to encrypt the hard drive, and so, the keys are stored locally. However, it raises a challenge when communicating information. When two parties want to communicate securely, they need to meet in advance to secretly discuss the symmetric keys, not a very practical option, or they need to establish private channels to distribute the key securely. In the future, efficient quantum key distribution protocols may provide a quantum-enhanced security level when transmitting a secret symmetric key. However, today, secure communication links are established using public-key cryptography based on asymmetric keys. Public key cryptography was developed in the 1970s by several groups. Whitfield Diffie and Martin Hellman published the first public-key cryptography scheme, the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol, in 1976. Later in 1978, the RSA algorithm was published by Ronald Rivest, Adi Shamir, and Len Adleman. Researchers at the British General Communications Headquarters, GCHQ, had developed similar public-key cryptography schemes in the early 1970s, but only declassified those achievements in 1997. Public key cryptography is based on asymmetric keys. A public key is used for encryption, and a separate independent, private key is used for decryption. The keys are necessarily related to one another mathematically, and the information security relies on it being computationally impractical to determine the private key given the public key. It is possible to use one-way mathematical functions. For example, RSA cryptography [24] is

based on the idea that it is mathematically easy for a computer to multiply two large prime numbers, p , and q , and obtain their product, N . However, it is a hard problem for a computer to do the inverse, that is, a factor that number, N , into its constituent prime factors, p , and q [25]. With one-way mathematical functions, ease of use is based on the mathematical simplicity in the forward direction, and security is based on mathematical complexity in the inverse direction. To get an idea for how this works, consider the following cartoon. Bob wants to communicate a message securely to Alice without that message being read by an eavesdropper, Eve. To do this, Bob requests a public encryption key from Alice. Alice then sends a public encryption key but retains her private decryption key. we will represent this by keys with the letter E for encryption, D for decryption, and a notional open lock. During transmission on a public channel, in principle, Eve obtains the open lock and the encryption key. When Bob receives them, he encrypts his plaintext message using the encryption key, creating cyphertext, and effectively locks the padlock. Bob then sends the cyphertext back to Alice on a public channel. Although Eve can obtain the cyphertext in principle, she cannot unlock the padlock since she only has the public encryption key. The security here is based on it is very hard for Eve to figure out the decryption key based on what she has in her possession. Alice, on the other hand, is able to trivially unlock the padlock using her decryption key, thereby converting the cyphertext to plaintext and reading the message. This type of public-key encryption scheme is used ubiquitously today for secure communication. In many cases, it is used to establish a private channel that provides authentication and enables symmetric keys to be exchanged securely. It is because the public key approach based on asymmetric keys is slower to implement than symmetric schemes. Public key encryption is a foundation for information security today. in the next section, we will take a more detailed look at one specific example, RSA cryptography, and how it works.

The Enigma machine is a legendary cipher machine used by German forces before and during World War II. Enigma is an electro-mechanical rotor cipher machine. A message called "plaintext" written by the operator is encoded by the machine similar in appearance to a typewriter in the following manner: a single character is pseudo-randomly replaced with a different letter according to the wiring of the machine. The subsequent letter is replaced following the same mechanism, but with the rotor shifted to a different position. The shifted rotor position causes the letter to be substituted according to a different electrical pathway and hence character substitution table. Thus, each character of the message is replaced according to a different encoding scheme. The resulting "ciphertext" can subsequently be transmitted via regular public communication channels. It can only be decoded using a machine with the same configuration and capability to reverse the encoding. Finally, a successful decipher trial reveals the true content of the message in the form of a plaintext again.

In 1941, at Bletchley Park, a British team, including Alan Turing, uncovered Enigma's working principles for the Allies. The deciphered information of the intercepted messages provided the Allies with a significant advantage that ultimately became a key element in their victory over the Axis powers.

The Enigma machine is an example of the symmetric encryption scheme, where the same key is used to encode and decode a message. Symmetric encryption schemes are still in use today. However, since World War II, a cryptographic key generation has evolved from electro-mechanical methods to classically constructed digital bit strings serving as encrypting keys. The keys are mathematically challenging to derive and require a significant amount of computational power and time. The computational power and time required to decode are to determine the security of an encoding key.

In 1975, the Data Encryption Standard (DES) was introduced by IBM. The DES algorithm generates a 56-bit symmetric encryption key using a complex mathematical method. Despite this mathematical complexity, DES was known from the beginning to be potentially susceptible

to a brute-force key-search attack due to its relatively limited key size. In fact, by the beginning of the 21st century, computational power had sufficiently advanced to the point that one could determine the key in less than a day. For example, Distributed.Net is an organization specializing in the use of idle computer time, utilizing more than 100,000 computers ranging from slow PCs to powerful multiprocessor machines to test 250 billion keys per second and thereby determine a particular 56-bit key in about 23 hours. Given the increasing vulnerability of DES, in 2001, DES was replaced by the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), a more secure symmetric-key cryptography scheme.

However, there remained a conundrum: how can two parties exchange a symmetric key to initiate secure communication, before they have a secure channel on which to send it? In 1976, a new method for distributing cryptographic keys was introduced by Whitfield Diffie, and Martin Hellman referred to as the Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol, which heralded the era of public-key cryptography with asymmetric keys. Asymmetric keys comprise a public key used to encrypt messages and a mathematically related (but unique) private key used to decrypt messages. The security of public-key cryptosystems is premised on the use of one-way mathematical functions to create the public and private keys. One-way mathematical functions are straightforward to calculate in the forward direction but prohibitively complex to calculate in the inverse direction. A widely used public-key distribution algorithm was published in 1978 by Ronald Rivest, Adi Shamir, and Len Adleman, referred to as the RSA algorithm. It was later declassified in the late 1990s that asymmetric encryption schemes like RSA were already developed by the British General Communications Headquarters (GCHQ) in the early 1970s. With public-key cryptosystems, one could exchange public keys and establish a secure link, without having symmetric keys in hand at the beginning. Once a secure link was established, one then has the option of continuing to communicate using asymmetric keys, or one can alternatively use this newly established secure link to exchange symmetric keys and use symmetric encryption/decryption protocols.

In practice, public-key encryption techniques are primarily used to establish a secure channel and distribute symmetric keys, which are, in turn, used to encrypt messages. It is because encryption using an asymmetric-key protocol is generally less resource-efficient than using a symmetric-key protocol. For example, a 128-bit symmetric key has 2^{128} different possible key combinations. In contrast, a 3000-bit asymmetric key can leverage only the fraction of the 2^{3000} possible bit strings that comply with the conditions required by the underlying one-way function. Therefore, whereas the symmetric key of 128 bits and a 3000-bit public key afford a similar level of security, the symmetric-key approach is generally more efficient to implement.

3 RSA Cryptosystem

We often communicate securely by encrypting data using cryptographic schemes. However, how do we initiate and establish a secure channel, if we have not yet securely exchanged cryptographic keys? In this section, we will discuss the RSA cryptosystem, a quintessential example of a public-key cryptosystem that leverages asymmetric keys based on one-way mathematical functions to communicate sensitive information.

In the last section, we introduced modern cryptography schemes and discussed the difference between symmetric and asymmetric keys. We discuss that cryptographic algorithms based on symmetric keys have a conundrum when it comes to key distribution. Namely, how can we securely exchange the keys if we do not yet have them in the possession to encrypt the initial transmission? The answer, as we discuss, is to use public-key cryptography based on asymmetric keys. That is, using a public key for encryption and a different private key for decryption. The keys are related to one another mathematically. Their associated information security relies on

it being computationally impractical to determine the private key even when we know the public key. This is achieved through the use of one-way mathematical functions where the ease of use of the cryptosystem is based on the mathematical simplicity of implementing the function in the forward direction, and its security is based on the mathematical complexity of implementing it in the reverse or inverse direction. Thus, now, in this section, we will look at a specific quintessential example of public-key cryptography, the RSA cryptosystem, and discuss the fundamentals of how it works. We will discuss communication in the context of Alice and Bob in the presence of an eavesdropper, Eve. Bob would like to send a secure message to Alice. So, he requests her public key, which we will represent here with the letter E . He uses it to encrypt his plain text message, which we will call M , and generate an unreadable cyphertext called C . Alice retains her private key, D , which she uses to decrypt the cyphertext she receives from Bob, and thereby reconstruct the original plain text message. Although Eve has access to the public key and the cyphertext, she cannot decrypt it to reconstruct the plain text message because she does not have access to the private decryption key. because the two keys are mathematically related to one another through a one-way function, computing the private key from what Eve has in hand is, by design, a very hard problem to solve on a classical computer. The RSA cryptosystem is based on a mathematical concept called modular exponentiation. The basic idea is that one can efficiently define three large positive integers, e , d , and N , such that the following expression is true for all integers m between 0 and N . Namely, m raised to the power e and then raised again to the power d is equal to itself, modulo N . It is very hard for a computer to calculate the number d even when given the numbers e and N . Now this is a fantastic result because it says that Bob can generate cyphertext by taking a plain text message, converting it to an integer N using an agreed-upon protocol, and then raising N to the power e using the public encryption key. Then Alice can decrypt the cyphertext by raising it to the power d to obtain back the number N , modulo N , from which she can reconstruct the plain text message. The public key comprises the numbers e and N , and the private key comprises the numbers d and N . Now, strictly speaking, the only d needs to be kept private, but Alice will need both d and N to do the decryption. With this background, the RSA cryptosystem can be broken into four steps, key generation, key distribution, encryption, and decryption. Let us take them one at a time. Key generation starts with finding two distinct prime numbers, p , and q , a task which can be performed efficiently on a classical computer using mathematical protocols called primality tests. Prime numbers are those that are divisible by only themselves and unity. importantly, these numbers must be chosen at random. we will discuss later in the section more about how quantum mechanics can, in principle, generate true randomness. For now, though, let us assume that we use a pseudo-random number generator on a classical computer. Next, the prime numbers p and q multiply together to generate the number N . Multiplication, which is also efficient on a classical computer. The number N is used as the modulus for both the public and private keys in the performance of modular exponentiation. The next step is to determine the encryption and decryption keys themselves, e and d . This is done using the periodicity property of modular exponentiation. To see this, let us consider a simple example. we will take the number 3 and its exponents, modulo 10. So, 3 to the i th power, modulo 10, where i is an integer, 1, 2, 3. we see that 3 to the first power modulo 10 is 3. 3 squared modulo 10 is 9. 3 cubed is 27, and so, 3 cubed modulo 10 is 7. The modulo 10 is the remainder when dividing 27 by 10. So, 27 divided by 10 is 2 with a remainder 7. Next, 3 to the fourth power is 81, which modulo 10 is 1. continuing, we see that the numbers repeat, 3, 9, 7, 1. 3, 9, 7, 1. Thus, the periodicity here is 4. we will call this periodicity r , So, r equals 4 in this case. Now there is a relationship between the periodicity r and the prime numbers p and q . Consider a general sequence: x modulo N , x squared modulo N , x cubed modulo N , where N equals p times q and x is a number that is not divisible by p or q . Then the sequence has a period r that evenly divides p minus 1-time q minus 1. Let us see how this plays

out in the above example. There, the modulus is N equal 10, which has prime factors p equal 2 and q equals 5. 2 times 5 equals 10 . Then p minus 1 is 1 . q minus 1 is 4 . Thus, the quantity p minus 1 time q minus 1 is 1 time 4 , and that equals 4 . this evenly divides the period r equals 4 . So, that checks. What is important here is that this is the one-way function. If we are given prime numbers p and q , then we can calculate the periodicity r . we will not go into how this is done here. we just note that it can be done efficiently on a classical computer, again, if we know the prime numbers p and q . However, if we are just given N , but we do not know p and q , it is hard to find the periodicity r . typically, the periodicity is very large, unlike the simple example given here. So, a brute force search is not efficient either. So, returning to the key generation, Alice has prime numbers p and q . She used them to determine the period r , and she keeps all these numbers private. She now uses r to determine the keys e and d . First, she chooses an integer e in the range 1 to r that is also co-prime with r . That is, e and r have no common divisor other than 1 . Now often, this number is simply chosen so that it is not too big and has mostly 0 s to enable efficient encryption. For example, 2 to the 16 th power plus 1 equal $65,537$, which, in binary, is 1 followed by 15 0 s and another 1 . This is the public encryption key, e . Then the private decryption key is directly calculated from the expression d times e equals 1 modulo r . In summary, Alice generated the public encryption key e and the private decryption key d from the periodicity r based on randomly chosen prime numbers p and q , which multiply together to yield N . Alice keep private the integers p , q , and r , which she used to calculate her private decryption key d . In contrast, the encryption key e and the number N can be made public. In the next step, key distribution, Alice sends Bob the public encryption key e and the number N . Bob has a plain text message that he wants to transmit to Alice securely. He first turns his message into an integer N using an agreed-upon reversible protocol called padding scheme. He then computes the cyphertext c using modular exponentiation and the public key. c equals N to the e th power modulo N . Bob then sends the ciphertext to Alice. Alice then applies her decryption key d to the cyphertext. Using modular exponentiation once more, c to the d -th power, Alice calculates the result, N modulo N . by reversing the padding scheme, Alice recovers the original plain text message. Again, the security of the RSA cryptosystem is based on the use of a one-way function, in this case, the challenge of period finding in modular exponentiation. As we just discussed, if one knows the prime factors p and q , then one can efficiently find the modular exponentiation period r , and thus generate encryption keys e and d . However, if we are just given the modulus N , there is no known efficient classical algorithm that lets us find its prime factors p and q . Thus, there is no efficient means to determine the period r under these conditions. Thus, even if we reveal the modulus N and the public encryption key e , there are no known efficient means for Eve to calculate the private key d , that is, on a classical computer. In the next section, we will look at Shor's Algorithm and discuss how period finding can be efficiently performed on a quantum computer, thus enabling, in principle, an efficient pathway to breaking the RSA cryptosystem.

Modern cryptography is a foundation for today's information and economic security, enabling secure communication between individuals, businesses, and governments. There are two basic classes of cryptosystems: symmetric-key and asymmetric-key cryptography. Asymmetric-key cryptography also referred to as public-key cryptography, uses a public key and a private key to encode and decode messages. The two distinct keys are mathematically related via a one-way function, which is computationally efficient to calculate in one direction, but not in the inverse direction.

The workhorse of public-key encryption schemes is the RSA cryptosystem, which can be broken into four steps:

1. key generation (a public key $\{e, N\}$ and a private key $\{d, N\}$),
2. public key distribution,
3. message encryption (a message $m \rightarrow$ a ciphertext c) and transmission,

4. message decryption.

Key Generation and Distribution:

The encryption and decryption keys are generated using a one-way function related to modular exponentiation. To begin with, the two distinct prime numbers p and q are chosen at random. The key generation then centers on the function.

$$f(x) = a^x \pmod{N}, \tag{1}$$

Where $a \neq p, q$ is an integer number, the modulus $N = pq$ is the product of p and q , and "mod N " means "modulo N ." The term "modular exponentiation" refers to an exponential a^x that is calculated modulo N .

From the number theory of modular exponentiation, it is known that the function $f(x)$ is periodic with period r , and finding the value of r is called order finding. Order finding is a manageable task if one knows p and q , but not if one only knows their product N . This is the one-way function under the security of RSA.

To see this, consider the following. When $x = 0$ in the above function,

$$f(0) = a^0 \pmod{N} = 1. \tag{2}$$

If $f(x)$ is periodic in r , then it follows that the function $f(r), f(2r), f(3r), \dots$ must also equal 1. The period r can be derived using Fermat's little theorem, which uses Euler's totient function

$$r = (p - 1)(q - 1) \tag{3}$$

To find the period r .

In essence, Euler's totient function gives the number of positive integers smaller than the product $pq = N$, which have no prime factors in common with N , that is, co-prime with p , q , and N and Fermat's little theorem shows that this is the period r . Note that r may be the fundamental period or an integer multiple of the fundamental period. The fundamental period is the least common multiple of $(p - 1)$ and $(q - 1)$. Both the fundamental period or a multiple of the fundamental period will work.

With p and q are known, the totient can be easily calculated with a classical computer. However, if one is only given N (without knowledge of q and q), then one must factor N to find p and q and thereby find the period r . Factoring is a hard problem for a classical computer [25].

With the period r in hand, one can generate the public key $\{e, N\}$ and private key $\{d, N\}$. One first chooses a public encryption exponent e that satisfies the following conditions:

1.

$$3 \leq e \leq (N - 1), \tag{4}$$

2. e is co-prime with r .

The second condition means that there is no integer (other than 1) that divides both e and r , and so their greatest common divisor (gcd) is 1. This is written as $\text{gcd}(e, r) = 1$.

Once a value of e is chosen, then one calculates a private decryption exponent d as the modular multiplicative inverse of e , modulo r :

$$d = e^{-1} \pmod{r} \tag{5}$$

Note that when using a modular calculator [53], we will have to use the syntax $A^B \pmod{C}$ and not $\frac{1}{A} \pmod{C}$ as the modular multiplicative inverse is only defined for integers. The notation above, while often found, can be misleading in this way.

Intuitively, as we explain in more detail below, the inversion follows that d is used to decrypt a message that is encrypted using e . one can again trivially calculate the private decryption exponent d given the public encryption exponent e , provided one knows the period r .

The steps are summarized in the following table for the specific example of $p=17$ and $q=19$.

Table 1: $p=17$ and $q=19$

1	p,q:	choose two random prime numbers	$p=17, 19$
2	N:	calculate $N = pq$	$N = 17*19=323$
3	r:	find the period $r = (p-1)(q-1)$	$r = 16*18=288$
4	e:	choose a public exponent e with greatest common divisor $\gcd(e,r) = 1$	$e = 7, \gcd(7,288) = 1$
5	d:	calculate the private exponent $d = e^{-1} \pmod r$	$d=247$

Having created the keys, Alice sends the public key $\{e, N\}$ to Bob. Importantly, she retains the private key $\{d, N\}$, and does not reveal the values p , q , or r .

Message Encryption and Decryption:

Bob has a message m he wants to send to Alice. Having received the public encryption key $\{e, N\}$, he encrypts m to create cyphertext c using the public key and modular exponentiation:

$$c = m^e \pmod N. \quad (6)$$

After the message is sent to Alice, she decrypts it with her private key $\{d, N\}$ using the properties of modular exponentiation,

$$c^d \pmod N = (m^e)^d \pmod N = m \quad (7)$$

provided the original message m is smaller than the modulus N . Eve has access to the public key $\{e, N\}$, but this is no use to her in trying to decrypt the cyphertext, since $c^e \pmod N \neq m$.

In summary, the number theory and properties of modular exponentiation underlie the security of the RSA cryptosystem. As we have seen, the challenge of order finding can be related to the problem of factoring. While it is straightforward to multiply two numbers p and q to give the modulus N , the inverse problem is hard on a classical computer. If N is chosen sufficiently large, then a brute-force search to find p and q is also inefficient. Thus, the RSA cryptosystem is believed to be securely provided the prime numbers p and q , and the private exponent d are not made public. However, the encryption exponent e and modulus N can be made public. This type of cryptosystem, where the encryption key is public, and anyone can encrypt a message. In contrast, the decryption key is private, and only the receiver can decrypt the cyphertext, which is the backbone of our modern-day communication systems.

4 Factoring With a Quantum Computer: Shor's Algorithm

The security of the RSA cryptosystem is premised on a one-way function that is difficult to invert using a classical computer. However, using Shor's algorithm, a quantum computer can perform this task much more efficiently. In this section, we will discuss how Shor's algorithm works.

In the last section, we looked at a specific implementation of public-key cryptography in the RSA cryptosystem. The security of RSA is based on the use of a one-way function prime factorization, which is related to the problem of period finding in modular exponentiation. As we discuss, if one picks two prime numbers, p , and q , which multiply together to give a modulus N , then one can efficiently find the modular exponentiation period r , and thus generate a public encryption key e and a private decryption key d . However, if we are just given the modulus

N , then we are stuck, because there is no known efficient classical algorithm that lets us find the prime factors p and q , and so, there is no efficient means to determine the period r . Thus, even if we reveal the modulus N and the public encryption key e , there is no known efficient way for an eavesdropper to calculate the private key d on a classical computer. However, if Eve has access to a quantum computer that can run Shor's Algorithm, she can efficiently find the modular exponentiation period r . This is called an order finding. Shor's algorithm finds the order r of a number with respect to the modulus N , where a number is raised to integer powers under modular exponentiation. With a means to efficiently determine, r . Eve can calculate the prime numbers p and q and derive the decryption key d , thus compromising RSA. In this section, we will walk through Shor's Algorithm using the quantum circuit model presented in section 1 [54]. Then, we will continue with the simple example of modular exponentiation to see the connection between order finding and factorization. Let us begin with the initialization stage. we need two registers of qubits for Shor's Algorithm. Roughly speaking, Register 1 is used to store the results of a period finding protocol, which is implemented using the Quantum Fourier Transform. we will discuss that one in a moment. Register 2 is used to store the values of the modular exponentiation. This is the function that will apply in the computing section. The number of qubits in the first register should generate a state space that is at least large enough to capture the maximum possible period, and do so, at least twice to see it repeat. Let us define N as twice the maximum period. So, we need at least L qubits, such that 2 to the L power is greater than N . Now, in fact, the more qubits we have, the more densely we can sample the solution space and reduce the error in determining the period. Here, we will take $2L$ qubits for the first register. for simplicity, we will use the same number of qubits in the second register. By choosing $2L$ qubits, the number of states 2 to the $2L$ power is greater than N squared. This guarantees that at least N terms are contributing to the probability amplitude when estimating the period. Even as the period r gets exponentially large, approaching N over 2 . we prepare the qubits in state 0 , which we denote with a superscripted tensor product, $2L$. As we did in section 1 for the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm, we will track the register states by color yellow for Register 1, and green for Register 2. we will track the current position within the algorithm using the vertical line. Next, at the compute stage, we use Hadamard gates to place the Register 1 qubit into an equal superposition state. Again, we use the superscripted tensor product notation to indicate that we apply a Hadamard gate to each of the $2L$ qubits. This puts each qubit into a superposition state, 0 plus 1 . Multiplying out all $2L$ of these single qubit superposition states results in a single large equal superposition state with 2 to the $2L$ components. From a component with $2L$ qubits in state 0 to a component with all qubits in state 1 , and with all combinations in between. If we now number these components from 0 to 2 to the $2L$ minus 1 , we can rewrite the superposition state as a sum over x . Each decimal number x corresponds to one of the binary numbers represented by the $2L$ qubits. Next, the function f is performed. f of x implements modular exponentiation, which outputs a number a to the x power modulo N . we will not present in detail how the modular exponentiation is implemented in a real circuit. There are multiple approaches to doing it based on reversible computing and multiplication algorithms. For the purposes here, we note that this function can be implemented using ancilla qubits and that it is efficient, requiring several gates that scales only polynomials with the number of qubits [55]. Now, the number is chosen at random, and it must be co-prime with N . That is, it must have no common factors with N . The resulting output values from the function f are then stored in the Register 2 qubits. Since the values of the power x are taken from the qubits in the first register, implementing f of x makes a conditional connection between the qubits in Register 1 and those in Register 2. Although we will not need to measure the qubits in Register 2, this step sets the stage for quantum interference and quantum parallelism to occur in Register 1 at the next step, which is the Quantum Fourier Transform. The Quantum Fourier Transform is a quantum

version of the classical discrete-time Fourier Transform. The classical Fourier Transform takes a vector of numbers, x often a digital sampling of a signal to be analyzed and transforms it into a vector of numbers, y , in the frequency domain. Periodic behavior in the time domain is more easily identified in the transformed frequency domain, which is why we do this. For example, a sine wave that oscillates in time with a specific frequency will transform to a large amplitude spike at plus or minus that frequency in the transform domain. Thus, it is easy to identify the spikes' location and then read off the frequency directly. if we know a signal's frequency, we also know its period, since the frequency is 1 over the period. Now, the Quantum Fourier Transform is essentially the same transformation, which is why we will use it for period finding. It takes a state j and transforms it into a superposition state with specific phase factors. If we start with a superposition state with coefficients X_j , the transformed result is also a superposition state with coefficients Y_k , where the probability amplitudes Y_k are the classical discrete-time Fourier Transform of the probability amplitudes X_j . due to quantum parallelism and quantum interference, implementing the Quantum Fourier Transform is exponentially faster than implementing the classical fast Fourier Transform algorithm. Now, that sounds great, but there is an important catch related to quantum measurement. As we know, the measurement of a quantum state is probabilistic. Although the output of the Quantum Fourier Transform is a large superposition state with transformed probability amplitudes, we cannot access those amplitudes. the measurement projects out only a single state, and even if we identically prepare the system and measure it many times, we only discuss the magnitude squared of the corresponding coefficients. we lose the phase information. So, we do not have access to the probability amplitudes in the quantum computer, which is quite different from the classical Fourier Transform, where the entire output vector of complex numbers can be directly read. Thus, the Quantum Fourier Transform is most useful in problems with a unique period or phase that can be found with high probability. For now, let us return to Shor's Algorithm. The Quantum Fourier Transform is applied here to the qubits in Register 1, and it imparts specific phase factors that are related to both x and z . That is, they are related to both the coefficients of the qubits on Register 1 and the modular exponentiation stored on Register 2. The phase sampling increment is represented here by ω , and it is the phase 2π divided by the total number of states 2^L . Here we can see that increasing the number of qubits will reduce the step size, and thus the error in estimating the actual period. Essentially, more qubits will more densely sample the phases that represent the period. Lastly, we measure the qubits in Register 1. The projected state that results is a binary value of z , and its decimal value is equal to or an integer multiple of 2^L divided by r . Thus, it can be used to find the period r using a continued-fraction expansion of z divided by 2^L . we can discuss more the Quantum Fourier Transform and related topics in the text units following this section. in the next section, we will take a closer look at how the Quantum Fourier Transform mediates the quantum interference terms that constructively converge to estimates for the period r .

The classical Discrete Time Fourier Transform (DTFT) is a mathematical transformation that takes a vector x of numbers as an input typically a digital sampling of a time-domain signal being analyzed and outputs a vector of numbers y that is its frequency-domain representation:

$$y_k = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} x_j \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi}{N} jk\right) \quad (8)$$

Where N is the total number of points in the vector x , this transform is used ubiquitously in the analysis of signals, because periodic behavior in the time domain is more easily identified in the transformed frequency domain. For example, a sinusoidal signal in time with a frequency f will transform to spikes at $\pm f$ in the frequency domain, find the spikes, and know the frequency of the input signal (or, equivalently, the inverse of its period).

The quantum analog of this transform the Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT) is essentially the same transformation. It takes a single quantum state $|j\rangle$ and transforms it to a superposition of states, each with specific phase factors:

$$|j\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{N}jk\right) |k\rangle, \quad (9)$$

where N is the total number of states $|k\rangle$; for n qubits, $N = 2^n$. If we start with a superposition of states $|j\rangle$ with coefficients x_j , then the QFT yields an output superposition of states $|k\rangle$ with coefficients y_k ,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{N-1} x_j |j\rangle \rightarrow \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} y_k |k\rangle, \quad (10)$$

Where the output amplitudes y_k are the DTFT of the input coefficients x_j . Due to quantum parallelism and quantum interference, the QFT can be implemented using only (n^2) gates. This is exponentially faster than the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) algorithm used to calculate the classical DTFT, which requires $O(n2^n)$ gates.

This sounds terrific, and it is, but there is an important caveat. In general, the QFT cannot be used as a straightforward replacement for the DTFT for real-world data processing applications, and the reason is related to quantum measurement.

In the case of the classical DTFT, even for a real input vector \mathbf{x} , the transformed output vector \mathbf{y} is complex. We can classically access all of the complex elements of \mathbf{y} .

In contrast, in the case of the QFT, a measurement of the output superposition state will project the system into only one of those states with a probability that is the magnitude squared of the corresponding coefficient. We generally have no access to the complex probability amplitudes y_k . Even if we identically prepare the system and measure it many times, we can only reconstruct the magnitude squared of those coefficients (the magnitude squared of the Fourier spectrum); we have no access to the phase information, and it will take an exponentially large number of measurements to reconstruct the probability for all 2^n states.

Nonetheless, the QFT is a critical element in quantum computing protocols, including phase estimation and period finding. For these types of applications, the desired output from the QFT is highly localized into a few states with high probability. These states encode the desired information, for example, the period r of modular exponentiation used in Shor's algorithm.

5 Factoring With a Quantum Computer: How Shor's Algorithm Works

In the last section, we discuss how Shor's Algorithm is implemented within the circuit model for quantum computing. In this section, we will discuss one more critical step in the algorithm, the application of the quantum Fourier transform.

In the last section, we presented Shor's Algorithm in the context of the quantum circuit model. we used two registers of qubits. Register 1 was used to store the results of period finding, and Register 2 was used to store the modular exponentiation function's values. we then applied the Quantum Fourier Transform to Register 1 and measured the output. The projected state resulted in a binary value of z , and its decimal value was an integer multiple of $2L$ divided by r . This, in turn, can be used to find the period r using a continued-fraction expansion. In this section, we will take a closer look at how the Quantum Fourier Transform and the resulting quantum interference lead us to this result. To see how this works, we need to rewrite the sum

over x as a combination of two sums. we can use the example of an equal 3 and N equal 10, which we discuss has a period r equal 4. we want to sum over all x from 0 to 2 to the $2L$ power minus 1. The corresponding function f of x , the modular exponentiation is calculated for several values of x , and the period is, indeed, 4. Let us call the values of x in the first period x_0 , and the resulting values of the function f we will call w . we see that w has only four unique values and repeats for values of x equal to x_0 plus integer multiples of the period r . That is, x_0 plus y times r , where we use y as the integer. for a given x_0 , the function f of x_0 plus y r is the same value, as indicated in orange for x_0 equals 0. we can see the same behavior for x_0 equals 1 in green, x_0 equals 2 in blue, and x_0 equals 3 in gray. we see that in doing this for the four values of x_0 , we have covered all values of x . Thus, we can rewrite the sum over x as a sum over the four values of x_0 and a sum over the integer y , which runs from 0 to 2 to the L th power divided by r . Together, these two sums run over all x values from 0 to 2 to the L minus 1. Writing in this way enables us to see how quantum interference occurs with these phase vectors. we first replace ω with its explicit value, e to the power i times $2\pi/2$ over 2 to the $2L$. there are two-phase factors here. The first is a fixed phase offset independent of the sum over y . It will rotate the phase of any net result that survives the sum. The second is the quantum interference phase related to the sum over y itself. This sum is performed for every value of x_0 and z , and it is essentially a test to see if the value of z is related to the period r when starting from a value x_0 . The sum over y adds together vectors with specific phases related to x_0 , z , r , and y . In most cases, these phases are not multiples of 2π , so the corresponding vectors, according to their phases, end up pointing in various directions, uniformly distributed around the unit circle. Since they point in all directions, adding these vectors gives a net result of 0, which is another example of destructive quantum interference. Now, for a few specific cases where z is related to r through x_0 , the phases are a multiple of 2π . When this is true, the corresponding vectors will always point in the same direction to the right and thus add together constructively. There are 2 to the $2L$ divided by r unit vectors, and so, the sum is 2 to the $2L$ divided by r . Mathematically, the sum over y is a geometric sum. we encourage us to calculate this and find the condition which yields non-0 values. we will find the resulting condition is that $2\pi/2$ to the $2L$ times z times r is 2π times an integer, d . Thus, it occurs when z equals d times 2 to the $2L$ divided by r . If we plot the probability at the output of the Quantum Fourier Transform, we find a series of spikes that occur when z equals d times 2 to the $2L$ over r . The probability of measuring any one of these spikes is 1 over r since there are r spikes between 0 and 2 to the $2L$ over r . This is for a specific value of x_0 . Whichever one of these spikes we measure, the projected state z with value d times 2 to the $2L$ over r can be used to find the period r using a continued-fraction expansion procedure. we will not discuss here in detail how that is done. we just note that it is a known algorithm and it can be effectively performed on a classical computer. Now, we just discuss how Shor's Algorithm can find the period r , but how is this connected to the factoring problem in RSA? Again, we will take the example with N equal 10. we want to find the prime factors p and q that, multiplied together, equal 10. To do this, we randomly pick a number, a that is smaller than N and prime. That is, their Greatest Common Divisor-GCD is unity. we will again choose a equal 3. we then use Shor's Algorithm to find the period of a to the x modulo N . Shor's Algorithm, with classical post-processing, will efficiently give us the period r equal 4. Before proceeding, we need to do a couple of checks. First, r must be an even number. second, we need to ensure that a to the r over 2 power plus 1 does not equal 0 modulo N . If we fail either of these tests, we need to go back to step 1 and pick another value of a . However, in the case here, we are fine. For a equal 3 and r equal 4, both conditions check, and we can proceed. we know that a to the r equals 1 modulo N , as this is a property of modular exponentiation. we can rewrite this expression as a to the r -th power minus 1 equals k times N for an integer, k . we then replace N with the unknown prime factors p and q , and we factor the left-hand side to yield a to

the r over 2 minus 1 time a to the r over 2 plus 1. Then, p and q can be found from the greatest common divisor of a to the power r over 2 plus or minus 1, and N . Let us take them one at a time. a to the power r over 2 minus 1 is 8. Thus, the greatest common divisor of 8 and 10 is 2, so, p equals 2. Then a to the r over 2 plus 1 is 10, and so, the greatest common divisor of 10 and 10 that is not trivial is 5, so q will equal 5. Therefore, p equals 2, q equals 5, both are prime numbers, and p times q equals 10. Now, this is a very simple example. However, it illustrates how Shor's Algorithm and period finding can be used to calculate prime numbers p and q , and thus calculate the private decryption key and compromise the RSA cryptosystem. More details and background information related to these topics can be found in the following text units.

6 Quantum Fourier Transform

The Quantum Fourier Transform (QFT) is a critical operation used in quantum computing protocols, including period finding and phase estimation. For example, in the period finding protocol, the input state encodes a sequence with an underlying periodic structure, and, following the application of the QFT, the output encodes the period of the sequence.

The QFT is a unitary linear transformation implemented with a series of quantum gates. It maps an n -qubit quantum state $|j\rangle$ as

$$|j\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi}{N} jk\right) |k\rangle, \quad (11)$$

N is a constant defined by the number of qubits $N = 2^n$, and j and k go from 0 to $N-1$.

Note that the input quantum state can be written as $|j\rangle$ where j is a decimal number spanning 0 to $N-1$ (as above), or, equivalently, it can be written as a binary number $|j\rangle = |j_1 j_2 \dots j_{n-1} j_n\rangle$, where each j_i take the value 0 or 1. As short-hand notation, this is sometimes written as the decimal value, e.g. $|10\rangle = |2\rangle$ or $|11\rangle = |3\rangle$.

In addition to knowing the mapping of the Quantum Fourier Transform, we also need to know how to implement it. For a single-qubit, the mapping of the QFT is:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^1}} \sum_{k=0}^{2^1-1} \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi}{2^1} 0 \times k\right) |k\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^1}} \sum_{k=0}^{2^1-1} \exp\left(i \frac{2\pi}{2^1} 1 \times k\right) |k\rangle = \frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (13)$$

This transformation corresponds to a Hadamard gate,

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

The figure below shows a graphical representation of the Quantum Fourier Transform for a single-qubit system (the notation $0.j_1$ in the exponent is a binary representation that will be introduced below).

Figure 1: Quantum Fourier Transformation

To understand how the Quantum Fourier Transformation works, Let us analyze the two-qubit case, $n=2$. The state $|j\rangle$ transforms to:

$$|j\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2}} \sum_{k=0}^{2^2-1} \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{2^2}jk\right) |k\rangle, \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2}} \left(\exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{2^2}j \times 0\right) |0\rangle + \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{2^2}j \times 1\right) |1\rangle \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{2^2}j \times 2\right) |2\rangle + \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{2^2}j \times 3\right) |3\rangle \right) \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

When the system is initialized in the ground state, $j=0$, the QFT leaves each qubit in the equal superposition state

$$\frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (17)$$

This is true for any number of qubits n . The QFT maps the ground state of n qubits into n equal superposition single-qubit states,

$$|00\dots 0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes \dots \otimes \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}. \quad (18)$$

The table below shows the output state corresponding to each of the values of j .

Table 2: output state

$j = 0$	$ 0\rangle$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2}} (0\rangle + 1\rangle + 2\rangle + 3\rangle)$
$j = 1$	$ 1\rangle$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2}} (0\rangle + \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}i\pi\right) 1\rangle + \exp(i\pi) 2\rangle + \exp\left(\frac{3}{2}i\pi\right) 3\rangle)$
$j = 2$	$ 2\rangle$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2}} (0\rangle + \exp(i\pi) 1\rangle + 2\rangle + \exp(i\pi) 3\rangle)$
$j = 3$	$ 3\rangle$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^2}} (0\rangle + \exp\left(\frac{3}{2}i\pi\right) 1\rangle + \exp(i\pi) 2\rangle + \exp\left(\frac{9}{2}i\pi\right) 3\rangle)$

When the system consists of more than one qubit and is not initialized in its ground state, the implementation of the QFT is not as simple as implementing Hadamards. To gain insight, Let us write the input and output states as the product of single-qubit states. The input state for an n qubit system is

$$\begin{aligned}
|j\rangle &= |j_1 j_2 \dots j_{n-1} j_n\rangle, \\
&= |j_1\rangle \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_{n-1}\rangle \otimes |j_n\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

and the output state is

$$\begin{aligned}
|k\rangle &= |k_1 k_2 \dots k_{n-1} k_n\rangle, \\
&= |k_1\rangle \otimes |k_2\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |k_{n-1}\rangle \otimes |k_n\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Next, we should write the indexes j and k in binary using the following procedure:

$$k = k_1 2^{n-1} + k_2 2^{n-2} + \dots + k_n 2^0 = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i 2^{n-i}, \tag{21}$$

and

$$\frac{j}{2^n} = j_1 2^{-1} + j_2 2^{-2} + \dots + j_n 2^{-n} \equiv 0.j_1 j_2 \dots j_n. \tag{22}$$

Note that the notation $0.j_1 j_2 \dots j_n$ is new, and the treatment of the entries is position dependent: that is, the position of the variable j_n to the right of the “0.” matters, and not it is subscript. For example, the following equivalences follow:

$$0.j_1 = j_1 2^{-1} \tag{23}$$

$$0.j_2 = j_2 2^{-2} \tag{24}$$

$$0.j_1 j_2 = j_1 2^{-1} + j_2 2^{-2} \tag{25}$$

$$0.j_2 j_4 = j_2 2^{-2} + j_4 2^{-4} \tag{26}$$

and so on.

Replacing the terms $k = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i 2^{n-i}$ and $\frac{j}{2^n} = 0.j_1 j_2 \dots j_n$ in equation (1), the n -qubit output state can be written as the product of n single-qubit states

$$\begin{aligned}
&|j_1\rangle \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_{n-1}\rangle \otimes |j_n\rangle \\
&\rightarrow \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_{n-1} j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \\
&\otimes \dots \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_2 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_1 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

The figure below shows a graphical representation of the Quantum Fourier Transform for an n -qubit system.

Figure 2: Quantum Fourier Transform

To understand how this new representation works, Let us go back to the n=2 example. The table below shows the output state corresponding to each of the values of j_1 and j_2 . Note, that these states are all written in the single-qubit basis $\{|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle\}$.

Table 3: output state

	binary to decimal	quantum states	
$j_1 = 0, j_2 = 0$	$00 \equiv 0\rangle$	$ 00\rangle = 0\rangle \otimes 0\rangle$	$\frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$
$j_1 = 0, j_2 = 1$	$01 \equiv 1\rangle$	$ 01\rangle = 0\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$\left(\frac{ 0\rangle+\exp(\pi i) 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \otimes \left(\frac{ 0\rangle+\exp(\pi i \frac{1}{2}) 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
$j_1 = 1, j_2 = 0$	$10 \equiv 2\rangle$	$ 10\rangle = 1\rangle \otimes 0\rangle$	$\left(\frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \otimes \left(\frac{ 0\rangle+\exp(\pi i) 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
$j_1 = 1, j_2 = 1$	$11 \equiv 3\rangle$	$ 11\rangle = 1\rangle \otimes 1\rangle$	$\left(\frac{ 0\rangle+\exp(\pi i) 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \otimes \left(\frac{ 0\rangle+\exp(\pi i \frac{3}{2}) 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$

(The binary to decimal column illustrates the connection to the table above, where the decimal short-hand notation was used.)

The single-qubit output states are transformed as:

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (28)$$

$$|1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + \exp(i\phi_m)|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (29)$$

where ϕ_m is a phase between 0 and 2π . If the input state is $|0\rangle$, then the output state is always an equal superposition state with zero relative phase. If the input state is $|1\rangle$, then the output is an equal superposition state, but with a phase shift $\exp(i\phi_m)$ on state $|1\rangle$. Specifically, for n qubits, the phase of the first output qubit is $\phi_1 = 2\pi 0.j_n$, the second is $\phi_2 = 2\pi 0.j_{n-1}j_n$, the third is $\phi_3 = 2\pi 0.j_{n-2}j_{n-1}j_n$, and so on until the last qubit which phase is $\phi_n = 2\pi 0.j_1 \dots j_n$.

There are two takeaways:

1. When the input state is $|0\rangle$, the output state is an equal superposition state with zero relative phases.
2. When the input state is $|1\rangle$, the output state is an equal superposition state that undergoes a relative phase rotation.

From these two points, it is clear that the implementation of the QFT is related to a controlled operation that modifies a qubit state, as shown in the table below.

From these two points, it is clear that the implementation of the QFT is related to a controlled operation that modifies a qubit state as shown in the table below.

Table 4: QFT

Controlled Operation	
Input state	Output state
$ 0\rangle$	$\frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$
$ 1\rangle$	$\frac{ 0\rangle+R_k 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$

The figure below shows the circuit implementation of the Quantum Fourier Transform in terms of multiple Hadamard gates and controlled R_k gates. The phase rotation R_k is defined as

$$R_k |0\rangle = |0\rangle, \quad (30)$$

$$R_k |1\rangle = \exp\left(i\frac{2\pi}{2^k}\right) |1\rangle. \quad (31)$$

Figure 3: Quantum Fourier Transform

Let us analyze how the system evolves under this implementation.

1. A Hadamard gate is applied on the first qubit

$$|j_1\rangle \rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad (32)$$

and this puts the system in the state

$$\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (33)$$

2. A controlled phase R_2 -gate is applied with the second qubit as control and the first as target,

$$\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1 j_2) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (34)$$

3. A controlled phase R_3 -gate is applied with the third qubit as control and the first as target,

$$\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1 j_2 j_3) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (35)$$

4. This continues until a controlled phase R_n -the gate is applied with the last qubit as control and the first as a target, leaving the system in the state

$$\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1 j_2 j_3 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (36)$$

5. A Hadamard gate is applied on the second qubit,

$$\left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1 j_2 j_3 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_2) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (37)$$

6. A controlled phase R_2 -gate is applied with the third qubit as control and the second as target,

$$\left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_1 j_2 j_3 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0 \cdot j_2 j_3) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (38)$$

7. This continues until a controlled phase R_{n-1} -gate is applied with the last qubit as control and the second as target, leaving the system in the state

$$\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_1 j_2 j_3 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes \frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_2 j_3 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \otimes |j_3\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_n\rangle. \quad (39)$$

8. This same process is done on each qubit until the last qubit, on which we can only apply a Hadamard gate. This implementation transforms as

$$\begin{aligned} & |j_1\rangle \otimes |j_2\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |j_{n-1}\rangle \otimes |j_n\rangle \\ & \rightarrow \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_1 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_2 \dots j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \\ & \otimes \dots \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_{n-1} j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + \exp(2\pi i 0.j_n) |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

However, the output states in equations (27) and (40) are not equal. The output state of the first qubit in (27) is equivalent to the output state of the last qubit in (40). The output state of the second qubit in (27) is equivalent to the output state of the penultimate qubit in (40). The state of qubit n in (40) should be the state of the first qubit in (27), the state of qubit $n-1$ in (40) should be the state of the second qubit (27), and so on. To return the qubit states to their original ordering, we need to apply swap-gates, which are generally used to exchange qubit states. Thus, the difference between the output states in equations (27) and (40) can be straightforwardly undone by applying a swap gate between qubits “1” and “ n ”, a swap gate between qubits “2” and “ $n-1$ ”, a swap gate between qubits “3” and “ $n-2$ ”, and so on [56].

Figure 4: RSA Cryptosystem, Factoring, and Shor's Algorithm Quantum Fourier Transform

7 Period Finding Algorithm

The quantum part of Shor's algorithm is called "period finding." In this section, we will discuss this quantum subroutine.

The period finding algorithm determines the period r of a periodic function $f(x) = f(x + r)$ from modular exponentiation. For example, to find the period of $f(x) = 2^x \pmod{15}$, we could test the function for different values of x from its smallest to its greatest value until we find the first x for which $f(x) = 2^x \pmod{15} = 1 \pmod{15}$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(0) &= 2^0 \pmod{15} = 1, \\
 f(1) &= 2^1 \pmod{15} = 2, \\
 f(2) &= 2^2 \pmod{15} = 4, \\
 f(3) &= 2^3 \pmod{15} = 8, \\
 f(4) &= 2^4 \pmod{15} = 1, \\
 f(5) &= 2^5 \pmod{15} = 2, \\
 f(6) &= 2^6 \pmod{15} = 4.
 \end{aligned}$$

From here, we can realize that the function's period is $r=4$ since the function's values start repeating after $x=4$. However, for large numbers, finding this period is difficult to implement by hand, but it is also inefficient to find the brute force on a classical computer. However, Shor's

algorithm provides an alternative, efficient method.

The quantum period-finding algorithm uses two registers of qubits. The first register is called the source register, and the second one the target register. If the number to be factorized using Shor's algorithm is N , then the number of qubits l in the first register has to satisfy

$$N^2 \leq 2^l \leq 2N^2. \quad (41)$$

The number of qubits in the first register should generate a state-space that is at least large enough to capture the maximum possible period. The larger the value of l , the more densely the solution-space that can be sampled, and thereby, the error in determining the period can be reduced. For simplicity, the number of qubits in the second register will be l .

1. The qubits in the both registers start in the $|0\rangle$ state. The first step is to apply Hadamard gates to the source register to create a large, equal superposition state. This is equivalently sometimes called a QFT, although a QFT is much less efficient to implement in general than a single Hadamard on each qubit. Whether written as Hadamards or as a QFT, the operation transforms the state of the source qubits:

$$\begin{aligned} |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \otimes \dots \otimes |0\rangle \otimes |0\rangle &\rightarrow \left(\frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \dots \\ &\dots \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \otimes \left(\frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

which can also be written as

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^l}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^l-1} |x\rangle, \quad (43)$$

where now $|0\rangle$ is in the l -qubit basis. This leaves the system in the state

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^l}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^l-1} |x\rangle |0\rangle \quad (44)$$

2. The unitary operation U_f is applied. This gate implements the modular exponentiation, $x \rightarrow f(x) = a^x \pmod N$, such that the system ends in the state

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^l}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^l-1} |x\rangle |a^x \pmod N\rangle. \quad (45)$$

From here, we can see that the result of the period function $f(x) = a^x \pmod N$ gets stored on the target register.

3. The second register is measured, and assume that this measurement projects the second register to the state $|f(x_0)\rangle = |a^{x_0} \pmod N\rangle$, where x_0 are the unique values of x in the first period of $f(x)$ values.

Now, remember that a periodic function with period r only takes r different values. The function $f(x)$ is unique for distinct periodic values of x ,

$$f(x_0) = f(r + x_0) = f(2r + x_0) = f(3r + x_0) = \dots = a^{x_0} \pmod N \quad (46)$$

If the second register is projected to $|f(x_0)\rangle$, the first register will be in a superposition of the states $|x\rangle$ for which $f(x) = a^{x_0} \pmod N$. For simplicity, Let us assume that there are $2^l/r$ different values of x for which $f(x) = a^{x_0} \pmod N$, such that

$$f(x_0) = f(r + x_0) = f(2r + x_0) = \dots = f\left(\frac{2^l}{r}r + x_0\right) = a^{x_0} \pmod N, \quad (47)$$

or

$$\sum_{y=0}^{2^l/r-1} f(yr + x_0) = a^{x_0} \pmod{N}, \quad (48)$$

with y an integer from 0 to $2^l/r - 1$. Once the second register is projected to $|f(x_0)\rangle$, state of the system can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^l/r}} \sum_{y=0}^{2^l/r-1} |yr + x_0\rangle |f(x_0)\rangle. \quad (49)$$

4. Even though the information of the period r is encoded in the first register, there is still one more step before being able to find its value. A (second) Quantum Fourier Transform is applied on the first register, this leaves the first register on the state

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{r}} \sum_{z=0}^{r-1} \exp\left(\frac{2\pi i}{r} z x_0\right) \left|z \frac{2^l}{r}\right\rangle. \quad (50)$$

5. The first register is measured, projecting the l -qubit system to the state $|C\rangle$, with $C = z2^l/r$. Knowing the value of C implies knowing the value of the ratio

$$\frac{C}{2^l} = \frac{z}{r}. \quad (51)$$

If z and r have no common divisors, $\gcd(z, r) = 1$, the ratio $C/2^l$ can be reduced to an irreducible fraction, as

$$\frac{C}{2^l} = a_0 + \frac{1}{a_1 + \frac{1}{a_2 + \frac{1}{\dots}}}. \quad (52)$$

The approximations to the ratio z/r can be computed by using the continued fraction expansion relations:

$$\begin{aligned} z_0 &= a_0, \\ r_0 &= 1, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} z_n &= a_n z_{n-1} + z_{n-2}, \\ r_n &= a_n r_{n-1} + r_{n-2}. \end{aligned}$$

6. Different values for z_j and r_j are tested, until one finds values such that $\gcd(z_j, r_j) = 1$. For the valid values of r_j , the function $f(x) = a^x \pmod{N}$ is evaluated with $x = r_j$. If $f(r_j) = 1$, then the period of f is r_j ; otherwise, we have to go back to step 1.

To understand how this algorithm works, Let us find the period of the function $f(x) = 11^x \pmod{21}$.

We start by choosing the number of qubits in each register. For the first register, the number l has to satisfy $21^2 \leq 2^l \leq 2 \times 21^2$ or $441 \leq 2^l \leq 882$. Let us consider that each register has $l = 9$ qubits.

1. All the qubits start in the ground state $|0\rangle$. A Hadamard gate is applied on each one of the qubits on the first register. This transforms the state of the first register as

$$|0\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9}} \sum_{x=0}^{2^9-1} |x\rangle. \quad (53)$$

This leaves the system in the state

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9}} \sum_{x=0}^{511} |x\rangle |0\rangle, \quad (54)$$

Where $|0\rangle$ represents the ground state of 9 qubits.

2. The unitary operation U_f is applied, leaving the system in the state

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9}} \sum_{x=0}^{511} |x\rangle |11^x \bmod 21\rangle \quad (55)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9}} (|0\rangle |11^0 \bmod 21\rangle + |1\rangle |11^1 \bmod 21\rangle + |2\rangle |11^2 \bmod 21\rangle) \quad (56)$$

$$+ \dots + (|509\rangle |11^{509} \bmod 21\rangle + |510\rangle |11^{510} \bmod 21\rangle + |511\rangle |11^{511} \bmod 21\rangle) \quad (57)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9}} (|0\rangle |1\rangle + |1\rangle |11\rangle + |2\rangle |16\rangle + \dots + |509\rangle |2\rangle + |510\rangle |1\rangle + |511\rangle |11\rangle) \quad (58)$$

3. Assume the second register is measured, projecting it into the state $|f(2)\rangle = |16\rangle$. This leaves the first register in

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9/r}} \sum_{y=0}^{2^9/r-1} |yr+2\rangle |16\rangle \quad (59)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9/r}} \left(|2\rangle + |r+2\rangle + |2r+2\rangle + \dots + \left| \left(\frac{2^9}{r} - 1 \right) r + 2 \right\rangle \right) |16\rangle \quad (60)$$

4. A Quantum Fourier Transform is applied on the first register such that

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^9/r}} \sum_{y=0}^{2^9/r-1} |yr+2\rangle |16\rangle \rightarrow \frac{1}{\sqrt{r}} \sum_{z=0}^{r-1} \exp\left(2 \frac{2\pi i}{r} z\right) \left| z \frac{2^9}{r} \right\rangle. \quad (61)$$

5. Assume the first register is measured, projecting it into the state $|427\rangle$. The irreducible fraction of the ratio $C/2^9$ is given by

$$\frac{C}{2^l} = \frac{427}{2^9} = 0 + \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{5 + \frac{1}{42 + \frac{1}{2 + \frac{1}{\dots}}}}}. \quad (62)$$

Note that we can calculate this irreducible fraction in Wolfram Alpha by typing in the bar “continued fraction of 427/512.”

6. The values z_j and r_j are tested for the condition $\gcd(z_j, r_j) = 1$ with j from 0 to 3,
 $\gcd(z_0, r_0) = \gcd(0, 1) = 1,$
 $\gcd(z_1, r_1) = \gcd(1, 1) = 1,$
 $\gcd(z_2, r_2) = \gcd(5, 6) = 1,$
 $\gcd(z_3, r_3) = \gcd(427, 512) = 1.$

The function $f(x) = 11^x \bmod 21$ is evaluated for different valid values of r_j ,
 $f(1) = 11^1 \bmod 21 = 11$
 $f(6) = 11^6 \bmod 21 = 1$
 $f(512) = 11^{512} \bmod 21 = 16$

With this result, we can conclude that the period of the function f is $r=6$.

8 Shor's Algorithm: Reduction of Factoring to Order Finding

In the next text units, we will take a deep dive into several details behind Shor's algorithm, including a discussion of the reduction of factoring to order finding, the related Simon's algorithm that helped inspire Shor's algorithm, and the use of Shor's algorithm to perform order finding.

How do we get factoring from order finding? So, first, let say the second-fastest classical algorithm is the quadratic sieve. So, we would say most classical algorithms [57]. So, suppose we have N equals P times Q . They work in more general cases, but we will just worry about the case of two products. So, the first step, really the only step, the trick is to find x squared congruent to y squared mod N x not congruent to plus or minus y mod N . So, suppose we are trying to factor 21. we get 4 is congruent to 25 mod 21, right? Because 25 minus 4 is a multiple of 21. So, 4, these are both squares. Moreover, now we have 5 minus 2 times 5 plus 2 is congruent to zero mod 21. whenever this happens, one of these contains P , and the other contains Q . Or rather, whenever neither of these is 0, we have a product of two numbers, which is zero mod 21. Thus, we know that the product has to contain three somewhere, and it has to contain somewhere. If neither of these factors is 0 mod 21, 3 has to be contained in one factor and 7 in the other. Then, what we can do is we can use Euclid's algorithm for GCD to get P and Q . So, we are essentially done whenever we get two squares, which are equal to each other. This is how the quadratic sieve works. That is the second-fastest classical factoring algorithm known. How do we find x squared y squared? Well, let us look at the function f of x equals g to the x mod N . So, this is periodic. If g to the r is congruent to 1, then g to the x plus r is congruent to g to the x mod N . Because if g to the r plus is congruent to 1, then g to the x plus r congruent to g to the x because it is just multiplying both sides of this by g to the x . So, that says that f of x is periodic. We mean, it has to start repeating some time because there are only N possible things here. Whenever it starts repeating, we get a g to the x plus r congruent to g to the x . that means g to the r is congruent to 1. g to the r over 2 squared is congruent to 1 squared if r is even. So, let us do an example. Suppose we are trying to factor 21. So, 2 to the 0, 2 to the first, 2 squared. So, this is 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32. 32 minus 21 is 11, so, the next column then is 11. 22 minus 21 is 1. 1. So, 2 to the sixth is congruent to 1 mod 21. That means 2 cubed minus 1 minus time 2 cubed plus 1 is congruent to 0 mod 21. this is 7, and this is 9. 7 contains the factor 7, 9 contains the factor 3. So, the question is, how can this go wrong? Moreover, well, there is a couple of things that could go wrong. We could have started with 4. 4, 16. 16 squared, well, we know 2 to the sixth is congruent to 1 mod 21. So, 4 cubed is congruent to 1 mod 21. So, we get 4 cubed is congruent to 1 mod 21. 4 to the 3/2 does not exist. Well, we cannot compute it. So, this shows that 4 could go wrong. The only thing that could go wrong is we could do this. When we look at the middle element, it is minus 1. that would be a problem because then we have x equal to minus y mod N . we cannot use that, we cannot use this trick then. So, some things can go wrong, but the great theorem is the probability of success with g to the x th is greater than or equal to 1/2 for a random g between 0 or a random g less than N . So, we choose a random g less than N . we do this repeated squaring. The probability this will work is at least 1/2. If it does not work, we choose another random g . So, eventually, with high probability, we will get a g , which lets us factor.

9 Introduction to the Shor Quantum Factoring Algorithm

we discovered the factoring algorithm after seeing Simon's algorithm before Simon's algorithm got published. We are going to show we write down a circuit diagram so we can see the similarity.

So, Simon's algorithm, remember, we started with n qubits in the plus. Then we went, and here is a black box that computes f of x . From x , it computes f of x . then we did a Hadamard transform to the n , which is just the quantum Fourier transform over the group of two elements to the n -th power. So, n copies of the group of two elements. So, this is just binary strings under addition without carries. After that, we believe we measured this register, and then did classical post-processing. So, what is factoring? So, what we are not going to do directly is a quantum algorithm for factoring. We are going to do a quantum algorithm for an order finding a quantum algorithm for periodicity. So, suppose we have a function over integers, f of x is equal to f of x plus c for some c . here we can see that f of $x + 2c$ equals f of x plus $3c$. So, it is a periodic function, and a period is well, we call it C right now, but at some point during this section, we are going to start calling it r because that is what we used to call it. Find c . Now we might think this is easy. We just start with f of 0 , f of 1 , f of 2 , f of 3 , and keep on going until f starts repeating. So, even if the period is exponentially long. That means that if we want to try to find a period of length r , we can do this length polynomial and \log of r . So, we can find the period. On the classical computer, if we have a black-box function, the best thing we can do is to keep on testing values until it starts repeating. So, that means the best we can do is period r . in quantum mechanics, quantum computing, we can do $\log r$. So, it is going to be exponentially long in a period of a number we want to factor. However, if we are just finding a period, find a period in time O of $\log c$. So, we will be able to find the period and time well, that is going to be quicker than $\log c$ if we want to do it quicker. $\log c$ squared if we want to do it quickly because we cannot use the exact quantum Fourier transform, but the approximate quantum Fourier transform, which has like $\log c$, $\log \log c$ gates But here, so, we want to find a period. We have a black box function for f . f has some period of c . So, what is the quantum algorithm for this? Well, we are going to do the same thing here. We are going to start at plus to the c , 0 , the n here. Here we have a black-box function, which, if we put in x , computes f of x . Alternatively, actually, it computes well, remember this took x , t to x , t x r f of x . we can assume this does the same thing. x , t to x t x r f of x . nowhere is the only difference, really, between the circuits. We use the quantum for each transform over 2 to the actual, let us do this right. There is $2n$. We want $2n$ qubits, n qubits here. Quantum Fourier transforms over 2 to the n . then we measure. Then we do classical post-processing. So, it looks very similar. So, let us go into detail, in both these cases, what happens to the bottom branch? We do nothing to the bottom branch. We mean that we could measure the bottom branch and throw away the results if we want to. Alternatively, we do not have to. If we measure something and throw away the results, it does not matter whether we measure it. However, we do need to compute it. Because if we do not compute it, what have we done? We have taken the Hadamard transform of x to the n . That is just all 0 's. So, if we do not compute f of x , it destroys the interference in the upper half. Again, action in a quantum circuit has back action.

10 Simon's Algorithm

In 1994, Daniel Simon posed the following question: Does a particular function map distinct input elements to unique output elements hence representing a permutation or a one-to-one mapping function or, does it follow a two-to-one mapping scheme? Despite the problem's small practical importance, it is a quantum algorithm that exhibits an exponential speedup. Simon's algorithm served as an inspiration for Peter Shor and his famous quantum algorithm for period finding.

Simon's algorithm addresses a particular black-box function $f : \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^n$, which is known to map inputs in either a one-to-one or two-to-one manner. Two distinct input bit strings

$a_1, a_2 \in \{0, 1\}^n$ are mapped to the same output $f(a_1) = f(a_2)$ if:

1. the two bit strings a_1 and a_2 are equivalent a one-to-one function, or
2. there exists a bit string $s \neq 0^n$ such that $a_1 \oplus s = a_2$ - a two-to-one function.

If there exists a single $s \neq 0^n$, the mapping is “two-to-one” and otherwise (if $s = 0^n$ works) it is “one-to-one”. Simon’s algorithm finds the bit string s and the type of function mapping exponentially faster than known classical algorithms.

The algorithm starts with the initialization of $2n$ qubits in their ground state. Subsequently, half the qubits are rotated with a Hadamard gate to form an equal superposition state. Thereafter, the oracle function U_f is applied on all qubits. A second Hadamard gate is applied to the same qubits that received the first Hadamard gate, and then the qubits are read out. The mathematical description of the protocol can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
|0\rangle \dots |0\rangle &= |0^n\rangle|0^n\rangle \xrightarrow{H^{\otimes n} I^{\otimes n}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n}} \sum_{a \in \{0,1\}^n} |a\rangle|0^n\rangle \\
&\xrightarrow{U_f} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n}} \sum_{a \in \{0,1\}^n} |a\rangle|f(a)\rangle \\
&\xrightarrow{H^{\otimes n} I^{\otimes n}} \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{b \in \{0,1\}^n} \sum_{a \in \{0,1\}^n} (-1)^{a \cdot b} |a\rangle|f(a)\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

if $f(a_1) = f(a_2) \rightarrow a_1 \oplus s = a_2$:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{b \in \{0,1\}^n} \sum_{a_1 \in A} ((-1)^{a_1 \cdot b} + (-1)^{a_1 \oplus s \cdot b}) |a_1\rangle |f(a_1)\rangle \\
&\frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{b \in \{0,1\}^n} \sum_{a_1 \in A} (-1)^{a_1 \cdot b} (1 + (-1)^{s \cdot b}) |a_1\rangle |f(a_1)\rangle \\
&\quad \text{summands} \neq 0 \quad \text{only if } s \cdot b = 0 : \\
&\frac{1}{2^{n-1}} \sum_{b \in \{0,1\}^n \ \& \ s \cdot b = 0} \sum_{a_1 \in A} (-1)^{a_1 \cdot b} |a_1\rangle |f(a_1)\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{63}$$

The detectable states non-zero coefficients fulfill the condition of $s \cdot b = s_1 b_1 \oplus \dots \oplus s_{n-1} b_{n-1} = 0$ a dot product modulo 2. To determine s with high accuracy it is necessary to repeat the algorithm to acquire $n-1$ linearly independent b_1, \dots, b_{n-1} . Upon repeated runs of the algorithm, equations $s \cdot b_1 = 0, \dots, s \cdot b_{n-1} = 0$ enable a classical calculation of the solution s' . If $f(s') = f(0^n)$ holds, the black box function maps its input states in a two-to-one manner. In contrast, if $f(s') \neq f(0^n)$ with $s' \neq 0^n$, the derived s' is not a valid solution. Therefore, only $s = 0^n$ satisfies $f(s') = f(0^n)$ and the function is one-to-one. Simon’s algorithm is optimal and yields an answer after $\mathcal{O}(n)$ queries. In contrast, a classical algorithm requires at least $\mathcal{O}(2^{n/2})$ queries.

Both Simon and Shor’s algorithms are related to finding the order or the period of a function of interest. In Simon’s algorithm, this is accomplished through quantum interference induced by Hadamard gates and multiple measurements. In Shor’s algorithm, the period finding is accomplished using the quantum Fourier transform.

Figure 5: SS Algorithm

11 Shor's Algorithm: Detailed Steps of the Quantum Order Finding Algorithm

What is the algorithm in detail? So, suppose we have a bound on r we should call it r_{\max} and choose a power of 2 bigger than $2r_{\max}$. Well, we will write down the algorithm. We start with plus to the $2l$ 0. That is here. Next, we take the compute f with x . We know that whatever ends in the first register, we compute it in the second register. However, this is just sum i equals 0 to 2 to the $2l$. i , where i is just the binary representation of the number. We need to divide by 2 to the l because we want this to be a unit vector. So, we compute f . So, this becomes sum to the $2l$ i f of i . i equals 0 to 2 to the $2l$. Do the quantum Fourier transform. So, that is 1 over to 2 to the $2l$ summation. We know i is a really bad letter to use because it is also the square root of minus 1. So, let us use x . So, the quantum Fourier transform takes x to, let us call it, z f of x . z equals 0 to 2 to the $2l$ minus 1. e to the $2\pi i xz$ over 2 to the $2l$. So, we have taken x and taken the Fourier transform of it, which gives us this. Now, what happens if we measure f of x ? well, we are going to get some value for f of x . we are going to leave that out the normalization constant for the time being because figuring out exactly What is going on with a normalization constant is possible, but it is much tedious algebra. We will come back to it later. So, without a normalized, z equals 0 through 2 to the $2l$. Let x_0 be the smallest x giving f of x . So, this is going to be z of the form x_0 plus y times π . Because when we measure f of x , we only get z no, not z . When we measure f of x , we only get x equals x_0 plus yr f of x_0 z e to the 2 minus $2\pi i$ x well, xz , but x is of the form x_0 plus yrz over 2 to the $2l$. So, what did we do? We measured f of x here. We are just looking at the ones who give us f of x_0 . We know all of these x 's are the form x_0 plus yr . The phase factor does not change, and z does not change. So, now we have the sum. We have to figure out how big it is. Well, we can write sum z equals 0 through 2 to the $2l$.

Sum y equals 0 through 2 to the $2l$ over r , plus or minus 1 here, but that does not matter. f of $x_0 z e$ to the $2\pi i x_0$ plus yz over 2 to the $2l$. What is this? This is a geometric sum.

12 Shor's Algorithm: Order Finding Algorithm Measurement Result as a Geometric Sum

So, first, we will do the intuition, and then we will do the math. So, it is a geometric sum, and it is a whole bunch of points around the unit circle. So, we start with e to the minus $2\pi i x_0$. Let us plot these points minus $2\pi i x_0$. now we go r, z over to the 2 to the $2l$. So, the next one we want to plot is y equals 1. So, we go some distance around the circle. Let us plot another point. Then we plot another point, another point, another point. We keep ongoing. What we get is quite possibly points that are exactly uniformly distributed over the unit circle, sum close 0. well, and next, what happens is, here was e to the $2\pi i x_0$ 2 to the $2l$. Here is e to the minus $2\pi i x_0$ plus yz zero over 2 to the $2l$. So, unless what happens is when we plot the point, we move around by the angle $2\pi i yz$ over 2 to the $2l$. Suppose this angle is tiny. Well, what happens then is we get points uniformly distributed. Suppose it is tiny enough so, that when we add all of these 2 to the l over r points, we get points that are we know, some kind of an arc, which does not even go all the way around the unit circle sum is close to well, how many points were there? There were 2 to the $2l$ over r . they were all pointing in more or less the same direction. So, an absolute value. So, there are two cases here. $2\pi i yz$ If $2\pi i yz$ over 2 to the $2l$ is close to 1, which means yz over 2 to the $2l$ is close to an integer. Let us call that integer d . So, if this is close to an integer, then we get a large probability of seeing this. If it is not close to an integer, we get a tiny probability of seeing it. So, the geometric sum is $1 - e$ to the $2\pi i$. we want the last term of the sum. So, that is 2 to the $2l$ yz over 2 to the $2l$. No, it is y goes from 1 to 2 to the $2l$ over r . So, the last term we substitute in 2 to the $2l$ r over z . So, something like 2 to the $2l$ over r . we will have to take the floor of that time r times z over 2 to the $2l$. Which really, because of this floor could be anywhere on the unit circle. However, it is always less than 2 in absolute value. We are dividing that by $1 - e$ to the $2\pi i yz$ over 2 to the $2l$. Remember, the sum is, so we are dividing something by something else. It is going to be relatively small unless something else we are dividing is close to 0. So, this is roughly something O of 1 divided by oh, what is this? This is rough yz over 2 to the $2l$. The probability of seeing a number z is rough yz over 2 to the $2l$ squared minus d because d was the integer. So, we have d over r is roughly z over 2 to the $2l$. So, what the algorithm does is it output z . we know 2 to the $2l$, and we need to round it off to something like d over r . there is a procedure for rounding real numbers of two smaller fractions that is efficient. It is called continuous fractions. However, it is a classical algorithm. So, once we get this, we can round it to d over r , and then we are found r , which was the period we were looking for.

13 Demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm: Introduction

In the next several sections, we will explore two demonstrations of Shor's algorithm on small-scale quantum-computers realized using liquid-state NMR and trapped ions. Although the numbers of qubits and the number being factored is rather small ($15 = 3 \times 5$), the demonstrations illustrate that Shor's algorithm works in principle. We will also discuss how many demonstrations have used "compiled" versions of Shor's algorithm that are not generalizable.

To date, there have been a handful of prototype demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm using different qubit modalities, including nuclear spins, photonic qubits, superconducting qubits [58],

and trapped ions. In this section, we will look at two of these demonstrations in detail. The first is a demonstration of Shor’s Algorithm using liquid-state nuclear magnetic resonance, NMR. This was, in fact, the first such experimental demonstration, and it showed the factorization of 15 into the primes 3 times 5. It used molecules with seven individually addressable nuclear spins in a liquid solution at room temperature, and the algorithm comprised a sequence of around 300 pulses. we will discuss this work. The second demonstration is recent, and it was performed using trapped ions [59]. In this case, seven ions were used to again factor the number 15 into primes 3 and 5. In this example, modular multiplication was implemented, and no simplifications presumed prior knowledge of the result were employed. Instead, a concept called qubit recycling was used to make up for the fact that seven qubits are insufficient to implement the general algorithm. Still, to date, this demonstration constitutes the most realistic implementation of Shor’s Algorithm. MIT Professor Isaac Chuang participated in this demonstration with Professor Rainer Blatt’s team at Innsbruck. To factor 15 in a straightforward manner, it is estimated that one needs about 12 qubits, eight qubits in the period register, and four qubits in the modular multiplication register. The demonstrations we will discuss in this study had fewer than 12 qubits, and so, certain simplifications had to be made. Now in many cases, the simplifications were quite reasonable. For example, the use of qubit recycling. Nonetheless, it is important to understand the impact of various types of simplifying assumptions. Finally, from a business perspective, these prototype demonstrations of Shor’s Algorithm illustrate that quantum computing is real. Although these implementations are not yet at scale, they are concrete indications of and steps towards the promise of quantum computing. From an engineering perspective, these types of demonstrations force groups to confront practical realities of implementation, from qubit control engineering to algorithmic compilation. Although not yet at scale, these algorithms motivate experimental groups to go beyond scientific demonstrations and to meet face-to-face with the practical realities that will need to be accommodated to enable scalable quantum computing. scientifically, these demonstrations test the knowledge of system noise [60,61] and decoherence [62]. Lastly, from a technology standpoint, these demonstrations serve as a benchmark of progress in the field, indicating where the technology currently stands and clarifying what needs to be addressed in order to reach future milestones. With that brief introduction, let us discuss.

14 Demonstrations of Shor’s Algorithm: Shor’s Algorithm with NMR

In 1998, after implementation of the first two-qubit algorithms on the chloroform molecule and using NMR, Isaac Chuang, who supervised the research, gave a great challenge to factor the number 15 within the time span of Ph.D. at Stanford. At that time, Isaac Chuang was transitioning from Los Alamos National Laboratory to the IBM Almaden Research Center outside San Jose. He was finishing the first year of Ph.D. at Stanford. At that time, Isaac set up his new lab at Almaden, some 30 minutes away from Stanford. Researcher did not know what it would take to factor the number 15, but it did seem like a great challenge. certainly, it was clear that there was an enormous interest in Shor’s Algorithm and that it was a major driver for the field. So, we thought it would be very awesome to demonstrate Shor’s Algorithm experimentally. So, what would it take to run Shor’s Algorithm experimentally? The simplest instance of quantum factoring is to factor the number 15, to pull it apart into 3 times 5. However, how many qubits does that take, and how many operations? we got great insight from a pedagogical article by Dave Beckman from the Preskill group at Caltech. In particular, he analyzed the steps for factoring the number 15. Shor’s algorithm, in general, consists of two parts, a classical part and the quantum mechanical part. The quantum part that we run on the quantum computer is designed

to find the period of a function, specifically the function a to the power x modulo N , that is to say, the remainder after division of a to the x by N . N here is the number we are trying to factor. A number can be anything as long as it is co-prime with N , and x is the function's argument. For period finding on a quantum computer, we divide the number of qubits into two registers. One register needs to be large enough that it can store the number N . For 15, we need four bits, so, four qubits are needed for that register. The other register, in principle, needs to be twice as large or eight qubits, bringing the total to 12 qubits to factor the number 15. The algorithm consists of, first, a Hadamard operation that prepares an equal superposition of all the states of the first register then a function call of the function a to the x modulo N where x is the states of the first register. the result is mapped into the state of the second register. the third step is the Quantum Fourier Transform applied to the first register. At the end of the computation, we read out this first register. Now, if we begin to analyze how to implement this complex function a to the x modulo N , we realize that it can be broken apart into multiple simpler operations. Each of them is an operation controlled by just one bit out of all the bits of the first register. then we find for the number 15 that we are lucky. Only two of the control qubits play a role in factoring 15. in some cases, some choices of a , even just one of the control qubits, plays a role. So, that allows us to eliminate many qubits of the first register. In principle, we could eliminate all of them except two. We decided that for a meaningful Quantum Fourier Transform, we would like to have not just two qubits but three qubits. With two qubits, the Quantum Fourier Transform comes down to a single two-qubit gate. we thought that was too trivial. So, in the end, we went with an experiment with a total of seven qubits to factor the number 15. So, in NMR, the qubits are represented by the nuclear spins in the molecule, the spins of the atomic nuclei in a molecule. For a successful molecule for NMR qubit experiments, the molecule needs to have rather unusual properties. we need what we call large chemical shifts. That is to say, large separations in frequency between all the spins we want to get involved in the computation for selective addressing of the qubits. and we want a coupling network that allows sufficient pairs of qubits, pairs of spins, to be coupled to each other so that all the required two-qubit gates can be implemented on the molecule. So, a staff member at IBM Almaden did an extensive search looking through fast tables and documents with tabulated NMR properties of known molecules. after spending days in this process, he concluded that none of the tabulated molecules were good enough for the experiment that were attempting. However, there was one that came close. It consisted of a backbone of four carbon atoms. surrounding it, there were five fluorine atoms that all could serve as a spin one-half and provide a qubit. besides, there was an iron complex. The iron complex created asymmetry in the molecule so that the resonance frequencies of the five fluorine atoms would be separated. To go from five fluorine spins to seven, what we needed to do was to isotopically label two of the carbon spins so that they became carbon-13 and also acquired a spin one-half. Synthesizing this molecule was a real tour de force. Greg Breyta, IBM staff member who usually worked on chemical synthesis in the Resist program, spent over one year trying to synthesize this molecule. at any point in time in this multi-step synthesis, they did not know if this next step would be successful. However, finally, after more than a year, actually just in time, when they were ready to try the experiment, he delivered the molecule. So, the next challenge was to develop the control techniques to take the seven spins through the steps of Shor's Algorithm, to make them do the spin dance with a great degree of control. Here we could benefit from decades of technology development in NMR spectroscopy, where people were interested in revealing the structure of molecules they were synthesizing. Mark Sherwood done great work on NMR spectroscopy at IBM. In the years that followed in 1999 and 2000, we did experiments with the first two, then three, and five spins to discuss how to control the time evolution of increasing spins. They were all coupled together. Nevertheless, the factoring experiment became clear beyond anything that anyone had ever done in terms of controlling

many coupled quantum spins. It required more than 300 radio frequency pulses, specially tailored in amplitude and phase, to allow selective addressing of each of the seven spins. Also, we had to account for unintended phase shifts that occurred on any of the qubits when we drove any other qubits. In addition to that, since we were competing against the decoherence timescale, we had to apply simultaneous rotations where crosstalk effects were even more severe. we had to account for those as well. then finally, in NMR in these molecules, the couplings are always on. So, we had to use some sophisticated so, called decoupling sequences that effectively remove the effect of all the couplings except the one coupling that we needed to run a two-qubit gate between two spins. So, together with Matthias Stephan, fellow Ph.D. student at Stanford, who started one year after, they went out to try and control the seven spins, starting in September of 2000. throughout that fall and the winter of 2001, they made much progress. they used a variant NMR four-channel spectrometer to control the seven spins. after some time, they were far enough that the output spectra revealed the information about the period of a to the x modulo 15. from that, they could say that they had factored 15. At the same time, they were disappointed because the output spectra, even though they did give us the right information, they did not look like what ideally expected. even though they added more and more sophistication in the control techniques, it seemed like they were hitting a wall. At some point, they set out to write a model to capture the main effects of decoherence simply. there it was, beautifully reproducing the experimental spectra, the simulated spectra accounting for decoherence. It was interesting because, in the four years of experience programming NMR sequences and operating on molecules, this was the first time that decoherence had become the limiter. The relationship between duration, strength, and phase of our pulses and their ultimate effect on rotations? so, we can think of operations on a single qubit in terms of a Bloch sphere, or the planet earth, and so we call the North Pole the ground state, state zero. We call the South Pole state one, and those are just classical states, zero, one. But anywhere else on the Bloch sphere, or think of it as planet earth, anywhere else on the earth, we are in a superposition of zero and one. so, we can perform rotations by applying resonant pulses to the qubit, and that will effectively rotate this Bloch vector around the planet earth. So, Let us say we start at the North Pole, and if we, so first we will discuss about duration and strength of the RF pulses. Basically, the amount of rotation we going to get is the area under this pulse. So, it is both the duration, as well as the amplitude of the pulse that matters. Now, we often apply a Gaussian-shaped pulse, or some kind of smoothly-shaped pulse. But if we think of it as a rectangle, then it is very easy to just say, look, it is the duration of the pulse, times the amplitude of the pulse, and we can rotate a given amount of degrees around a certain axis, and we can do that for a short, poll pulse, or we can do that for a very long pulse that is got a low amplitude. As long as they have the same area, we going to rotate the same amount. If we want to rotate further, similarly, we can increase the amplitude more, or we can keep the amplitude fixed, and increase the duration more. So again, it is the area under the pulse that matters, that is going to determine how far we rotate around the Bloch sphere. so, one of the first things that an experimentalist will do is calibrate their pulses, and part of what that means is understanding what duration and amplitude do we need to rotate 90 degrees? And what do we need to rotate 180 degrees? so that has to do with the amount of rotation. Now the second question is, what axis am we rotating around? And so, the, if we think of the, equator around the Bloch sphere, or around the earth, we can put an x and a y axis on here. so x is going to point in one direction, and y will be 90 degrees away from that, pointing in a perpendicular direction. there is plus and minus x, and there is plus and minus y. Now, when we apply this microwave pulse, we can generate that pulse using IQ mixing. so we means in-phase, Q means quadrature, and basically, what this allows us to do is output a pulse where the microwave tone that is resonant with our qubit transition is [63, 64], has zero phase shift with respect to the source, that would be the end phase channel. Or, we

can use the quadrature channel, and output same pulse shape, but with the microwave shifted within that envelope by 90 degrees, And when we use the in phase, the in phase port, then what we will do is we will rotate around the x-axis. when we use the quadrature port, which shifts the microwaves by 90 degrees, we will rotate around the y-axis. so that is basically how the phase of the RF pulses will effect the rotation. It determines what axis these rotations are going to occur around. Now we might say, how do we know what is the x-axis to begin with? It turns out that there is always this relative phase offset that people discuss about. it is a little bit of jargon but, in quantum mechanics, and so, what sets the x-axis, basically, is our first pulse, right? So if our first pulse, Let us say it is got zero phase, we will rotate around a given axis. That axis becomes our x-axis, right? And everything relative to that, now, is either in-phase with that, or in quadrature with that, and if it is in-phase, we will rotate around that axis, and we call it x, and if we are in quadrature with that, we will rotate around the y-axis.

15 Demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm: Perspective on NMR

So, let us reflect on what made this experiment successful. The first is that the coherence times, the t_2 's in this specially designed molecule, were exceptionally long all more than 1 second. We have to compare, the coherence time to the time scale of the operations that form a single qubit-shaped pulse here varied between 0.2 and 2 milliseconds. We also have to compare to the value of the coupling strings between the spins in the molecule. They varied from about a hertz, which was too low to be usable, to about 200 hertz. In total, the longest sequences we had to run to implement Shor's Algorithm lasted about 700 milliseconds. The second success factor is that in these experiments, we used liquid state NMR based on ensembles of many copies of a molecule, making the detection trivially easy, almost, compared to the great challenge of trying to work with individual spins as is done today. Furthermore, the liquid state NMR Hamiltonian is relatively transparent and simple. All the terms in the Hamiltonian commute with each other. Single qubit terms have to form $\omega \sigma_z$. the two-qubit interactions have to form $J \sigma_z \otimes \sigma_z$ on one qubit and σ_z on another qubit. Scaling this approach, however, is hard. First, we have already commented on the difficulty of finding a suitable molecule with seven spins. Moreover, finding molecules with larger numbers of qubits, with larger numbers of suitable spins, to solve more complex problems quickly gets extremely difficult. However, there is a more fundamental and severe limitation to the liquid state NMR approach, and it is that even though we work in large magnetic fields, the fact that we use liquid states pushes us to work at large temperatures. We operated at room temperature. Nuclear spins in a magnetic field at room temperature are in a highly mixed state, that is to say, the probability for a spin to start in the upstate or the downstate are almost equal. We used techniques developed in the community to prepare so-called, effectively pure states. These are states that produce a signal that is proportional to that of a pure state, but the cost of this technique is that the signal is halved for every qubit that we add. Thus, this induces exponential cost that offsets any exponential gain that we hope to get from the quantum algorithms [65]. The NMR experiments, and in particular the short experiment, had been great fun. Furthermore, we think we discussed a great deal from it that also benefit and still benefits, today, the community. However, certainly, we wanted to move to technology, where the potential for scaling was far better. We decided to move from nuclear spins to electron spins and from molecules to artificial molecules. The artificial molecules we make use of are built from Silicon quantum dots in which we can find individual electrons and use their spins as qubits [66]. Similar to the NMR molecules, these electron spins in silicon offer long coherence times [67], but the devices are much more scalable, and the control, in the end, can take us much further. Matthias Stephan, instead, chose to work on superconducting qubits,

and he was one of the early members of the IBM team working on superconducting qubits, a very large and successful program today. Isaac Chuang finally decided to move to trapped ions. He set up a lab at MIT, and in collaboration with the group of Reiner Blatt. Some years later. They redid the factoring experiments a beautiful experiment implementing the factoring of 15 on trapped ions. As for the silicon spins that we work, we set state of the art earlier this year in implementing for the first time, in this type of system, again, a two-qubit algorithm. It brought back great memories from '98. However, different from the NMR approach and these early memories, the expectation is that with the group at QuTech in Delft and close collaboration with Intel, with the silicon spin qubits, we can go much beyond factoring 15.

16 Demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm: Quantum Factoring With Trapped Ions - Ion Trapping System

Shor's quantum factoring algorithm has been implemented by several physical systems, including trapped ions. Let us consider what was done and why. Perhaps the most important starting point is to consider the question, what is the smallest meaningful instance of the Shor quantum factoring algorithm? Recall that the intent of Shor's factoring algorithm is to compute the period of this function, f of x equals a to the x mod N . In this expression, N is a number we wish to factor. x is the argument to the function. a is a random number, which is chosen that co-prime to N . It shares no prime factors in common with N . The period of this function, r , allows us to find with some probability, a high probability, a factor of N , which is non-trivial. Quantum factoring, thus, has as a goal finding this period, r . Solving this problem takes an amount of time, or several operations roughly proportional to L^3 where L is the number of digits of the number N . Classically, using the best-known algorithm, the time required, or several operations required roughly go as $e^{L/3}$. The difficulty of this factoring problem is at the root of what secures widely used cryptosystems, such as RSA. To appreciate the smallest meaningful instance of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm, it is helpful to review the quantum circuit for the algorithm. Recall that there are two registers, the top one here, which holds the value x in a superposition of all possible values, and a bottom register, where the result of the modular exponentiation is held. The top register is then fed three inverse Quantum Fourier Transform, which returns the result. There are three main steps in this procedure. First, the input superposition of the top register must be created. Second, the modular exponentiation, a to the x mod N , must be computed. It is the most difficult part of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm because multi-qubit gates are required. The third step is a Quantum Fourier Transform. because the result of the Fourier transform is measured, only single-qubit gates, some of them controlled by classical results, are required in principle. After the result is measured, there are some classical post-processing. this can be done by essentially any classical computer. Now, the number we are factoring is N . And it is clear that the algorithm is too trivial when N is an even number. That is, it has a factor, which is 2. Thus, the smallest meaningful factors are 3 and 5. Here is a generic quantum factoring circuit for the case of N equal 15, namely 3 times 5. What makes this specific for N equal 15 is the choices available for the random base to be chosen, a . a must be co-prime with N . In other words, it must not discuss any factors with N . it must be less than N . Therefore, the only two meaningful cases are a being 7 and 11. Thus, the modular exponentiation circuit in the middle reduces to looking like this, where we have used repeated squaring as it is common to realize the modular exponentiation. Note that each one of these exponentiations is calculated mod 15. So, we began with a controlled multiplication by a , then a controlled multiplication by a square, a to the fourth, a to the eighth, a the 16th, and so, forth, all the way up to a to the 128th power. the result of each of these multiplications is still a number between 0 and 14

because of the modular multiplication being performed. So, two non-trivial values of a may be used in factor 15. we claim that one of these is easy to handle, and the other is hard. Why is this the case? well, let us see why by working out the two cases explicitly. Consider the case of a being equal to 11. Now, what we want is to take powers of a modulo 15. a to the 1 is equal to 11. Now, if we multiply 11 by 11, we get 121. That value, modulo 15, is simply equal to 1. Thus, the pattern continues to repeat. If we multiply again by 11, we get 11 and then 1, and then 11 and 1. So, computing 11 to the x modulo 15 for any value of x is really easy because it only requires one bit of x . thus, the quantum circuit looks simply like this. Because the period is 2 in this case, we find that the quantum circuit required is very simple. All it is a single controlled a multiplication circuit with 1 bit of x involved, the least significant bit. since only two possible values of multiplication by a matter, 11 and 1, it is tempting to replace this controlled by just a single controlled-NOT gate. thus, this case is the easy one. Now, consider the other case of a being equal to 7. Here, we find 7 to the 1 is equal to 7. 7 squared is equal to 49. Modulo 15 is equal to 4. 4 times 7 is 28. 28 modulo 15 is equal to 13. 13 times 7 modulo 15 gives us 1. thus, the period here is 4. So, the quantum circuit required needs 2 bits of x . thus, we find that the quantum circuit is much less trivial. It involves a controlled multiplication by 7, as well as a controlled multiplication by 49 modulo 15. In contrast to the a equal 11 case, this circuit is much more complicated. thus, this is known as the hard case. From this analysis, it is clear that only 7 qubits are needed to realize Shor's Algorithm for factoring 15. Here is the quantum circuit. This circuit includes both easy and hard cases. If we further consider what is needed for the controlled multiplication by a as well as the controlled multiplication by a squared modulo 15, we find that this sequence of gates suffices. It includes two controlled-NOT gates for the easy case and four additional controlled-NOT gates and two Toffoli gates for the hard case. Altogether, including the Quantum Fourier Transform and the superposition creation Hadamard gates, around 20 gates are required. some of these are not elementary gates. The Toffoli gates are three-qubit gates, controlled-controlled NOT gates. they can be very highly non-trivial to realize in a physical system. The first realization of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm was done with a nuclear magnetic resonance system, [68]. The NMR experiment did both the easy and hard cases and required around 200 pulses. Each of these pulses realizing some elementary operation, a sequence of which, for example, realized the Toffoli gate. It was done in 2001 at IBM. More recently, in 2007, Shor's Algorithm was also realized using a linear optics setup. However, only the easy case was implemented in that experiment. Thus, only 3 qubits were required, and 13 elementary gates were performed. this experiment required post-selection, meaning that the results were only correct when conditioned on a specific output being in a certain state. The first solid-state qubit implementation of Shor's Algorithm was done with a superconducting qubit system in 2012. Again, this was for factoring the number 15 using 3 qubits, and two controlled-NOT gates. A more complicated case factoring the number 21 was also done using linear optics quantum computing. However, again, only an easy case was performed with a 4-qubit system and 26 gates in 2011. One of the lessons from these experiments is that it is incredibly tempting to reduce this quantum factoring algorithm into something increasingly simple to realize with an experiment. factoring almost any number using a quantum algorithm can be done trivially by choosing the period r is equal to 2. In this case, the quantum circuit for Shor's Algorithm reduces to a very simple 2-qubit circuit shown here. It illustrates the ridiculousness of what happens when one compiles the quantum factoring algorithm down too far. This point is driven home by a beautiful article by John Smolin, Graham Smith, and Alex Vargo, which appeared in Nature in 2013, "Pretending to factor large numbers on a quantum computer." They observed that running algorithms on such tiny experiments is a somewhat frivolous endeavor when such extreme compilation is performed [69]. So, one must be very careful in choosing a meaningful instance of Shor's Algorithm as well as a meaningful rendition of that instance in a physical system. If this is

done, quantum factoring can be a useful test of scalability. One of the main points of the trapped ion quantum computing realization was how Shor's Algorithm could provide a meaningful and stringent test of the scalability, integration, classical control, and quantum control of quantum computers [59]. In the trapped ion realization of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm, there were four main goals. First, when doing both the easy and hard cases, it is clear that a cascade of multi-qubit gates is required. If each one of these gates fails with a small probability, the cascade rapidly fails because of the product of those probabilities decreasing very fast. So, to achieve high fidelity, the non-pole selected deterministic output is a challenging goal to realize. The trapped ion demonstration's second goal was to demonstrate the feed-forward control needed for the recipes used in fault-tolerant quantum computation [70–73]. A third goal was to perform not just quantum computation but also to integrate quantum memory with quantum computation. Finally, one of the most important goals of building a process for building quantum computers is to be able to predict their performance in advance of realizing the hardware [74, 75]. Thus, one of the goals of the trapped ion demonstration of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm was to demonstrate such predictive modeling of expected system behavior. Altogether, this meant that the goal of the trapped ion quantum computing realization of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm was to use it as a strategic test of scalability elements.

17 Demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm: Quantum Factoring With Trapped Ions - Ion Trapping System

Let now discuss with us a description of the trapped ion quantum computing system employed for the demonstration of Shor's quantum factoring algorithm. Two energy levels of an atom can be employed as a qubit. However, it is ordinarily very hard to hold onto a single atom and not lose it. On the other hand, if an electron is removed from the atom, it becomes a positively charged ion that is much easier to trap and hold. Calcium 40 is a common ion which can be trapped in this way and employed for quantum computation because of its internal level structure. The so-called $D_{5/2}$ and $S_{1/2}$ levels of calcium 40 make excellent two-level systems used as a qubit because of its approximately one second lifetime, and the transition can be excited by photons, which is accessible to the solid-state lasers. In reality, however, the atom has other energy levels also involved. For example, the higher energy $P_{3/2}$ level can connect with the $D_{5/2}$ level via an 854-nanometer optical transition. The $P_{3/2}$ level can also decay to the $S_{1/2}$ ground state via a short wavelength 393-nanometer optical transition. It produces a closed cycle, which is useful for controlling the ion's motion. This cycle and the short wavelength photon emitted are also employed to measure the qubit state since this emission occurs if the qubit is in the $S_{1/2}$ state but not in the $D_{5/2}$ state. Two additional levels, the $P_{1/2}$, and $D_{3/2}$ levels, also form a closed cycle and provide the primary transitions used for laser cooling of the ion. How the ion itself is trapped, however, only involves its charge. Consider a single ion [76, 77]. Trapping is accomplished based on the following idea. Surround the ion with four electrodes shown here in cross-section. Two additional end cap electrodes in front and the back are not pictured. These metal electrodes hold positive and negative charges via electrical voltage is applied. Opposite charges attract and equal charges repel. However, if the ion were exactly in the middle, all forces would balance. More likely than not, an ion would initially be off-center, and thus, it would move towards the nearest oppositely charged electrode, such as the negatively charged one on the upper left. As the ion moves, we change voltages such that the close electrode becomes positive, repelling the ion before it reaches the electrode. The ion then moves onward, for example, to the next closest negative electrode on the bottom left. Again, we change voltages to keep the ion dancing around, never reaching one of the electrodes, always confined within the region defined by the electrodes. This

idea is at the heart of the physical process for which Wolfgang Paul was awarded the 1989 Nobel Prize in physics. The left is a picture of an actual four-electrode quadripolar linear ion guide, which can be employed as an ion trap [78] when the end cap electrodes are added. By applying lasers, which cool the motion of the ion using its internal level structure, the trapped ions can be made to come to rest at the very center of the electrical potential. Such trapping and cooling have been demonstrated with a wide variety of atomic and molecular ions, including strontium, beryllium, ytterbium, barium, magnesium, and calcium. Physical parameters determined by the lasers and by the atomic structure determine how cold the ions get and how cooling competes with heating processes. For scalable quantum computation, the quadripolar ion structure can be simplified as follows. First, imagine rotating the electrode configuration by 90 degrees. Next, envision replacing the three lower electrodes with three coplanar electrodes beneath the ion. The top electrode becomes a top metallic conductor that may be far away from or part of the confining vacuum chamber. This configuration still traps ions. Lasers can be applied from the side just as before for cooling and also to perform quantum gates. The substrate can be cooled, for example, to liquid helium temperatures, to allow integration with devices such as superconducting electronics. This substrate can be micro-fabricated with modern semiconductor lithography techniques with geometries that include sophisticated patterning in the third dimension, such as the segmented structures shown here, comoving ions. A wide variety of such surface electrode ion traps have now been realized in laboratories around the world, including six pictured here from research groups at the University of Mainz, MIT, Maryland, Sussex, Sandia National Lab, and NIST. Designs for trapped-ion chips [79–85] include ones fabricated using sophisticated modern semiconductor line processes such as this one fabricated by Lucent Technologies and pictured installed in a vacuum chamber at MIT. The ion trapped chips have also been operated at cryogenic temperatures, including this one made of silver on quartz used at MIT to trap crystals of strontium ions, shown here with one, two, three, four, and over 20 individual atomic ions visible in the CCD image. The quantum factoring demonstration with trapped ions was carried out in this laboratory at the University of Innsbruck. Pictured here from photos we took during the opening collaboration in 2001, the ion trap here is a macroscopic hand machined quadripolar trap at the center of these magnetic field coils. It shows the same setup from another angle showing the optical components needed to guide all the laser beams to the trapped ions. It is the control computer and electronics used to generate the frequency and amplitude-controlled laser pulses, which perform quantum operations on the ion state. Professor Rainer Blatt, at the University of Innsbruck, his group and David Wineland at NIST set the standard for the field, as well as the character of scientific openness and collaboration that shaped the field of trapped ion quantum information science today [7, 86]. The trapped ion quantum factoring demonstration was done with a linear ion chain of five calcium ions, each of which has the internal level structure shown earlier and reproduced. Recall that the qubit transition is between the $D5/2$ level and the ground state $S1/2$ level. Laser pulses focused on individual ions realize single-qubit rotations addressed at individual qubits. The laser is typically tuned to affect rotations about the qubit is z axes. Multi-qubit collective gates are realized either by applying a monochromatic laser beam to multiple ions, which implements in parallel many single-qubit rotations or by applying two simultaneous laser frequencies tuned such that a multi-qubit gate operation is realized, known as the Molmer-Sorensen gate, after its inventors. It is the mathematical form of the gate, which we can discuss more in atomic physics. The basic set of Molmer-Sorensen collective spin-flip and individual light shift operations available can be combined to realize arbitrary multi-qubit quantum gates. For example, the quantum Toffoli gate can be realized as this sequence of five collective three Molmer-Sorensen and three single qubit light shift gates. How well do the traps and gates work in practice? Here are performance numbers for the system employed for the quantum factoring demonstration. The system was demonstrated to reliably trap up to 14 ions

with state preparation of 99.5% fidelity, taking a few milliseconds for each preparation, routinely realizing T1 and T2 coherence times of one second and five seconds respectively. Requiring about 400 microseconds for a quantum state measurement when using a photomultiplier tube, and between 20 and 45 microseconds to realize single and multi-qubit gates, which have gate fidelities of over 99% for single-qubit operations, and between 99% and 94% for two and five ion gates. Additional energy levels within the ions can also be employed as quantum memories with storage fidelity of 99.5% and write times of 45 microseconds.

18 Demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm: Quantum Factoring With Trapped Ions - Experimental Results

Let us now go in-depth into the actual experimental demonstration of quantum factoring with trapped ions. Recall that this demonstration has four strategic goals. First, to demonstrate fast feed-forward control, the capability needed for quantum error correction used in fault-tolerant quantum computation [87,88]. Second, to integrate quantum memory with quantum computation, noting that data memory is a vital component of modern classical computation. Third, to cascade a sizable number of multi-qubit quantum gates deterministically and with high fidelity. fourth, to demonstrate predictive modeling of the system behavior allowing extrapolation to large scale system performance. The following four issues challenge these four goals. First, the Quantum Fourier Transform and the modular exponentiation circuit for the hard case naively requires over 200 gates. even if the fidelity of each is around 99%, the product of these is expected to have a fidelity lower than 10%. Second, multi-qubit gates, measurement, and state initialization can be slow, meaning that the total time required can exceed a millisecond, which approaches the available quantum coherence time. Third, multi-qubit gate fidelities typically decrease inversely with the number of qubits. Fourth, measurement readout causes ions to fluoresce, and this scattered light can decohere near ion qubits. This experiment brings two main new ideas to address these challenges. These are a new way to use additional magnetic sub-levels of electronic states as quantum memory and an algorithmic structure for the Quantum Fourier Transform originally developed by Alexei Kitaev, which reduces the number of qubits required. we now go through the challenge for each of the four goals starting with the first to demonstrate feed-forward control. For this, we employ Kitaev's version of the Quantum Fourier Transform, which replaces the multi-qubit circuit by a serial single-qubit circuit based on the fact that the outputs are measured. This example is for the 3-qubit QFT, which is what we need for the factoring demonstration. The trapped ion system is suitable for demonstrating Kitaev's QFT because of the ability to read out single qubits and to re-initialize and reset qubit states, all within a given computation which continues onward. we test Kitaev's QFT using this 3-qubit circuit with three different inputs. The experimental results in red and the expected theoretical results in blue for the three input states are shown here. The expected outputs match the experimental data with classical squared statistical output fidelity of 95%. It is much better than the full three ion qubit QFT fidelity due to the quantum memory performance being higher than that of multi-qubit gates. The second challenge goal to integrate quantum memory with quantum computation is tested by implementing the quantum order-finding algorithm. Recall, this takes a permutation of N objects as input and finds the power r such that the permutation returns to identity. The quantum phase estimation circuit shown here solves the problem with an exponential speed-up over the classical algorithm compared by counting the number of uses of the permutation operation. For permutations of N equal 4 objects, this is the required quantum circuit. it simplifies to this 3-qubit quantum circuit using Kitaev's Quantum Fourier Transform. The experimental implementation of quantum order-finding tested these four

permutations and produced these results shown in red, which matched theoretical expectations shown in blue, with fidelities of the 80% level. The third challenge goal is to implement both the easy and hard cases of Shor’s quantum factoring algorithm. Recall that this algorithm is essentially a special case of order-finding, where this modular multiplication function defines the permutation. Shor’s algorithm begins with a random choice of a number a , and the algorithm finds the order of a to the $x \pmod N$. For factoring 15, and there are two non-trivial choices of a , namely 11 and 7, as we have seen. The a equal 11 case is easy because it has a power of 2. In contrast, the a equals 7 cases hard because it has a longer period of 4. we employ the Kitaev version of the QFT for the factoring algorithm with 5 qubits, an extra quantum memory qubit state, and feed-forward control. observe that for the a equal 11 easy case, only the controlled a multiplication need be implemented, and that requires only two CNOT gates realized using 16 laser pulses. For the a equals 7 hard cases, controlled a and controlled a squared multiplication must be implemented. after the peephole compilation, which only uses local information and is blind to the final result, the circuits required involve two 3-qubit quantum Fredkin gates and two CNOT gates, altogether needing 52 laser pulses. Such complex 3-qubit gates had not been realized with trapped ion systems before this experiment. Here are the experimental results for the easy and hard cases of Shor’s Algorithm. The data are shown in blue, and the ideal noiseless theoretical expectations shown in red agree to over 90% for both cases. This is an improvement over the NMR implementation from 15 years ago, which had a much worse performance for the hard case than the easy case. The fourth challenge is to predict the actual results, taking into consideration all known imperfections and noise sources without fine-tuning. we developed a tool for this, known as TIQC-SPICE, inspired by the similarly named SPICE tool important in simulating integrated electronic circuits. TIQC-SPICE compiles quantum algorithms into laser pulses, simulates the resulting ion internal and motional state from the pulses, and analyzes performance to produce the same metrics as obtained from the experiment. Shown here, the experimental in red, ideal theoretical in blue, and TIQC-SPICE simulated results in green for the easy and hard cases of the quantum factoring demonstration. The TIQC-SPICE results accurately predict the experimental results to within error bars, including four sources of major errors, namely addressing of individual ions by laser beams, dephasing of ion states due to fluctuations in the laser or magnetic field [89], the spontaneous emission lifetime of the ion qubits, and measurement and gate times. In conclusion, the trapped ion demonstration of quantum factoring provides a meaningful test of scalability by demonstrating fast feed-forward control, quantum memory interleaved with quantum computation, multiple cascaded and deterministic multi-qubit gates, and predictive simulation of outputs using TIQC-SPICE. These results indicate that technical and not fundamental issues limit scalability. For the future, we now understand how modular multiplication circuits can be realized using an algorithm known as the Quantum Fourier Montgomery Multiplier as an elementary building block, such that the factoring of an N bit number would require $2n$ plus 2 qubits. on the order of N squared gates, of which less than $3N$ and are 3-qubit Toffoli gates, the hard ones to implement. A feasible future experiment could thus demonstrate the factoring of N equal 21 for which the hard case has a period of 6. Using the Quantum Fourier Montgomery Multiplier circuit, this would require 7 ions and 52 Molmer-Sorensen laser pulses. Altogether, this experiment, while tiny compared with those needed to break cryptographic codes, shows how meaningful conclusions and serious extrapolations can be drawn from this scientific endeavor.

19 Demonstrations of Shor's Algorithm: Pretending to Factor

Peter Shor's 1994 polynomial-time quantum factoring algorithm is what started the quantum computing revolution. It was discovered at IBM Research in 2001 that 15 equals 3 times 5 using seven NMR qubits. Then it was discovered again in 2007 using a different technology, photonics, with just four qubits, and in 2009 using five, finally, in 2012, using only three superconducting qubits. Also, 21 was factored using a photonic qubit and qutrit, which is a three-level system. We have plotted these results versus time, and we may notice something strange. The number of qubits is going down. Furthermore, one can extrapolate that by 2020, 15 will be factored without any qubits at all. So, we started to wonder just What is going on here. How many qubits do we need to factor a number? First, a quick review of Shor's Algorithm. The core of the algorithm is as follows. To Factor a number N , we first pick a base a which is some integer. Then we find the period r of a to the power x modulo N . This period finding is the only quantum part of the algorithm. If we find that r is odd, or that a to the r over 2 is minus 1 mod N , we try again. Otherwise, the greatest common divisor of a to the r over 2 plus or minus 1 and N is a factor. Euclid's algorithm, which is rather old technology circa 300 BCE, is efficient for finding the GCD. The quantum period finding step requires a register big enough to hold N and one more bit, which is used to pull out bits of the Quantum Fourier Transform using a technique known as qubit recycling. So, to Factor N , we need $\log N$ plus 1 qubit. For 15, this works out to five bits as the minimum and even more if qubit recycling is not used. So, how did people factor 15 with so, few qubits? It turns out that even the original 2001 experiment with seven qubits used an additional trick called in an abuse of the term compiling. What was noticed was that for some bases a , the period r is small. Then the quantum register used to find the period only needs to be big enough to hold r instead of N . Can we always find a base that results in a small r ? It turns out that the answer is yes. We employ a much more modern result than Euclid's algorithm, the Chinese remainder theorem from 400 CE. It says that given two primes p and q , then a squared is 1 mod PQ if and only if a squared is 1 mod p and also mod q . If we then choose a equal plus or minus p PQ plus or minus q QP where PQ is the inverse of p mod q , and QP is the inverse of q mod p , then by construction, a squared equals 1 mod p and mod q . Furthermore, we can find PQ and QP efficiently using what else Euclid's algorithm. In other words, for any N equals p times q , we have an efficient algorithm for finding a base a with a squared equals 1 mod N , or period r equals 2. So, we can now implement Shor's Algorithm using exactly 2 qubits and Factor an arbitrary N . The circuit looks like this. We can further simplify if we notice that the bottom qubit is never measured and realize that the circuit makes a maximally entangled state, and it measures just one of the qubits. So, all it does is produce random bits. We implemented this using the device shown. Here is the back of the device with a quarter next to it for scale. We factored 15 RSA 768, which we believe is the largest number ever factored on classical computers, and a 20,000-digit number of the own creation called N 20,000. Now, this devolved somewhere into nonsense. The trick the cheating part is that finding a base with a small period is easy only if we already know the factors p and q . Naturally, factoring is easy provided only that we know the factors. As it is the 100th birthday of Richard Feynman, so, let us leave we with this quote from his commencement address to the 1974 class at Caltech. "The first principle is that we must not fool yourself. We are the easiest person to fool. After we have not fooled yourself, it is easy not to fool other scientists." [90,91]

20 Quantum Cryptography - Making Codes

In the last section, we introduced the basics of modern cryptography schemes with a focus on public-key encryption based on one-way mathematical functions. We discussed the RSA cryptosystem in detail and showed that its security is based on prime number factorization and the related problem of period finding. The period finds it is a hard problem for a classical computer. We showed how it could be efficiently performed on a universal quantum computer running Shor's algorithm. We also discussed the topic of key distribution, namely the conundrum that arises when using symmetric keys for encryption and decryption. How can we securely exchange symmetric keys when we do not yet have the encryption keys in the possession for the first transmission? The answer was to use public-key encryption based on asymmetric keys, like the RSA cryptosystem. However, as we just noted, RSA is vulnerable to attack by a quantum computer running Shor's algorithm. However, where quantum figuratively closes one door, it can also open another. In this section, we will show quantum mechanics not only gives us the tools to compromise secure communication protocols but also provides the resources to enhance secure communication through quantum key distribution or QKD [92]. In section one, we briefly discussed QKD in the context of a one-time pad, that is, distributing symmetric keys continuously to provide fresh secure keys that can then be used continually to encrypt data. Here, we will introduce two general classes of QKD [93]. One is based on single-photon sources and detectors. The other is based on entangled photons and Bell state measurements. Both rely on many of the quantum concepts we discussed in section one, such as entanglement, projective measurement, and the no-cloning theorem. In this section, we will expand on those concepts. We will also discuss the importance of randomness in implementing QKD. Pseudorandom number generators output sequences of numbers with properties that are approximately random [94]. However, because it is based on an algorithm that uses an initial value, called a seed, the sequences are never truly random. It has implications for cryptography schemes since, ideally, a current bitstream should not be predictable from the previous bitstream. On the other hand, the randomness of projective measurement is believed to be truly random. This concept, in conjunction with distributed entanglement [95], is a foundation for quantum random number generators.

21 Post Quantum Cryptography

Cryptography is the art of using mathematical tools to achieve information security while using untrusted channels like the internet or wireless communication. We use this to confirm that the software we download every day by auto-updates came from a legitimate source and did not tamper [96]. It is what we use to know an online shopping or banking web page is authentic. Public key signatures are one of the most commonly used methods to provide authentication and data integrity guarantees. Most of the encryption we use today to protect the confidentiality of information is symmetric-key encryption. However, how are these symmetric keys established? In a typical transaction, we might use a public key signature to authenticate our bank, then public key encryption to establish a symmetric key, and then AES to encrypt our confidential information. However, quantum computers will break the mathematical problems at the core of virtually all public-key cryptographic schemes in use today, namely integer factorization and the discrete logarithm problem. It means RSA and Diffie-Hellman schemes are decimated. Going to larger keys adds very little extra security against quantum attacks. Quantum computers also weaken symmetric cryptography because they can brute force search quadratically faster. That is, a quantum computer can effectively search space of N keys with only square root N quantum steps. Doubling key lengths can effectively mitigate the known quantum attacks against symmetric cryptography. Now, while acronyms like RSA and ECC might not mean much to most

users of technology, these tools underpin the security of tools such as secure web browsing, VPN, secure email, auto-updates, blockchains [97], and so, on, which are the basis of technological infrastructure, including the internet, cloud computing, IoT, and so, on. So, to reap the benefits of quantum computing, it is imperative that we first deploy the new cryptographic tools designed to be safe against quantum attacks. It is sometimes called quantum-safe cryptography or post-quantum cryptography [23]. We do not believe that quantum computers capable of breaking RSA and Diffie-Hellman schemes in use today exist, but this does not mean we can just wait and see before doing something about it. Whether we need to take action now depends on three parameters. Firstly, what is the security shelf-life of the information our system is supposed to protect? Call this x year. Secondly, how long will it take to migrate our systems to ones designed to be secure against quantum attacks? Let y be the migration time. Lastly, what is the collapse time, the time until our threat actors can use quantum computers to attack our systems and compromise our information? Now, note that for the next y years, we are stuck with the vulnerable quantum tools. So, information is recorded during this period may be exploited by quantum computers in the future. This information is supposed to be protected for another x years. However, if x plus y is bigger than z or z , then we will not be providing the x years of confidentiality that we are supposed to. For example, information may be for sale on the dark web while it is still supposed to be confidential. Suppose our information is supposed to remain secure for ten years after transmission, and it takes ten years before the systems protect those transmissions against quantum attacks. If quantum computers capable of decrypting that information are available in 15 years, then there will be a five-year period where those transmissions will be vulnerable to compromise before their 10-year shelf life is up. Further, if y is bigger than z , then systems collapse with no reliable way to rebuild them. That is, there is no effective remediation because the tools to protect against new attacks are simply not available. Also, it is important to note that rushing y will not only be disruptive and expensive but will lead to flawed and vulnerable implementations. While viable candidates exist, there is a long road to wide-scale, practical, robust deployment, including many challenges. we need to identify candidates. we need to scrutinize them against quantum and classical attacks. Protocols using the tools must also be secure. Software and hardware implementations need to be secure. we need to analyze the side channels and design countermeasures. we need to look at the performance requirements. we have to integrate them into tools and applications. we have to worry about migration and compatibility, standardization so, systems will interoperate and validation and certification, who can easily take 10 to 20 years to migrate existing systems properly. In August 2015, the National Security Agency of the United States announced that it would initiate a transition to quantum-resistant algorithms in the not-too-distant future. This sent a very clear signal to the world that quantum computing was something that needs to be taken seriously now. Shortly after, the National Institute of Standards and Technology, NIST, started outlining its plans to move forward and produce standardized post-quantum algorithms [98]. It launched its post-quantum cryptography project, which is a process to solicit, evaluate, and standardize one or more quantum-resistant public-key cryptographic algorithms. The submission deadline for proposed post-quantum algorithms was November 30, 2017, and the first workshop to review the submissions was held in April 2018. Most submissions are based on the hardness of lattice problems or of solving multi-linear equations or of decoding error-correcting codes or computing kernels of elliptic curve isogenies. For signatures, there are also schemes based on the security of hash functions. we expect to see some NIST standards for public-key signatures and key agreement in the early to mid-2020s. Other standard bodies around the world are also studying this challenge and taking steps to repair the wide range of standards needed to protect the information technologies from quantum attacks. For example, standards for how the financial industry will use new algorithms. This need to upgrade the cryptographic systems might seem

like a nuisance. However, there may be an additional positive impact. This very advanced warning of the systemic threat to the cyber systems not only gives us a chance to prepare the defenses against this threat, but, if done properly as part of lifecycle management and not as crisis management, we can rebuild the foundations of cybersecurity to be stronger than ever before. we can have a stronger and more agile cyber immune system capable of protecting, detecting, and responding to new, unexpected threats.

The long-term security of modern cryptographic systems has been brought into question by developments in quantum computing. The existence of Shor's factoring algorithm shows that the inversion of the one-way functions needed for asymmetric cryptography is an instance where quantum computers have a quantum advantage over classical algorithms. It is worth noting that the development of quantum computers is not catastrophic for symmetric-key cryptography schemes.

Based on the pace of quantum computing research and the effort required to update cryptographic standards, researchers have argued that the process of finding and implementing algorithms that are suitably robust to quantum computers should begin immediately. Michele Mosca, a leading expert in quantum computing research, has estimated the odds of a quantum computer capable of breaking RSA-2048 an RSA cryptosystem using 2048-bit private and public keys being constructed by 2026 and 2031 at 1/7 and 1/2 respectively. These probabilities are informed estimates based on several parameters such as when a fault-tolerant and scalable qubit will be designed, how many qubits are needed to break RSA-2048, and how long it will take to scale quantum computers to this size.

Professor Mosca argues that, based on these projections, quantum computers capable of breaking RSA-2048 are reasonably likely to be available before the shelf-life of information encrypted with RSA-2048 has expired. Both NIST and NSA have advocated that action should begin now to safeguard cryptographic standards from quantum computers. In 2016, NIST began requesting nominations for post-quantum public-key cryptography algorithms, with the eventual goal of standardizing one or more quantum-resistant algorithms. Additionally, in 2015 the Information Assurance Directorate of the NSA announced it would begin transitioning to quantum-resistant algorithms.

The search for cryptographic algorithms and hardware which are secure against both classical and quantum computers is called post-quantum, or quantum-resistant, cryptography. At present, all post-quantum cryptography algorithms come from either quantum cryptography or by exploiting math problems, similar to prime factorization, which have no known efficient solution on either classical or quantum computers.

Quantum key distribution (QKD) uses fundamental quantum-mechanical properties of systems, usually implemented with light, to securely exchange keys over an insecure public channel. Unlike other solutions, the security of QKD does not rely on assumptions about an adversary's computational resources and can be considered provably secure. Realistically, many QKD implementations are open to attacks on the hardware or software which perform the protocol. At present, QKD is a mature and active area of research with commercial systems available.

Alternatively, two of the most promising post-quantum cryptographic schemes are lattice-based cryptography and code-based cryptography. Lattice-based cryptography makes use of problems on a set of points in n-dimensional space, which have a periodic structure; these sets are called lattices. An example of a lattice problem used in cryptography is the "shortest vector problem," which is based on the shortest non-zero vector for a given lattice. Code-based cryptography uses the properties of error-correcting codes to secure information. Intuitively, these systems consist of a public key that adds random noise to a signal and a private key, an error-correcting code capable of removing the noise. While it is still unclear which of these methods will become a post-quantum cryptographic standard, it is unlikely that the new approach will

be compatible with existing systems. Rather, new hardware will likely be required, at significant expense, and therefore careful planning will be required before the current standards are updated.

22 Single Photon Sources and Detectors

Quantum mechanics provides a means to enhance information security by encoding information in quantum mechanical systems, such as qubits. then distributing those qubits from point A to point B. However, how is this done in practice? This section will introduce quantum communication protocols and how they are implemented using single and entangled photons. To get started, before discussing photons, Let us first discuss light in general. Light is an example of an electromagnetic field, and electromagnetic fields are responsible for the many phenomena we commonly associate with electricity and magnetism. For example, it is what causes electricity to flow through a wire, making bar magnets attract or repel one another. when whether propagating in a material or an empty space, the electromagnetic field is a wave that oscillates at a given frequency. these oscillations are what we call light. Now fundamentally, the electromagnetic field is quantum mechanical and so, light, as with all quantum mechanical systems, is quantized into discrete quanta called photons. The fact that light could be described as both a particle and a wave is What is known in quantum mechanics as wave-particle duality. this is why we can discuss discrete particle-like photons having a particular frequency or a wavelength, which are both wave-like properties. Now, like any wave, a photon will oscillate with a given frequency and in a particular direction. So, let us take those one at a time. In the vernacular use of the word, light is generally part of the visible electromagnetic spectrum, the part which we can see, with different colors being different frequencies of light. However, more generally, light as we are using the term and its associated photons can exist at any frequency. From the radio frequencies used in radio communication bands to microwaves and terahertz, infrared, visible, ultraviolet light, and on up through x-rays and even γ rays. Photons are the quanta of light across this entire electromagnetic spectrum. Now, in addition to frequency, an electromagnetic wave oscillates in a particular direction. It is called polarization, and it generally refers to the direction that the electric field is oscillating. Once that is established, Maxwell's equations determine the direction of the magnetic field as well. So, the direction a photon's electric field oscillates is called its polarization [99]. when a photon travels through space, its electric field can oscillate up and down, it can oscillate side to side, and it can even oscillate in an arbitrary, complex superposition of these two directions. we are saying superposition here deliberately. Horizontal and vertical photon polarizations are orthogonal quantum states. So, we can put these polarization states, H and V, on the poles of a Bloch sphere and treat them as qubit states, zero and one. Similarly, on the equator of the Bloch sphere, the X-axis corresponds to diagonal and anti-diagonal linear polarized light, H plus or minus V. as one goes from the north to the south pole along the X-Z plane, the polarization remains linear and rotates from horizontal at the north pole to diagonal at plus X, to vertical at the south pole, anti-diagonal at minus X, and back to horizontal again at the north pole. Now, the Y-axis corresponds to right and left circularly polarized light. Circular polarization results from having a complex coefficient, such as H plus or minus i times V. so, the polarization rotates in time as the photon propagates. Elsewhere on the surface of the Bloch sphere, the polarization is neither purely linear nor purely circular, but instead is generally elliptical. one can think of the linearly and circularly polarized light as special cases of a distorted ellipse. note that in optics, they give the sphere a different name. They call this a Poincare Sphere. their convention is to swap the Y and Z axes so that circularly polarized light is at the poles, and linearly polarized light is on the equator. In any case, we will use the Bloch convention

here. The electromagnetic field is quantized into photons. The polarization of a single photon can be used as a qubit with horizontal and vertical polarization at the north and south poles. Now, we generally do not encounter pure, single-photon states in everyday life. First, there are typical, on average many more than a single photon from a given source. For example, the light coming from our computer screen right now contains many many billions of photons, each with some arbitrary polarization. second, such classical light sources are generally statistical combinations or mixtures of many different photon number states. To implement QKD protocols based on single-photon polarization, we need to find a way to generate single photons with a specific polarization state. To begin with, a pure quantum state of n photons is called a Fock State. it is stated with exactly n photons. what we would like to do here is generate a one-photon Fock State. The Fock States are called non-classical states of light because they generally do not exist in the classical world around us. At least, not on their own. However, there is a form of classical light called a Coherent State, which comprises an infinite superposition of Fock States. Lasers and microwave oscillators [100,101], for example, create this type of light. While a photon Fock State contains a specific number of photons, a coherent state has a probabilistic distribution of photon numbers. For a given coherent state α , the probability of measuring n photons is given by a Poisson Distribution centered around some average number of photons, the magnitude of α squared. It means that a Coherent State will always have some probability of being in a one-photon Fock State. However, its presence is stochastic and very unlikely when the average photon number is larger than one. Now, a quick and dirty way to produce a single photon is to attenuate a coherent source simply. If we pass laser light through an extremely opaque filter, the average photon number decreases, and the beam gets dimmer. As the average photon number decreases, the Poisson Distribution shifts, and the probability of measuring a low photon number Fock State increases. To make this concrete, imagine we attenuate a laser light until the average photon number is only 0.1. Plugging this into the formula for the probability of measuring n photons, we find that 90% of the time, we will measure zero photons. Nine percent of the time, we will measure one photon. only one percent of the time will we measure more than one photon. So, with light attenuated to this degree, we can say with reasonably high confidence that if we have a photon, it is likely to be in a single photon state that we need. there is only a one percent chance that it is a multi-photon Fock State. However, while attenuation is by far the simplest way to produce a single photon, this procedure is far from ideal. After attenuation, the light is still in a Coherent State, not the pure single-photon Fock State that we want. while we exceeded increasing the probability of measuring only one photon, this came at the expense of lowering the probability of measuring any photons at all. In the above example, nine out of ten times, there was no photon. as we further lower the average photon number, we will certainly decrease the chance of getting any multi-photon states. However, at the same time, we dramatically increase the likelihood that we obtained no photons. Thus, the rate at which we obtain single photons goes down, which translates to a lower communication rate. A far better scheme for single-photon generation relies on an intermediary quantum system, such as an optically active quantum dot. As we discuss in section one, a quantum dot has a ladder of quantized energy levels. A unique energy splitting separates each pair. transitions between energy levels are generally associated with the absorption or emission of a single photon. The idea is to drive the quantum dot to a higher excited state and then let natural, spontaneous emission occur. The quantum dot relaxes back into its ground state, emitting photons at frequencies corresponding to the energy level spacings of its transitions. Importantly, the final transition from the first excited state to the ground state is generally unique and emits a photon at a specific frequency. We can block all frequencies of light except the frequency of this final single-photon if we filter the photon emission from the quantum dot. This final single photon passes through the filter, creating exactly the single-photon source we need. Although the relaxation process is also stochastic in time, the

timing jitter of the single-photon emission can be minimized to the extent to the dot relaxes quickly. In more sophisticated sources, the emission process may even be mediated by a clocked pulse to obtain a heralded stream of single photons. We can then pass these photons through a polarizing filter and prepare the polarization corresponding to the qubit state we need for the QKD protocol. Now, in addition to a single-photon source, we also need a device that can detect single photons at the other end of the communication channel. The challenge here is to convert the small amount of energy stored in a single photon into a measurable electrical signal. A common example of a single-photon detector is a Geiger mode avalanche photodiode. Essentially, a semiconducting material such as silicon with a large external voltage applied across it. When a photon hits the detector, its energy is sufficient to dislodge an electron from the semiconducting material. The external voltage then accelerates this electron through the bulk semiconductor colliding and dislodging more and more electrons, creating an avalanche effect. This cascade of dislodged charges generates a large measurable electrical current, which indicates that a photon was absorbed. Other examples of single-photon detectors include photomultiplier tubes, superconducting nanowires, and superconducting transition-edge sensors. In generating or detecting single photons, these processes should be performed with high quantum efficiency. For example, a photon is generated on each clock cycle, or every photon that is generated is detected without loss. In the coming section, we will see how the source and detector quantum efficiencies come into play when implementing quantum key distribution protocols.

So, the readout for these quantum computers with few qubits are based on bulky microwave components [63]. How should these readout chains develop to actually make use of quantum computers with hundreds of qubits? So, that is particularly true for the solid-state implementations. So for example, superconducting qubits, or semiconducting qubits, the ones that obviously are operated in the microwave regime are going to have these microwave components. In fact, we think that, up to about 1,000 qubits or so, we will be able to do what we are doing today, and just brute-force it. So up to around 1,000, that is not a hard number. But going beyond 1,000, we start thinking about 10,000, 100,000, a million qubits, then, we are not going to be able to brute-force it, and we have to come up with other ways to readout these qubits. Now, whether that means we are going to take the current, bulky microwave components that we have got and integrate them into smaller form factors, that is one approach. So for example, today we use microwave isolators, or circulators, so the signal goes away from the quantum computer towards some subsequent amplifiers, but noise is coming back down towards the qubit that is either blocked or diverted to another direction. Those today are bulky, as we say. But they are ideas, and some early demonstrations using topological materials. A class of materials called topological materials, or two-dimensional materials, that can show something called chirality, or basically quantum Hall-like effect, but without magnetic field. So, these still need to be improved, and proven out, but there are ideas out there of how we can actually integrate some of these bulky components into a smaller form factor, and in particular, in an integrated manufacturing sense. So, these are the kinds of things that have to happen, right, for these, in particular, the quantum computers that use these bulky, microwave components to scale, as we said, beyond the thousands of qubits.

Single-Photon Generation:

The concept of a photon, a quanta of light, was first introduced by Albert Einstein in 1905. A photon embodies a discrete amount of energy proportional to its frequency. Depending on the characteristics and statistical properties of the photons' source, the light may be adequately represented classically called "classical light," or it may necessitate a quantum description called "non-classical light."

The conventional light sources we encounter daily, for example, from a light bulb, are generally classical sources emit so-called "chaotic light." Chaotic light originates from a large ensemble of

independent and incoherent photon emitters. The incoherent and uncorrelated behavior of the ensemble can be perceived as being chaotic, having large intensity fluctuations, and thus the term "chaotic light." A special case the laser is an ensemble of photon emitters acting in concert to create a coherent light source that essentially behaves as a classical, coherent sinusoidal wave.

In contrast, a typical example of non-classical light is a single-photon source, a system that emits one (and only one) photon at a time. There are two general approaches to realizing single photons, but only one of them is non-classical. The classical approach is to attenuate a classical multi-photon field such as a laser field to ensure that when a photon arrives, it is likely to be only a single photon. It is just attenuated classical light, and, the attenuation must be large enough to reduce the probability of multi-photon arrivals. While large attenuation ensures that most arrival events are single photons, it comes with the trade-off that those single-photon arrival events are relatively rare, and, most of the time, there are no photons.

The second approach is truly a non-classical light source based on the spontaneous emission of a single photon from a two-level quantum system. A two-level system in its excited state will spontaneously relax to the ground state and, in doing so, emit a single photon with energy ΔE (the energy separation between the two levels). The frequency f of this photon is $\Delta E/h$, where h is Planck's constant. The precise time at which the two-level system emits the photon is generally a random variable described by an exponential probability distribution $(1/\tau) \exp(-t/\tau)$, where τ is the characteristic excited-state lifetime. In this case, the single-photon emission time is on average the excited state lifetime τ . Examples of single-photon emitters include quantum dots [102], quantum-well heterostructures, and certain atoms or molecules with energy-level transitions at the desired emission frequency.

Single-Photon Detection:

Single-photon detectors are devices that respond (or figuratively "click") when a photon is absorbed. Importantly, the detector should ideally distinguish between photon absorption events and background noise. It becomes particularly challenging when detecting low-energy photons, such as microwaves.

A detector's "internal quantum efficiency" is a measure of how well a detector works, and it is essentially the probability that a photon is accurately detected, given that it enters the detector. Increasing the photon absorption probability and the detector sensitivity will increase the likelihood of detecting a single photon and generally improve quantum efficiency. However, doing so may also make the detector more sensitive to background noise, generating responses even when no signal photons are present. Such errant photon detection events are referred to as "dark counts" and reduce the signal to noise ratio (SNR), negatively affecting the overall detection efficiency.

Avalanche photodiodes (APDs) are one type of a single-photon detector. These detectors are generally semiconductor p-i-n diodes, where p, i, n refer to a hole-doped region, an intrinsic region (no doping), and an electron-doped region of the semiconductor. The diode is operated under a strong voltage bias, which imparts a large electric field across the intrinsic region of the device. When a photon is absorbed, it knocks out an electron. This electron is then accelerated by the electric field and proceeds to knock free other electrons. This process cascades, creating an "avalanche" effect that results in a large, measurable electrical current pulse. The presence of an electrical pulse thus indicates that a photon was absorbed.

Beamsplitters:

A beamsplitter is an optical device that partitions an incoming stream of photons and either transmits or reflects those photons to the output ports. The figure below shows a four-port beamsplitter with input ports (1 and 2) and output ports (3 and 4). As shown, photons impinge

on the beamsplitter at port 1 and are transmitted to port 3, and reflected port 4. Photons that arrive at port 2 would similarly be transmitted to port 4 and reflected port 3. There are two basic categories of beamsplitters of interest here: spatial beamsplitters and polarizing beamsplitters.

Figure 6: Beam Splitter

Polarizing Beamsplitter:

A polarizing beamsplitter is a device that selectively reflects or transmits photons depending on their polarization (the orientation of its electric field). For example, light with polarization V being reflected and H being transmitted. This type of beamsplitter is generally constructed from anisotropic crystals. Light passing through anisotropic (non-uniform) crystals will refract at different angles and spatially separate depending on the light polarization. By choosing the appropriate crystals and angles of incidence, light with one polarization (e.g., vertical) can be completely reflected, while opposing polarization (e.g., horizontal) is completely transmitted. Polarizing beamsplitters are thus a key component in performing a photon polarization measurement. One can infer the photon polarization with a photon detector at each output by measuring a detection event in either the transmission arm or the reflection arm.

Figure 7: Polarized Beam Splitter

Spatial Beamsplitter:

A spatial beamsplitter takes an incoming photon field and transmits it to the output port with a probability T , and reflects it with a probability R . When $T=R=50\%$, we call this a “50:50 beamsplitter.” A spatial beamsplitter is generally described by a 2×2 matrix U_{BS} that takes incoming photon-field amplitudes (we will call them a_1 and a_2 for short) and outputs transmitted and reflected fields (a_3 and a_4).

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_3 \\ a_4 \end{pmatrix} = U_{BS} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (64)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} t & r \\ r & t \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (65)$$

$$\rightarrow a_3 = ta_1 + ra_2 \quad \& \quad a_4 = ra_1 + ta_2 \quad (66)$$

Since the fields a_i are amplitudes, it follows that obtaining the photon field energy or photon number requires taking the magnitude squared $|a_i|^2 = a_i^* a_i$. In cases where these are quantum-mechanical photon-field operators, one similarly calculates an ensemble average $\langle a_i^\dagger a_i \rangle$. The matrix unitarity condition $U_{BS}^\dagger U_{BS} = I$ requires that $|r|^2 + |t|^2 = 1$ and $r^* t + t^* r = 0$, and this ensures that photons are neither lost nor gained in the beamsplitting process. In other words, it conserves probability $T+R=1$ where $T = |t|^2$ is the transmission probability and $R = |r|^2$ is the reflection probability. For a 50:50 beamsplitter, one can take $r = i/\sqrt{2}$ and $t = 1/\sqrt{2}$. With this matrix relation in hand, one can calculate the average output field intensity and the intensity fluctuations induced due to the beamsplitter partitioning process.

1. Beam Splitters; When a single photon enters an ideal, lossless 50:50 spatial beam splitter at port 1 shown in Fig. 1, it is partially transmitted to port 3 and partially reflected port 4. Therefore, a single photon leaves the beamsplitter in a superposition state of being in both the transmission and reflection arms. A detection event then randomly collapses the photon into one of those arms, with a 50% chance of detecting the photon in the transmission arm, and a 50% chance of detecting it in the reflection arm. On the other hand, if the beam splitter is a

polarizing beam splitter illustrated in Fig. 2, then the horizontal component of the photon is transmitted and detected at port 3, whereas the vertical component gets reflected and detected at port 4. Which of the following phrases is valid?

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Figure 8: Beam Splitters

23 Quantum Key Distribution - BB84

Ordinary classical information everybody understands that because it surrounds us. It is like the information in a book. we can copy it at will, and it is not disturbed by reading it. However, what is quantum information [7,103,104]? Rather than give a mathematical description, we try to find a metaphor for it. It is rather like the information in a dream. If we try to describe our dream to someone, our memory of it changes, and eventually, we forget the dream, and we only remember what we said about it. we cannot prove to someone else what we dreamed, and we can lie about our dream without getting caught. However, there is no really hard science of dreams, despite the effort of Sigmund Freud. unlike dreams, there is a good mathematical theory of quantum information. Indeed, when we develop it, we will see where classical information comes from, that we used to think was just simple information. well, here are some examples of elementary quantum behavior. we can use single photons of light to carry one bit of information because a horizontal photon, as at the top of the figure, can be reliably distinguished from the vertical photon, as in the middle. if we pass them through a calcite crystal like that, or crystal of any other sufficiently un-symmetric material, the horizontal photons will get passed straight through, and the vertical ones will get deviated by some amount. therefore, we can count them in two separate detectors. that means each photon can carry one reliable bit of classical information. However, if we put in photons at some other angle, instead of being deviated by an intermediate amount, as we might expect, they behave probabilistically. Some go into the upper beam and become horizontal, and the others go into the lower beam and become vertical. It is, we might say, one of the central mysteries of quantum mechanics, the random behavior of things that are individually identically prepared. We can use vertical and horizontal photons to send one bit per photon of the message. However, if we put in diagonal photons, well, simply by rotating the apparatus, we can distinguish a left diagonal from a right diagonal, like a slash from a backslash. However, once that rotated apparatus is used, that thing cannot distinguish the vertical from the horizontal. So, we have four separate states of the photons that are pairwise, perfectly distinguishable. Nevertheless, we cannot distinguish all four kinds. Now we want to get us to worry a little bit about this strange behavior. Bill Wootters, a physics professor, has a pedagogic analog for quantum systems' behavior when measured. He says it is really like one of those old fashioned 19th-century British schools where the students, who are not supposed to ask any questions they were just supposed to respond to the questions the teacher posed, and where the student is the photon, and the teacher is the measuring apparatus. So, the strict teacher is asking the student a question, saying, is our polarization vertical or horizontal? Furthermore, the students start saying, and we polarized about 56, 55 degrees. we believe we asked a question. Are we vertical or horizontal? Oh, horizontal. Did we ever have any other polarization? No, we were always horizontal. So, that is how quantum systems behave when measured, and that is what lies behind many of the interesting things we can do with it. ultimately, when we come to entanglement, we can understand where that behavior comes from. well, now, we will discuss how we put it to use. This is the quantum money that was proposed by Wiesner in 1968. He says a piece of quantum money will have a serial number on it like ordinary money, but it also will have 20 perfectly reflective boxes, each containing a single photon of one of those four states. the bank will have a record based on the serial number of which photon is in which box, which kind of photon, and when we bring the money back to the bank, the bank will open the boxes, one by one, and measure each photon in the way that it would behave reliably, and therefore check that they all agree with what was supposed to be stored there. However, if we do not know What is stored there, we will disturb some of them by measuring them the wrong way, and the chance of passing a fake bill or making a copy that passes is $3/4$ to the 20th power, which is small. It is the idea that Gilles Brassard and Peter Shor used in building the quantum

cryptography apparatus where we do not try to store the photons, but we send them over a short distance, which in this case was only about 30 centimeters. the idea is that any eavesdropper in that empty middle section of the apparatus would spoil the sum of the transmitted photons by measuring the wrong way, and therefore, would betray their presence. So, in more detail, the way quantum key distribution works are that we have two parties. we call them Alice and Bob. Alice sends a stream of polar ice photons of those four kinds to Bob. Eve is the nickname for the eavesdropper. She can try to measure those photons if she wants, but if she does, she will introduce errors with high probability. the other thing we allow her to do is to listen to the classical discussion between Alice and Bob. that takes place through a series of ordinary classical messages exchanged over a public channel. when they are done with all this, they end up each with a shared secret key, in other words, a random string that they both know, and they have high confidence that no one else knows. well, that is the case if there is not too much eavesdropping, or there is no eavesdropping, but if there is much eavesdropping, they will detect a lot of errors and effort to distill this key will have failed. However, they will know that it has failed with high probability. they just try again tomorrow. So, in more detail, here is how the protocol works, which is called BB84, after the names of the author and the year that it came out. Alice, in the first line, sends a random sequence of these four kinds of photons. Bob, on the other side, makes random measurements uncorrelated. He does not know what Alice would send, and he randomly chooses to make a rectilinear measurement that is vertical versus horizontal or diagonal. So, he does, and then in the third line, we get his measurement results. we including the realistic effect that some of the photons may get lost or his detectors may not be perfectly efficient. So, in some cases, he does not get anything. For example, in the first case, Alice sent a vertical photon. He chose to make a rectilinear measurement, and he gets a vertical result, which is correct. In the second case, Alice sent a horizontal photon, but he decided to make a diagonal measurement, and he gets a random one of the two diagonal results. However, he does not know that it is bad. It is a 45-degree photon, and so, on for the others. The next stage of the protocol now is, after he is received them, Bob tells Alice which kind of measurement he did. He said we measured the first one rectilinearly, the second one diagonally, the third and fourth one rectilinearly, the fifth one we did not get, and so on. That is indicated by the classical message in quotation marks. then Alice tells him in which cases he did the right thing. That is, he made a measurement that did not spoil the polarization that she sent. She very carefully does not say whether she said vertical or horizontal, but she says in the first case, we made a rectilinear measurement, which was good. Keep that photon. Do not tell what it was, because somebody might be listening. In the second case, too bad, we made a diagonal measurement. we sent a rectilinear photon, and so, on. So, they cull from the photons that Bob received, the ones that he spoiled. we can identify, say, a vertical photon is a 1, a horizontal is 0, or for the diagonal photons, they choose to identify the 45 degrees as a 0, and the 135 is a 1. So, what they have, essentially, at this stage is a bunch of bit values that they ought to agree about if there has been no eavesdropping. So, the next question is to find out whether there has been eavesdropping, and we can do those various ways, but the most economical way that does not involve giving away a lot of the data is for Alice to choose a random subset of the bit positions, and announce the parity of that random subset. in the first case, she chose this collection outlined in red, and it has odd parity. She says that it is odd. then the second one, she chooses a different random subset and says that is even, and they go on for 20 of these random subsets. if they agree about all of them, then the chance that there is even one mistake in their sequence is about one in a million. So, they are pretty happy with that. they have to throw away some of the photons to compensate for the fact that they have leaked 20 bits of information to the eavesdropper. So, that is the elementary version of the BB84 protocol.

Quantum key distribution (QKD) is a protocol used to distribute shared secret keys with

security guarantees that are ideally based on the properties of quantum mechanics, rather than on the presumed computational resources of an eavesdropper. This may be contrasted with classical methods of key exchange, such as the RSA cryptosystem, where security is based on the presumed classical computing complexity of the order-finding problem.

The first QKD protocol, now commonly referred to as BB84, was introduced in 1984 by Charles H. Bennett from IBM and Gilles Brassard from the University of Montreal. Since then, there have been several proposed QKD protocols, many of which have been demonstrated, including long-range experimental demonstrations via satellite and even commercially available QKD systems.

The BB84 protocol can be used by a sender (Alice) and a receiver (Bob) who wish to create a shared secret key. It requires that Alice and Bob have access to a quantum channel [105] over which Alice will send polarized photons to Bob and a classical, broadcast channel for coordination purposes. By a broadcast channel, we mean that an eavesdropper (Eve) can listen to and record all information sent over this channel, but she cannot alter it.

To begin the protocol, Alice produces, records, and sends Bob single photons with polarization encodings each chosen at random from one of the four polarization states:

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_H\rangle &= |H\rangle, \\ |\psi_V\rangle &= |V\rangle, \\ |\psi_+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle + |V\rangle), \\ |\psi_-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle - |V\rangle). \end{aligned}$$

The first pair and the second pair of states are orthogonal $\langle\psi_H|\psi_V\rangle = 0$ and $\langle\psi_+|\psi_-\rangle = 0$ and, therefore, each pair forms a polarization measurement basis. As such, we can think of photon polarization states as qubit states, with the photon polarization being either in states H and V or in states + and -. Importantly, note that while the states within a basis are orthogonal, states between the two bases are not orthogonal with one another, for example, $\langle\psi_H|\psi_+\rangle \neq 0$.

Next, Bob measures each photon in one of the two bases either $\{H, V\}$ or $\{+, -\}$ which he chooses at random for each photon, and records the measurement results. Once complete, Bob announces the basis he used for each measurement, but not the result, over the broadcast channel. Because Alice and Bob independently chose the polarization basis at random for each photon, there is a 50-50 chance that they chose the same one for any given photon. For each photon where they did choose the same basis, Alice and Bob will have recorded the same polarization value, because the states within each basis are orthogonal, and we assume an ideal measurement.

For example, if Alice sends $|\psi_H\rangle$ and Bob measures in the $\{H, V\}$ basis, then Bob will also measure and record an H, assuming perfect measurement, since $\langle\psi_H|\psi_H\rangle = 1$ and $\langle\psi_H|\psi_V\rangle = 0$. It is considered a successful trial because both Alice and Bob recorded an H for this photon. However, for the other half of the photons, where Alice and Bob did not select the same basis, the results are uncorrelated, because the two bases are maximally conjugate. It means that a measurement in the wrong basis is equally likely to result in either of the two incorrect outcomes, for example, $|\langle\psi_{H,V}|\psi_{+,-}\rangle|^2 = \frac{1}{2}$. It would be considered an unsuccessful trial.

The security of BB84 starts with the fact that Eve gains no information from listening to the broadcast channel since only information about bases is available and not the measurement results. Thus, she must try to gain information from the photons in the quantum channel [106]. However, any attempt by Eve to extract information reveals her presence through the

introduction of abnormalities in the statistics of Bob's measured results. As a result, Eve is unable to extract information encoded by Alice without alerting Alice and Bob that she is trying to do so.

A straightforward strategy Eve could use is to intercept each photon and measure it on some basis, record the result, and then send a photon to Bob based on her measurement outcome. In doing this, Eve destroys Alice's original photon, and due to the no-cloning theorem, Eve cannot precisely reproduce each of Alice's photons. If Eve got lucky and selected the same polarization basis as Alice did, then she, by chance, will send Bob a photon with the same polarization. However, when Eve does not choose the same basis as Alice, Eve obtains the wrong measurement result, infers a different polarization (without knowing it), and thus sends Bob a photon with a polarization different than Alice's original photon. Consequently, the statistics of Alice and Bob's measured results successful trials versus unsuccessful trials and their statistics will be altered by Eve's activities and reveal her presence.

Realistically Alice and Bob do not want to throw out the entire key every time an anomaly occurs since even without an eavesdropper, noise and imperfect measurement will always lead to some level of errors and statistical variation. Alice and Bob adopt a strategy called privacy amplification to deal with this problem, which produces a new, shorter, shared key from the original one, which can, in principle, reduce Eve's inferred information to zero.

Before implementing privacy amplification, Alice and Bob must first ensure their keys match. They can do this using classical error correction methods: having Alice randomly choose two bits from her key, adding them together modulo 2, and announcing the result to Bob. He, in turn, tries the same and replies with his result. If they match, the two bits are kept. If they differ, the two bits are discarded. Just sending the result of modular addition over the classical channel does not reveal any information to Eve since it only indicates the parity of the bits, that is, whether the two bits have the same or different values, but not their specific values. Using this technique, Alice and Bob will arrive at two matching keys. However, Eve may still have knowledge of a few of these bits (but, certainly not all of them).

Next, the privacy amplification protocol is applied. Privacy amplification comprises a series of transformations on Alice and Bob's matching key to create a shorter key, one which Eve cannot replicate without knowing the entire initial key. For example, Alice and Bob jointly choose pairs of bits at random from their keys and replace them with their binary addition. Intuitively, this works because of parity; Eve cannot know the value of the binary addition without knowing the value of both initial bits. Based on the error rates found in Alice and Bob's initial keys, they can estimate how much information Eve has and then reduce it to the desired level (approaching zero) using the privacy amplification protocol.

So far, we have only dealt with eavesdropping in the ideal case; however, real-world implementations of BB84 and other QKD protocols are potentially open to a much wider range of system-level vulnerabilities. For example, if attenuated classical light is used to generate single photons rather than a true single-photon source, photon number splitting attacks become possible on residual states with more than one photon. In this case, Eve can split off and measure one of the photons in the multi-photon state without impacting the polarization that reaches Bob. Besides, access to the hardware at Alice and Bob's locations must be restricted to trusted personnel only. Otherwise, an Eavesdropper can gain access to the random number generator used to select bases or even the encoded keys themselves by other means. There are just a few examples of the types of attacks, many of which are independent of the quantum nature of QKD that may compromise the quantum-enhanced security afforded by an ideally implemented QKD system.

So, the Chinese satellite perform QKD [107], used to perform quantum cryptography, and the secure communication, and, how does this work, That satellite is independently communicating with two points on the ground. so, it is the satellite that is doing the exclusive or of the message with the pads, then independently, when it is over one city, it is communicating with that city, and then it carries the information when it is on the other side of the earth, communicating with another city. it is then also communicating with that side. so, the satellite is acting basically as a relay, and performing the quantum cryptography during that transit.

24 Entangled Photon Sources and Detectors

So, for this section, we have introduced single-photon sources and detectors and seen how single photons can be used to encode and transfer quantum information across a communication channel, for example, to distribute a cryptographic key. In this section, we will discuss the generation in the detection of entangled pairs of photons. later this section, we will discuss how entangled photons may also be used for quantum key distribution, as well as for quantum teleportation and random number generation [108]. As discussed in section 1, an entangled state is a manifestly quantum mechanical multi-qubit state that cannot be written as a product of single-qubit states. Let us start with a counter-example. we have seen through section 1 and section 2 that if we apply Hadamard gates to 2 qubits, each prepared in state zero, then we obtain the 2 qubits equal superposition state, $0, 0$ plus $0, 1$ plus $1, 0$, plus $1, 1$. While it might appear that this state cannot be factored into single-qubit states, we know it is possible because we generated it by applying Hadamards to single qubits. as we have seen, this state is the tensor product [109,110] of the single-qubit superposition state 0 plus 1 . Thus, it is not an entangled state, because we can write it in terms of the single-qubit states ; 0 plus 1 for qubit A, tensor product 0 plus 1 for qubit B. In fact, 0 plus or minus 1 are the excited and ground states along the x-axis of the block sphere. Thus, we can write this as the plus and minus state in the x spaces. In contrast, we can see that state $0, 0$ plus $1, 1$ cannot be written as a tensor product of single-qubit states. it is an entangled state of 2 qubits called a Bell state. even when we perform a transformation to the x basis, we still get a state that cannot be factored into single-qubit states A, tensor product B. This is a property of entangled states. They remain unentangled even on different bases. looking at the circuit model, we see that we needed a conditional 2 qubit gate to generate the entanglement. Single qubit gates alone were not enough. we will return to Bell states in a moment. Recall from earlier this section that single photons have a polarization, for example, horizontal and vertical. since vertical and horizontal polarizations are orthogonal quantum states, we choose to put them at the poles of the block sphere and call this the qubit. For single-photon QKD protocols, like BB84, this is sufficient. Bob prepares a single photon in a particular qubit state that is a particular polarization state and then sends it along the communication channel to Alice. However, as we will see in the next couple of sections, using entangled photons enables certain alternative types of QKD protocols, as well as a means to generate random numbers in teleport quantum information. Thus, the question is, how do we generate and detect entangled photons? The most common method for producing entangled photons is through a process called spontaneous parametric downconversion. Parametric downconversion is essentially a frequency conversion process, where a photon at frequency $2f$ is converted into two individual photons whose frequencies together add to $2f$ and conserve energy, for example, each photon having a frequency, f . Now, linear time-invariant systems, by definition, do not convert frequencies. If we take a sine wave and pass it through a linear system, its amplitude and phase may change, but its frequency remains the same. It is essentially a statement that a plane wave e to the i ω t is an eigenfunction of a linear system. Thus, to take a photon at one frequency and convert into

two photons at a different frequency, we need a material with strong nonlinear optical properties. a common example of such a crystal is beta barium borate or BBO. When a strong pump beam passes through a BBO crystal, there is a small probability that one of its photons will convert into two photons, one called a signal, and the other called an idler. It is just convention. Now, due to energy conservation, the signal and idler frequencies are each half of the pump frequency. due to momentum conservation, the signal and idler photons will leave the crystal in correlated spatial directions. Additionally, these two photons will also have correlated polarizations. Depending on the type of crystal we use. The two downconverted photons will either have the same polarization, which we call a Type 1 Crystal, or they have opposite polarizations from a type 2 Crystal. BBO is a Type 2 Crystal. We see that the two downconverted photons exit the crystal in directions that form a cone, one having horizontal polarization and one having vertical polarization. The locations of the photons on the cones are correlated, equidistant from the original beam trajectory, again, due to momentum conservation. For example, the colored dots on the polarization cones indicate the correlated spatial positions of the emitted photons. Now, crucially for the two photons to be polarization entangled, their direction of emission cannot indicate which photon is vertically polarized and which is horizontally polarized. Therefore, we use an iris to selectively keep only photons that arise from positions where the two polarization cones cross. Thus, whether the signal and idler photons travel left or right once they exit the crystal, one will have polarization h and the other polarization v. Nevertheless, which is not known. In other words, the direction of propagation does not label the polarization. Under these conditions, the state of the two downconverted photons is polarization-entangled, and it is all of the form H, V plus $e^{i\phi} V, H$. The phase ϕ can be made 0 degrees by choosing the correct phase-matching conditions, crystal thickness, or using a phase shifter. Thus, one has the state H, V plus V, H . This is one of the four Bell states. from this, the other Bell states can be generated by changing the phase ϕ and swapping the polarizations H and V, using a half-wave plate. Now that we are able to generate all four entangled Bell states Let us see how to detect these states. we first need to introduce an optical device called a polarization beam splitter [111]. A polarization beam splitter will transmit or reflect a photon depending on its polarization, H or V. at each output of the beam splitter is a single-photon detector. By seeing which detector clicks, we can determine whether the photon had horizontal or vertical polarization. To see how this works, let us try a test case. we begin with a photon polarized in the vertical direction. we also show here for completeness a polarization rotator, a device that changes the polarization of incoming photons. For now, however, we just set it so that it passes photons without making any changes. If we send in a vertically polarized photon, it reflects off the polarization beam splitter, which is detected by the single-photon detector in the reflection arm. On the other hand, if we send in a horizontally polarized photon, it is transmitted by the polarization beam splitter and detected using the single-photon detector in the transmission arm. Thus, we can determine the photon polarization by seeing which detector clicks. So, what happens if we have entangled photons? Let us take the H, V plus V, H entangled state. Photon A travels to the left polarization beam splitter, and Photon B travels to the right polarization beam splitter. what we will observe are correlated detection events. That is, if Photon A's polarization analyzer indicates horizontal polarization, then the Photon B analyzer indicates vertical polarization. Similarly, if Photon A is measured to have a vertical polarization, then Photon B must have horizontal polarization. These are correlated detection events. Now, the presence of correlation suggests polarization entanglement, but it is not proof of entanglement. After all, the source may randomly send out classical states of either H, V , or V, H , which would give the same results. However, it is not an entangled quantum state H, V plus V, H . To test for entanglement, one needs to measure the entanglement in different polarization bases [112]. As we discussed earlier, changing the bases does not change the entanglement. Thus, the measured correlations will be retained in

any measurement basis. In practice, rather than changing the measurement hardware, one may instead rotate the input state’s polarization. This is experimentally more straightforward, and this is the role of the polarization rotator. With correlation measurements made on different polarization bases, one can compare the measured results with the classical probability model, assuming there is no entanglement. This type of test is called Bell’s inequality test. It is used to determine the degree of entanglement of a quantum state within certain assumptions, called loopholes. We will discuss more Bell state measurements, test the Bell’s inequality and loopholes later in the section, as well as the application of Bell state measurements to the problem of random number generation.

Entanglement is a manifestly quantum mechanical state of two or more quantum systems whereby the state as a whole cannot be reduced to a representation of independent, single-system states [113]. For example, the two-qubit state $|\Psi\rangle_{12} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2)$, cannot be written as a tensor product of two single-qubit states $|\phi\rangle_1 \otimes |\psi\rangle_2$. Moreover, we will find that we always get terms that do not appear in $|\Psi\rangle$. The entanglement of two quantum mechanical two-level systems results in what is referred to as Bell states, and there are various means to generate and detect the kinds of quantum states. However, they all share certain features, as we describe below, including the need for some type of two-body “nonlinearity” to generate and detect these states, whether a nonlinear crystal, a controlled-NOT gate, photon-number resolving detectors that distinguish 0, 1, and 2 photons.

In the case of photons, a common approach to generate Bell states is spontaneous parametric downconversion (SPDC), as described in the section. In this case, a nonlinear crystal, such as one made from beta-barium borate (BBO), converts incident “pump” photons at frequency ω_p into two photons: a signal photon at frequency ω_s and an idler photon at frequency ω_i . The process is energy conserving, and hence the frequencies of the two newly created photons will sum to that of the original pump photon: $\omega_p = \omega_s + \omega_i$ (Planck-Einstein relation). Similarly, the process is momentum conserving, and the vector momenta sum together as $\vec{k}_p = \vec{k}_s + \vec{k}_i$. Since the momenta \vec{k}_s and \vec{k}_i are vector quantities, momentum conservation correlates both the magnitude of the momentum and the directionality of the emitted photons.

Figure 9: Spontaneous Parametric Down conversion

There are two general types of SPDC. Type-I SPDC generates two photons with the same polarization, and Type-II SPDC will generate two photons with orthogonal polarization. In both cases, the photons are correlated and, in certain instances, polarization-entangled. As we discuss in the section, BBO is a Type-II SPDC crystal, and so its output comprises a horizontally (H) and a vertically (V) polarized photon. The photon emission forms two cones, one for each polarization. The locations of any two down-converted photons on their respective cones are correlated due

to momentum conservation. Thus, in general, the direction of the emission “labels” the photon polarization, such that the resulting two-photon state is not polarization-entangled. However, by selecting photon emission only from the two locations where the two cones cross, the emission direction no longer uniquely specifies the polarization and, in this case, a polarization-entangled state is formed of the form $|\Psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle_s|V\rangle_i + e^{i\phi}|V\rangle_s|H\rangle_i)$. By choosing the correct phase-matching conditions (e.g., size of the crystal, etc.), one can set the value of ϕ and generate the state $|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle_s|V\rangle_i - |V\rangle_s|H\rangle_i)$. In the following section, we will look at how to generate the three other Bell states starting from $|\Psi^-\rangle$.

$$|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H_A V_B\rangle + |V_A H_B\rangle)$$

Figure 10: Spontaneous Parametric Down conversion

Generating the Four Bell States:

In general, it is possible to create all four Bell states, given just one of them. For a polarization-entangled Bell state with horizontal and vertical polarization, this can be accomplished using optical elements called “waveplates.” Waveplates rotate the polarization axis around the direction of propagation by a specific angle chosen by the design of the waveplate. The waveplate material a birefringent crystal such as quartz has polarization-dependent refractive indices which enable a particular polarization to propagate faster through the material the “fast axis” than the polarization orthogonal to it the “slow axis.” These two axes form a two-dimensional coordinate system.

Suppose a linearly polarized photon is incident on a waveplate. The overall phase accumulated while the photon travels through the waveplate depends on the waveplate thickness corresponding to the distance the photon has to propagate to pass through the optical element. However, in addition, the photon polarization is projected on to the waveplate’s coordinate system, and the portion along the slow axis accumulates an additional phase with respect to the component along the fast axis.

If the “extra” phase is equivalent to one-half the incident photon wavelength, the waveplate is referred to as a “half-wave plate.” Moreover, the angle between the half-wave plate coordinate system relative to the photon’s polarization axis determines the projections onto the fast and slow axes and, thus, the rotation of the polarization.

With two half-wave plates, it is possible to generate all Bell states starting from one of them. Two transformations need to occur: 1) a polarization change that swaps $|H\rangle$ and $|V\rangle$, and 2) a phase shift $\phi = \pi$ that swaps + and -. To swap polarization, the half-wave plate’s coordinate system is oriented 45° with respect to the photon polarization axis. To impart a phase shift, another half-wave plate’s fast axis can be oriented -45° with respect to the horizontal axis to induce a phase inversion.

The following table summarizes the required optical elements a polarization swapping half-wave plate, HWP_{45° , and a phase inversion half-wave plate, HWP_{0° – to alter the polarization of the first photon p_1 or the second photon p_2 and what general quantum gate that corresponds to to generate all four Bell states starting with $|\Psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle_1|V\rangle_2 + |V\rangle_1|H\rangle_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2)$.

Table 5: optical elements - a polarization swapping half-wave plate

Target	p_2: Optical Element	Gate	Polarization	General
$ \Psi^+\rangle$	No elements	$I \otimes I$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle_1 V\rangle_2 + V\rangle_1 H\rangle_2)$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0\rangle_1 1\rangle_2 + 1\rangle_1 0\rangle_2)$
$ \Psi^-\rangle$	HWP_{0°	$I \otimes Z$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle_1 V\rangle_2 - V\rangle_1 H\rangle_2)$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0\rangle_1 1\rangle_2 - 1\rangle_1 0\rangle_2)$
$ \Phi^+\rangle$	HWP_{45°	$I \otimes X$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle_1 H\rangle_2 + V\rangle_1 V\rangle_2)$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0\rangle_1 0\rangle_2 + 1\rangle_1 1\rangle_2)$
$ \Phi^-\rangle$	$HWP_{0^\circ}, HWP_{45^\circ}$	$I \otimes ZX$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(H\rangle_1 H\rangle_2 - V\rangle_1 V\rangle_2)$	$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0\rangle_1 0\rangle_2 - 1\rangle_1 1\rangle_2)$

Detection of Bell States:

To determine the success of the generation of a particular type of Bell state, detection schemes that distinguish all four Bell states are necessary. A deterministic measurement of Bell states generally requires nonlinear elements and two-particle interactions capable of performing conditional two-qubit rotations, two-particle interferometry (e.g., Hong-Ou-Mandel experiment sensitive to quantum statistics), number-resolving photodetectors, and the like. The details and trade-space of the various types of Bell state analyzers are beyond the scope of this text unit. For our purposes here, we will consider one example of a Bell-state analysis which uses the CNOT gate as the conditional [114], two-qubit gate and apply it to our photon polarization-entangled Bell-state example.

Since photons interact only weakly (if at all), it is challenging to make reliable, nonlinear optical elements that implement deterministic, nonlinear operations with high efficiency. Linear optical elements are reliable, but they cannot be used to distinguish all four polarization-entangled Bell states deterministically. However, there are probabilistic schemes that can distinguish the Bell states using linear optics. In this case, one must identically prepare the same Bell state many times and run protocols using linear optical elements followed by measurement. Through these schemes, effective nonlinear interactions can be realized probabilistically and detected through an appropriate measurement scheme. When a spectator measurement indicates that an effective interaction has occurred, the results from that specific experimental trial are kept and aggregated to perform the Bell-state analysis; this is called post-selection. For example, although there is no deterministic CNOT gate with solely linear optics, there is a scheme for implementing a probabilistic, CNOT gate with linear optics that can be leveraged with measurement post-selection.

The following general protocol is able to distinguish all four Bell states. It can be imple-

mented in a probabilistic manner with a probabilistic CNOT gate following Emanuel Knill's, Raymond Laflamme's, and Gerard Milburn's proposal and a beamsplitter as a Hadamard gate. Note that in the notation below, we use $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ to represent the polarization states $|H\rangle$ and $|V\rangle$, so as not to confound the polarization state $|H\rangle$ with the Hadamard gate H .

$$\begin{aligned}
|\Psi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{CNOT} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|1\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{H\otimes I} |0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 \\
|\Psi^-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 - |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{CNOT} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 - |1\rangle_1|1\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{H\otimes I} |1\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 \\
|\Phi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|0\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|1\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{CNOT} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|0\rangle_2 + |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{H\otimes I} |0\rangle_1|0\rangle_2 \\
|\Phi^-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|0\rangle_2 - |1\rangle_1|1\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{CNOT} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|0\rangle_2 - |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2) \xrightarrow{H\otimes I} |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2
\end{aligned}$$

The two-qubit states are measured after a CNOT gate, and the Hadamard gate on the first qubit is applied. The measurement reveals the underlying type of the Bell state.

25 Quantum Key Distribution - Ekert91 and BBM92

There are various forms of quantum key distribution or QKD described by different protocols. They all make use of quantum mechanical properties to establish shared lists of random numbers that can be used for encryption. We have discussed the BB84 QKD protocol where one user, Alice, prepares a specific state that she sends to another user, Bob. Bob then measures the state. Alice and Bob then perform sifting by comparing the preparation basis and the measurement basis and then following several classical postprocessing steps to establish secure encryption keys. Protocols of this sort, which make use of quantum superposition where one party prepares a state and the other party measures it, are called to prepare and measure QKD protocols. An alternative set of protocols is called entanglement-based protocols, and they make use of entanglement. Two common and related entanglement-based protocols are the BBM92 protocol, named for its inventors Bennett, Brassard, and Mermin. Its invention, the year of 1992, and E91 or Ekert protocol, was invented by Artur Ekert in 1991. In both of these protocols, a transmitter consisting of an entanglement source generates a two-photon entangled state known as a maximally entangled Bell state, with one photon being sent to Alice and the other photon being sent to Bob. The photons are sent across quantum communication channels that can reliably transmit the single-photon states and preserve their entanglement. The relevant property of Bell states is that the photons are correlated in multiple measurement bases, including the basis consisting of the horizontal and vertical photon polarizations and the 45-degree rotated basis consisting of the diagonal and the antidiagonal polarizations. For an ideal transmission across the channel, if Alice and Bob choose the same measurement basis, their measurement results will be perfectly correlated between the measurement devices. However, individual measurements at each side will look random. Alternately, if Alice chooses the horizontal-vertical basis and Bob chooses the diagonal-antidiagonal measurement basis, the measurements will not be correlated at all. For intermediate basis choices, their measurements will be partly correlated. In the BBM92 protocol, Alice and Bob received their entangled photon, and both choose either the horizontal-vertical or the diagonal-antidiagonal measurement basis. They both record their basis choice and what the actual measurement result is. They repeat this many times, and they now have long lists of chosen measurement bases and measurement results. The remaining protocol steps are identical to the previously described BB84 protocol; namely, Alice and Bob use a classical

communication channel to announce their chosen measurement bases to sift out only the instances of them choosing the same basis. They then compare a random subset of measurement results to determine how well the quantum channel performed. If the determined error rate is below 20%, they perform classical postprocessing to erase any information that a potential eavesdropper could have discovered and correct for remaining errors between Alice and Bob. The benefit of the BB84 protocol is that the protocol does not require that we trust the source that prepares and sends the state. The protocol ensures that there is no way for a malicious actor to take control of the source and spoof Alice and Bob without them detecting it by observing lower correlation strengths and thus higher error rates than are required to form a secure key. The other entanglement-based protocol, the Ekert protocol, is similar but adds an interesting twist. In this protocol, the same sort of state is generated and distributed between Alice and Bob. Alice randomly chooses between three measurement bases: the horizontal-vertical basis, the 45-degree rotated diagonal-antidiagonal basis, and an intermediate basis rotated by 22 and 1/2 degrees. Bob also randomly chooses between three bases: the horizontal-vertical basis, the intermediate 22 and 1/2-degree rotated basis, and a final basis rotated by 67 and 1/2 degrees. The measurement bases and the measurement results are recorded. Alice and Bob repeat this many times and again announce their chosen measurement bases over a public classical communication channel. The instances where they have chosen the same basis are used for the key-generation process. The instances where they have chosen different bases are used to determine the performance of the channel. For these instances, the measurement results are announced publicly and are used in a Bell inequality to determine how well the channel transmission has preserved entanglement. This allows Alice and Bob to have an entanglement-based measurement of the maximum amount of information a potential eavesdropper could have obtained. Alice and Bob then perform classical postprocessing to erase any information an eavesdropper could have discovered and to correct for remaining errors between Alice and Bob. That is how entanglement can establish encryption keys, eliminate the need to trust the system transmitter, and check the security of the encryption keys. There are various other QKD protocols with differing benefits and tradeoffs that may be of interest to specific scenarios. However, the important point is that they all make use of the same basic ideas and concepts that we have described here.

The first quantum key distribution (QKD) protocol BB84 encoded information in the polarization of single photons. BB84 uses a quantum channel to communicate the photons, and a classical channel to broadcast the chosen polarization bases used for preparation and measurement.

In this section, we will present an alternative method proposed by Artur Ekert in 1991, known as Ekert91, which encodes information using polarization-entangled Bell states. Ekert91 also uses a quantum and classical channel. However, the advantage of the Ekert91 protocol is that its security can be traced directly to fundamental properties of quantum mechanics entanglement and measurement through a test called Bell's inequality. In this section, we will discuss Bell's inequality and its use in Ekert91 to communicate information securely and detect the presence of an eavesdropper.

Entanglement and Bell's Inequality:

In 1935, Albert Einstein, Boris Podolsky, and Nathan Rosen (EPR) argued that quantum mechanics is an incomplete theory in a scientific article titled "Can Quantum-Mechanical Description of Physical Reality Be Considered Complete?." Their argument was a thought experiment that can be related to two-particle entanglement. Essentially, imagine that we take a polarization-entangled state of two photons, and we then send one photon each to Alice and Bob. A very large distance separates them. If Bob and Alice measure on the same basis, then their results should be correlated, for example, if Bob measures H, then Alice measures V., if they measure

on different bases, then their measurements are uncorrelated.

However, what happens if Alice and Bob are separated by a distance so large that they can make their independent measurements faster than it would take light (and thus information) to travel between their locations? Then, we are left with the conundrum called the EPR paradox. Essentially, due to entanglement, there is a quantum-mechanical correlation in the measurements made by Alice and Bob. It is more than simply “if Alice measures H then Bob measures V.” Bob’s results correlated or uncorrelated depend on Alice’s choice of basis; but, Bob makes his measurement long before any knowledge of Alice’s choice could have reached him or his measurement apparatus. Einstein did not like such “spooky action at a distance,” and thus hypothesized that quantum mechanics theory must be incomplete, that there must be “hidden variables” that quantum theory does not account for to connect these measurements. So the perceived randomness of quantum mechanical measurement is a mirage.

Niels Bohr, a contemporary of Einstein, responded the same year in a scientific article with the same title and argued that the theory of quantum mechanics only captures the interaction of a quantum system with a measurement apparatus and not the intrinsic character of it. Therefore, any conclusion based on the assumption that measurement does not disturb the measured system in question such as the EPR conjecture that quantum theory is incomplete without hidden variables must be invalid [115].

The debate continued for decades. In 1964, John Bell proposed a theorem later referred to as Bell’s inequality, which can be used to test if hidden variables do exist experimentally. Essentially, Bell’s inequality is a statement based on purely classical arguments. If the inequality is violated in experimental measurements, quantum mechanics must be complete, and there are no hidden variables. In 1969, John Clauser, Michael Horne, Abner Shimony, and Richard Holt presented a method to quantify Bell’s inequality theorem, abbreviated as the CHSH inequality. If the measurement results of a probed quantum system do not exceed a certain threshold, the CHSH inequality is true and hidden variables do indeed exist. In contrast, if the theorem is violated, thus a value exceeding this particular threshold results, true randomness exists.

Suppose Alice and Bob have each a photon from the spin-singlet state $|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_A|1\rangle_B - |1\rangle_A|0\rangle_B)$. Alice randomly chooses between two different options to measure her photon, Q or R, once her photon arrives at her laboratory. Similarly, upon arrival of his photon, Bob randomly decides between two other measurements, S or T. Since Alice and Bob decide on and execute the type of measurement of their photon at the same time, any disturbance of each other’s process can be ruled out, and information can not propagate faster than light. Their measurements yield either 1 or -1. Considering all different measurement outcomes and some potential noise in the process, the following Bell’s inequality with the expectation value $E(x)$ being the probability-weighted average of all possible measurement outcomes $x \in \{-1, 1\}$ is always true if there exist a set of hidden variables.

$$|E(QS) + E(RS) + E(RT) - E(QT)| \leq 2 \quad (67)$$

Incorporating the rules of quantum mechanics and the definition of Alice’s and Bob’s measurements as single or combinations of quantum Z-gates and X-gates, Q,R,S, and T can for example be expressed the following way:

$$\hat{Q} = Z_1, \quad \hat{R} = X_1, \quad \hat{S} = \frac{-Z_2 - X_2}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad \hat{T} = \frac{Z_2 - X_2}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (68)$$

The expectation value for $\langle \hat{Q}\hat{S} \rangle$ results to be:

$$\langle \Psi^- | \hat{Q}\hat{S} | \Psi^- \rangle = \frac{\langle 0|_A \langle 1|_B - \langle 1|_A \langle 0|_B}{\sqrt{2}} \left(Z_1 \otimes \frac{-Z_2 - X_2}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \frac{|0\rangle_A|1\rangle_B - |1\rangle_A|0\rangle_B}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (69)$$

$$= \frac{\langle 0|_A \langle 1|_B - \langle 1|_A \langle 0|_B - \langle 1|_A \langle 0|_B - \langle 1|_A \langle 1|_B + \langle 0|_A \langle 1|_B - \langle 0|_A \langle 0|_B \rangle}{\sqrt{2} \cdot 2} \quad (70)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{1+1}{2} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} = \langle \hat{Q} \hat{S} \rangle \quad (71)$$

Similarly, $\langle \hat{R} \hat{S} \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, $\langle \hat{R} \hat{T} \rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, and $\langle \hat{Q} \hat{T} \rangle = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ can be derived. The resulting expectation values following the rules of quantum mechanics violate Bell's inequality.

$$\langle \hat{Q} \hat{S} \rangle + \langle \hat{R} \hat{S} \rangle + \langle \hat{R} \hat{T} \rangle - \langle \hat{Q} \hat{T} \rangle = 2\sqrt{2} > 2 \quad (72)$$

The violation of Bell's inequality is experimentally confirmed ruling out the existence of hidden variables and thus quantum mechanics is complete.

Ekert91 and BBM92:

The entangled states can be generated by a trusted source such as Alice or Bob. The required entangled state is the spin singlet state $|\Psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|H\rangle_1|V\rangle_2 - |V\rangle_1|H\rangle_2) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle_1|1\rangle_2 - |1\rangle_1|0\rangle_2)$. The particles are spatially separated, one is sent to Alice and one to Bob. Both perform measurements on their photon's polarization along three different unit vectors \vec{a}_i and \vec{b}_j respectively. Alice measures randomly relative to the horizontal axis along a unit vector \vec{a} with angle $\phi_1^A = 0^\circ$, $\phi_2^A = 45^\circ$, or $\phi_3^A = 90^\circ$. In contrast, Bob measures randomly along a unit vector \vec{b} with angle $\phi_1^B = 45^\circ$, $\phi_2^B = 90^\circ$, or $\phi_3^B = 135^\circ$.

Similarly to BB84, upon completion of all measurements, Alice and Bob publicly share along which orientation each photon was measured. The group for which they picked the same measurement procedure (\vec{a}_2, \vec{b}_1) and (\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_2) serve as the group which the key can be generated from. The group of measurements with differing measurement orientations (\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_1) , (\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_2) , (\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_3) , (\vec{a}_2, \vec{b}_2) , (\vec{a}_2, \vec{b}_3) , (\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_1) , and (\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_3) are used to evaluate the existence of potential eavesdroppers. The measurement results of the second group can be revealed publicly to evaluate via the CHSH inequality if the channel is corrupted or not. The CHSH inequality requires the subset (\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_1) , (\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_3) , (\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_1) , and (\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_3) to work and yields $-2\sqrt{2}$ if the quantum channel is not corrupted and hence secure.

$$S = E(\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_1) - E(\vec{a}_1, \vec{b}_3) + E(\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_1) + E(\vec{a}_3, \vec{b}_3) = -2\sqrt{2} \quad (73)$$

The CHSH inequality is true, meaning the absolute value of the result is $|S| \leq 2$ if the quantum channel is intercepted and one or both photons are disturbed and hence lost some aspects of their "quantumness." Unless the CHSH inequality is true, Alice and Bob can proceed and define an arbitrary subset of the group with the same measurement procedure to serve as a secret key. Ekert91 utilizes the completeness of quantum mechanics to generate a secret key and distinguishes itself from BB84 by the information carrier of choice, entangled spin-singlet states instead of single photons.

Shortly after, Charles Bennett, Gilles Brassard, and N. David Mermin generalized BB84 and Ekert91, referred to as BBM92. The BBM92 protocol is equivalent to BB84 and a simplified version of Ekert91 that does not require entangled states and Bell's inequality to ensure its security. It is able to withstand all known attacks allowed by the properties of quantum mechanics.

26 Random Numbers: An Introduction

we are going to discuss random numbers. This is a fascinating topic because random numbers are not only really useful in everyday life but thinking about random number generators also

brings up some interesting questions about reality and free will. Let us start out discussing why random numbers are so important. If we were a kid in the 80s, we might remember a game show called Press our Luck. Part of the game show had a box moving around different squares on a board that was also changing, and the player would press a button to stop the motion of the box. Whatever square the box was on would be what the player would win, or they could land on a whammy and lose everything. In 1984, Michael Larson went on the show, and he did well. We notice that he pays much attention, almost like he knows when to press the button. he did because the people that made this game did a really bad job randomizing the motion of the box and the squares. They were not random at all, but just randomly picked from a small number of possible sequences. So, Michael Larson spent much time with a VCR watching and memorizing the various, quote-unquote, random sequences that would come up. He ended up setting a record by winning over \$100,000, which we sure had consequences for the people who ran the game show. So, that is one-way random numbers can influence someone's life. here is another more serious one. As we know, the security of many forms of encryption relies on the computational difficulty of solving certain problems. For example, factoring is difficult with a classical computer, so some types of encryption are based on factoring's difficulty, and we can have an encryption key that is the product of two large prime numbers. If one of the prime numbers is reused in another encryption key, that breaks the algorithm's security. Now, this should not be a problem because if prime numbers are selected randomly, the probability of two keys using the same prime should be zero. However, in 2012, researchers found that if they looked at all the publicly accessible keys for RSA, a commonly used public-key cryptosystem, about a quarter of a percent of the time, two unrelated keys shared a prime factor. The authors speculate that the lack of entropy or randomness in one of the inputs to the algorithm resulted in this repeat of factors, which essentially made those systems completely insecure. Beyond public key encryption, many other cryptographic tasks require randomnesses, such as challenge-response protocols, like what we use at an ATM or digital signatures. Modern-day cryptography relies on random numbers, which are also important for scientific applications, like Monte Carlo simulations and lotteries. Now let us look more closely at what a Random Number Generator or RNG [116]. For now, we are going to keep the discussion abstract and just imagine that an RNG is a black box. when we press a button, a one or a zero comes out. to keep the discussion simple, we will assume that they are identically distributed. So, half the time, it is a zero, half the time it is a one. If the black box is truly an RNG, there is no way of knowing what will come out when we press the button, and we can say that each bit coming out has one bit of entropy, which is a measure of randomness. Now it is not just that we or we with limited knowledge have no way of knowing what comes out. It is that nobody, not even somebody with knowledge of everything in the universe, an infinite computational power, can predict it. One problem is that it is hard to tell when something is random or when it is just that we cannot predict it. For example, pseudorandom number generators are often used in practice. With a pseudorandom number generator, we put in a random seed, and what we get out is a lot of numbers that look random. However, a pseudorandom number generator is a classical deterministic algorithm, so it is not random. This quote by John Von Neumann puts it nicely. "Anyone who considers arithmetical methods of producing random digits is, in a state of sin." Because they are not random, pseudorandom number generators are susceptible to algorithmic and computational advances, and they require that the input seed is random and secret. If we cannot use a classical computer to make random numbers, how about it if we take a physical process that we know is random and use that to make the random numbers. So, flip a coin and say heads are zero, and tails are one. That is kind of a slow random number generator. However, people have built much faster generators using ring oscillators, a single photon hitting a beam splitter, and even images of a lava lamp. Many of these things should be random. For example, with a single photon

hitting a perfect 50/50 beam splitter, which arm we detect the photon in should be random, but it is hard to verify that everything is working the way we think it is. People have demonstrated the ability to blind detectors or force them to click, for example. here is an example of adversarial control of an RNG demonstrated by two researchers in 2009. They showed that by injecting noise onto a power supply, they could compromise the randomness of a ring oscillator based RNG of the same type used in challenge-response protocols for chip and pin credit card authorization. here is a visual representation of the RNG output from their paper. Before they launched their attack, it looks random, and after, there are patterns. Looking at this, we might say that just means that we should look for patterns. Many statistical tests will look for patterns and quantify the likelihood that a sequence of long numbers is consistent with being generated by a random process [117]. The problem is that it only looks for specific patterns, and there are plenty of things that do not have any patterns but are not random the digits of π , for instance. So, we cannot just take the output of the RNG and run statistical tests on it to say whether it is an RNG. We can try instead to open up the box, look at What is inside, characterize it, and make sure everything is working. The problem with that is that systems can be complicated and messy. There are many ways that components can fail or compromise, so there is no way of knowing whether or not we are testing for the right things. In 2010, some researchers realized that we could build something close to a black box random number generator. It turns out that we can make an RNG based on a loophole-free test of Bell's inequality. We can quantify the entropy of our RNG without knowing the details of how everything inside the box is working under some general assumptions.

Random numbers are needed in several applications and areas of research, including cryptography, tests of fundamental physical principles, and simulations based on Monte Carlo methods. True randomness is difficult to realize. Most realistic applications use pseudorandom number generation (PRNG) algorithms, which produce a string of numbers mimics randomness but are based on an algorithm using a private "seed" and therefore is ultimately deterministic. Thus, the use of numbers produced by PRNG in principle limits cryptographic security introduces loopholes in fundamental physical tests and may lead to unexpected errors in Monte Carlo simulations.

The necessity of random numbers in cryptography is exemplified by one-time pad encryption, where each user shares an identical secret key as long as the plaintext. To perform encryption, the sender will add each character of the plaintext to the corresponding character of the key using modular arithmetic. It is important to note that for every plaintext and ciphertext pair of equal length, there exists a key of the same length, which will translate between them. Therefore, if a key is chosen at random, every ciphertext is equally likely given any plaintext, and an eavesdropper gains no information by intercepting the ciphertext. This level of security is referred to as "information-theoretic" security. It is, in principle, unbreakable by an eavesdropper with infinite resources, as long as she does not possess the key.

Consider a PRNG algorithm called the middle-square method to gain an intuition for the types of problems associated with using PRNG numbers (rather than truly random numbers). In this method, a pseudorandom number of length n is calculated by starting with a seed of the same length, squaring it, and taking the middle n digits of the resulting number. For example, if we want a four-digit pseudorandom number, we could start with the seed 3452, which, when squared, is 11916304, and our new number is the middle four digits given by 9163. This process can then be repeated as many times as needed. One obvious problem with this procedure is that, if at any point, this key is compromised, then an eavesdropper could determine all past and future keys; this property is known as state compromise extension. Another issue with this technique is that it will eventually repeat, which reveals information to an eavesdropper. For example, when starting with the seed 0540, it cycles back to itself after the

sequence $0540 \rightarrow 2916 \rightarrow 5030 \rightarrow 3009 \rightarrow 0540$. Lastly, some pseudorandom number-generation algorithms will use a shorter seed in length than the message being encrypted, which reduces the number of keys that an adversary needs to search over. Explicitly, a 16-bit plaintext could be encrypted using a 4-bit seed, where the first four rounds of the middle-square method are concatenated to create a 16-bit key. The problem with this is that, even if the eavesdropper does not know the seed, they only need to search over 2^4 bits to cover every possible key, rather than the 2^{16} when each bit of the key is random.

The inherent weaknesses of using PRNG algorithms have motivated significant research to create robust sources of truly random numbers. One of the most promising areas of research in this area is in quantum random number generators (QRNGs), which rely on either superposition of quantum states or quantum entanglement to create randomness [118]. A simple example of how this works on a single system is to prepare a single qubit in the superposition state given by $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$ and then making a measurement in the $\{|0\rangle, |1\rangle\}$ basis. Since $|\psi\rangle$ is an even superposition of both basis states, the outcome of the measurement cannot be predicted, even in principle, and is, therefore, a source of random numbers.

Unfortunately, it can be difficult to verify that a QRNG based on a single system is properly functioning, without intimate knowledge of the system construction. For example, a QRNG could be manipulated to output states which are statistically random but are supplied by a third party, or less maliciously, the superposition of $|\psi\rangle$ could have collapsed before measurement, meaning that the measurement outcomes are actually classical noise and hence predictable in principle given enough knowledge about the system.

To contend with these problems and to guarantee the randomness of numbers, techniques known as “self-checking” QRNGs have been developed. Using a Bell state such as $|\Phi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$ as a resource, these QRNGs perform what is called a Bell test on $|\Phi\rangle$. A Bell test is a series of repeated measurements on each qubit of an ensemble of identical entangled pairs [27, 28], such as $|\Phi\rangle$, wherein an instance of the process each qubit can be measured in two different ways, and each of these choices has two different outcomes. Once enough statistics are assembled, it can be determined whether the state being tested violates a Bell inequality. All states which satisfy a Bell inequality can, in principle, be described by a deterministic local hidden variable model (DLHVM), which means that all measurement outcomes on particles described by that state are determined ahead of time, even if they are not available to the experimenter [27, 28]. Alternatively, if a state violates this inequality, it cannot be described by a DLHVM, and joint measurement outcomes on these states are determined at the time of measurement, regardless of the physical distance between them. While there are many ways to interpret the meaning of a Bell violation [27, 28], it suffices to say that the extent of a violation is quantitatively related to the amount of randomness present in the measurement results.

27 Bells Inequality

Let us now discuss entanglement, Bell’s inequality, and experiments that can tell us something about the nature of reality [27, 28]. In the particular example we use here, we will be discussing polarization-entangled photons. However, these concepts have been demonstrated in many different types of systems. we will start by discussing polarized single photons. Say we have a vertically polarized photon, which just means that the photon’s electric field is oriented vertically. We can send it through some polarization rotating element, and then to a polarizing beam splitter, which has single-photon detectors on each output. Right now, we are not rotating the polarization. the way this polarizing beam splitter works is that if the photon is vertically

polarized, it will always reflect off the beam splitter and be detected in this port. However, if the photon is horizontally polarized, it will pass through the beam splitter and be detected in that port. So, this idealized system makes a perfect measurement of the photon polarization as long as it is polarized either horizontally or vertically. we call this measuring on the HV basis. The photons can be polarized in other directions too. For example, diagonally. To measure the diagonal basis, we can rotate the polarization before it gets to the beam splitter. Then this detector will be associated with the diagonally polarized photons. this one is associated with the anti-diagonally polarized photons. This is a measurement in the diagonal, or AD basis. What happens if we take a vertically polarized photon and measure it on the AD basis? In that case, quantum mechanics predicts that it will randomly go to one detector or the other, and we cannot know what will happen in advance. we have been discussing single photons, but quantum theory predicts the existence of entanglement. here is a cartoon of an entangled photon source. It puts out two photons. we will call them A and B, and each goes in a different direction two researchers named Alice and Bob. The quantum state is shown here. what it means is that the source puts out a state that is an equal superposition, a photon A being horizontally polarized and B being vertically polarized, and photon A being vertically polarized and B horizontally polarized. When we measure on the HV basis, we find that if Alice measured an H, Bob would always measure a V and vice versa. So, far this does not seem too weird. if Alice and Bob both make their measurements in the same basis, what they measure is consistent with a source just putting out a classically correlated state, where half the time it sends an H photon to Alice and a V photon to Bob and half the time a V photon to Alice and an H photon to Bob. Now, let us rotate the measurement basis so that both Alice and Bob measure the AD basis. Remember, if we have an H photon and measure it on the AD basis, it will randomly go to one detector or the other with a 50% probability. Same with a V photon. If we did start with a classical state, we would expect that Alice and Bob's detector clicks would be uncorrelated when they measure on the diagonal basis. On the contrary, countless experiments have verified that the detector clicks are always anti-correlated if Alice and Bob measure on the same basis. These are the stronger than classical correlations that Einstein called a spooky action at a distance. However, another interpretation is possible. It could be that the photons have some hidden variable telling them to go to one or the other detector when they are measured on this or that basis. we can loosely phrase the question of which of these alternatives is correct. Is the world quantum, or is it classical and deterministic? Amazingly, there is an experiment that we can do to rule out one of these possibilities. More precisely, we can rule out something called local realism [119]. The local part just says that we cannot send out information faster than the speed of light. realism means that things have definite properties independent of whether or not we choose to measure them. This is, we think, how most of us see the world. Hidden variables are an example of the local realistic theory. The experiment involves doing the same measurement of polarization but changing the measurement basis Alice and Bob used. In the simplest form of the experiment, Alice and Bob each measure on two bases. It turns out that for some selection of their measurement basis, there is a correlation function we can define over the inputs, or basis selection, and the outputs, or which detector clicks, where the value of the correlation function is different if the photons have these hidden variables versus what quantum mechanics predicts. Now, there are some loopholes associated with these tests of local realism. The loopholes are ways in which nature could trick us into thinking that local realism is incorrect when, in fact, it is not. First, we need to make sure that Alice does not know in advance what measurement basis Bob will pick and vice versa. If one of them knew the basis that the other chose, they could trivially reproduce the statistics. The only way to guarantee this is to make sure that their basis selections are space-like separated, so there is no time for the information about which basis Alice chose to make it over to Bob before he needs to choose a basis. There is also the free choice loophole, which says the basis

selections on either side need to be uncorrelated with any classical variable. In other words, Alice and Bob's basis selections need to be made of their own free will without being affected by anything else. Finally, there is the detection loophole, which says we need to measure enough of the photon pairs to make sure we are not only observing a subset, which appears to violate Bell's inequality. The first experimental test of Bell's inequality was done in the '80s. For a long time after that, people tried to close these loopholes. People managed to close all the loopholes separately, but it was not until 2015 that experimentalists could close the loopholes in a single experiment conclusively. This was a tremendous accomplishment. It implies that the world we live in is inherently random. By the way, if we are the type of person who does not like the idea of the world is random, we should note that no experiment can ever rule out the concept of superdeterminism, which is the idea that everything in the universe, including Alice and Bob's basis selection, is predetermined. So, we can say that these experiments are consistent with superdeterminism, but we might also have to accept that we do not have any free will in that case.

28 Bell's Inequality and Certifiable Random Number Generation

Bell's inequality may seem just like an interesting experiment we can do and something to discuss in our first quantum section, but not something that has any real-world applications. However, in 2010, researchers show that we can take the base machinery for demonstrating Bell's inequality and use it to make a remarkable type of quantum random number generator one that is certified by the violation of Bell's inequality under some basic assumptions. They showed that they could use the violation of Bell's inequality to bound the entropy of the outputs of their RNG. Here is how it works. Alice and Bob start with a string of zeros and ones that is used to select one measurement basis or the other. Each time they run the experiment choosing one basis or the other, each gets out a 0 or 1, depending on which detector clicked. They repeat the experiment many times and use the input and output strings to compute the Bell inequality function. This tells them how much entropy is in the output string and uses classical techniques to extract randomness. The amazing thing here is that all we need to know is how much entropy is in the system is the violation of Bell's inequality. So, there is no need to continuously characterize every component in our system to make sure it is working properly. We have one number that we get out of the system that tells us if it is working properly. Again, something can always break, and this does not guarantee that nothing will go wrong in our black box. However, if something goes wrong, either because something broke or because an adversary is hacking the system, we see it reflected in the violation of Bell's inequality. This concept is called device independence or black box security. We have discussed here using this for random number generation, but people have demonstrated black-box security proofs for other applications, such as quantum key distribution. In these protocols, it is important to close the loopholes in Bell's inequality, because those could provide a way for an adversary to compromise the system, for example, by blinding detectors. The verifiable or certifiable random number generator was first demonstrated using trapped ions in 2010. The locality loophole was not closed, but the two halves of the experiment were spatially separated and thought to be not interacting. The only way to know for sure is to close the locality loophole. In 2018, some of the same people that showed they could close the loopholes in Bell's inequality tests then used their system to make a certifiable random number generator. We would like to close by pointing out the timeline for device-independent applications. It all started back in the '30s when Einstein, Podolsky, and Rosen wrote a paper on what they viewed as a paradox and a reason that quantum mechanics was incomplete this concept that they rejected called a

spooky action at a distance. Nearly 30 years later, John Bell realized that there is an experiment we could do to shed light on this paradox. People did the first experiments demonstrating the violation of Bell's inequality in the '80s. More than 20 years later, they came up with an idea of device independence and demonstrated it in a real system. Perhaps, someday we will have black box applications on a chip. If so, this would be an amazing story about how something that started as a scientific curiosity, which addressed a question mainly of philosophical interest, had profound effects on security.

So, can single entanglement exist between two distant locations, or does the entanglement always need to exist in the same locale for entangled QKD methods? the key property of entanglement, and the one that is so non-intuitive, is the fact that it can be non-local. non-local means, not local, but it means more than that. It means that these two particles, which have been entangled, Let us say two photons in their polarization are separated by such a large distance that even at the speed of light, we cannot communicate a choice to measure, say, particle one, we cannot communicate what we did to make that measurement over to another person over here measuring particle two. so, that is a space-length separation. so these two people could make their measurements on these entangled photons, without even in principle knowing what the other person did and yet the correlations still exist. Meaning that what this person measures is going to depend on the choice of basis that this person over here made. So, that is the spooky action at a distance that Einstein did not like, but as Bell and subsequent Bell test measurements have repeatedly shown, with various loopholes being introduced and subsequently being closed, that this is the way quantum mechanics in nature works, and we think the last loophole, as mentioned in section, the last loophole that still has to be closed is called the free will loophole. so, if everything is predetermined, right, then that is a different story, but if we believe that these two people, person one and person two, have the free will to independently decide, at any given time, which basis they are going to use, then quantum mechanics will not. Now, the question, if we read into it one bit further, is does the entanglement have to be generated locally? And most of the generations, if not all of them, the schemes start locally? That we do say, for example, parametric down conversion. One photon is generated, or one photon is down converted into two photons which then fly away to distant locales. But we think that that is a generation question. it is not a question about can entanglement exist between two distant locations? Absolutely, and that is the point.

29 Quantum Teleportation and Entanglement

If somebody gives us a single photon of unknown polarization and wants us to transmit it to somewhere else. It is a photon. It naturally likes to travel. we can send it to them. However, suppose it is daytime. we want to send it somewhere else. there are too many photons around. How can we get this photon to another destination intact? well, we could try to measure its polarization. However, if we did, we might measure along the wrong axis. we might spoil it. If we measured it, then We could tell the receiver our result. However, it would be a bad copy. It seems like the uncertainty principle prevents us from getting all the information out about the photon's state. if we cannot get the information out of it, how can we get a copy of this photon or get it to another destination intact? well, quantum teleportation is a way to make it end-run around this logic. it uses entanglement. here is how we do it. First, we will say why it does not work if we do not use entangle. So, we have got this photon of an unknown polarization. The best we can do is measure it. that uses the photon up and gives incomplete information. So, we would then send this partial information. we would make an approximate copy of a copy that might be right or might be wrong or might have a polarization that is not quite right. So, that

is the trouble. it would seem that the uncertainty principle prevents this job from being done. well, nowhere is what we can do to get around that problem. we use more photons. we have the original photon A, and we want to get it to another destination. So, we now take two entangled particles, which we will call B and C. they have never been near photon A., And they do not know anything about the state of A. what we do is we make a measurement, not on A alone, but A and B together. since those are two photons, we can get four possible outcomes of that measurement, so we do that. Essentially we measure the relation between their polarizations without measuring the polarization of either one. that spoils both of them. So, this looks like we are worse off than. we do not even have one copy of the information that we wanted to get to the receiver over on the right side of the figure. However, we take this information that we got the relation. that is a two-bit message. we send it to the receiving location. Then, at the receiving location, the receiver takes the other entangled particle C, who is never anywhere near A and does one of four different rotations. we might say applies a corrective treatment. when we do that, it puts it into an exact copy of the state of photon A that we spoiled by measuring it in the first part of the protocol. So, at no point do we exactly discuss the state of this photon. However, we protected it from being damaged. then we have destroyed one copy on the left and produced a perfect replica on the right. that is what we call quantum teleportation. we could draw some equations for this, showing how this works. However, can we do it, metaphorically? Furthermore, the metaphor we have is to say, suppose Alice suppose she has witnessed a complicated crime with possible terrorist implications here in Boston? Now, the FBI in Washington knows that her memory is this fragile dreamlike form. they want to ask her just the right questions in the right order. not to spoil her memory by asking her wrong questions. they certainly do not want to leave the investigation to the Boston Police, who will ask her stupid questions and confuse her. Thus, they ask her to come to Washington and be interviewed by a panel of experts who will ask her just the right questions in just the right order. probably these questions even depend on confidential information they would not want to discuss with the Boston Police. However, Alice does not like travel, and she refuses to go. So, they decide to send one of their agents to Boston. Unfortunately, their agents are all very opinionated about the case. they do not trust each other to ask the right questions. well, two agents seem to be pretty useless. They are around the FBI, but they do not seem to understand anything. They are twin brothers, Remus and Romulus. they do not have an opinion about anything. If we ask either of them a question about any subject at all, they give a completely random answer. However, for some reason, they would always give the same answer as each other. So, discussing this problem of who is going to go to Boston and talk to Alice, Remus says, well, we do not know anything about the case. So, we less likely to influence her than any of us. Besides, we like to travel, and Romulus agrees. So, they send Remus to Boston to meet Alice, And they explain that this is a speed date. They are not supposed to discuss anything substantive. They just have to figure out whether they click in their relationship. well, it goes badly, and Alice leaves in a few minutes, saying we cannot stand this guy. nd for some reason, it has been so stressful that we forget everything about this crime. the Boston Police thank her and say she can go home. Then they get on the phone to Washington and say, well, Alice and Remus do not get along. So, the FBI, the x, then go to Romulus and say, well it looks like Alice and our brother do not get on. So, any question that we would have asked Alice, we can ask us. we know that whenever we say yes, she would have said no. So, they proceed with their careful questioning, reversing every one of Romulus's answers to get what Alice would have answered. In other words, the metaphor is that by the speed date, Alice has transplanted her state, not into Remus, but his twin brother but with a random rotation. In this case, a reversal of all the answers. So, when we work for the math of teleportation, essentially, that is what it does.

Quantum teleportation is a method to transfer the state of a local quantum system from

one location to another location through the use of a pre-shared Bell state and the transmission of two bits of classical information. This protocol, first discovered in 1993, represents a fundamental building block for communicating quantum information. For this reason, it has been studied intensely and has been demonstrated numerous times experimentally. Despite the colloquial definition of the word teleportation as popularized by science fiction, no physical object is transferred by the process; instead, just the quantum information describing the state of a qubit is transferred between two local quantum systems.

To be precise, we can assume that a user Alice is in possession of a qubit in the state $|\psi_0\rangle_C = a|0\rangle_C + b|1\rangle_C$ and wishes to transfer this state to another user, Bob. Alice and Bob have pre-shared one of the four Bell states with subscripts A and B which are given by:

$$|\Psi^\pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle_A|1\rangle_B \pm |1\rangle_A|0\rangle_B) \quad \& \quad |\Phi^\pm\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle_A|0\rangle_B \pm |1\rangle_A|1\rangle_B) \quad (74)$$

Suppose Alice and Bob have chosen to pre-share the $|\Psi^-\rangle$ state (similar results would be found for the other choices). The initial state of the system can now be written as

$$|\psi_0\rangle_C \otimes |\Psi^-\rangle_{AB} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (a|0\rangle_C + b|1\rangle_C) (|0\rangle_A|1\rangle_B - |1\rangle_A|0\rangle_B). \quad (75)$$

By expanding equation (75) and grouping Alice's qubits together, the same state can be equivalently expressed as

$$|\psi_0\rangle_C \otimes |\Psi^-\rangle_{AB} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [a|0\rangle_C|0\rangle_A|1\rangle_B + b|1\rangle_C|0\rangle_A|1\rangle_B - a|0\rangle_C|1\rangle_A|0\rangle_B - b|1\rangle_C|1\rangle_A|0\rangle_B] \quad (76)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} [a(|\Phi^+\rangle_{CA} + |\Phi^-\rangle_{CA})|1\rangle_B + b(|\Psi^+\rangle_{CA} - |\Psi^-\rangle_{CA})|1\rangle_B] \quad (77)$$

$$- a(|\Psi^+\rangle_{CA} + |\Psi^-\rangle_{CA})|0\rangle_B - b(|\Phi^+\rangle_{CA} - |\Phi^-\rangle_{CA})|0\rangle_B] \quad (78)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} [|\Psi^-\rangle_{CA}(-a|0\rangle_B - b|1\rangle_B) + |\Psi^+\rangle_{CA}(-a|0\rangle_B + b|1\rangle_B)] \quad (79)$$

$$+ |\Phi^-\rangle_{CA}(a|1\rangle_B + b|0\rangle_B) + |\Phi^+\rangle_{CA}(a|1\rangle_B - b|0\rangle_B)] \quad (80)$$

where we have used the following identities

$$|0\rangle|0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\Phi^+\rangle + |\Phi^-\rangle) \quad (81)$$

$$|0\rangle|1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\Psi^+\rangle + |\Psi^-\rangle) \quad (82)$$

$$|1\rangle|0\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\Psi^+\rangle - |\Psi^-\rangle) \quad (83)$$

$$|1\rangle|1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\Phi^+\rangle - |\Phi^-\rangle) \quad (84)$$

The protocol then begins with Alice projecting the state of her two qubits onto one of the four Bell states in a process known as Bell state measurement (BSM). It leaves Bob with one of four qubit states, which for the case of $|\Psi^-\rangle_{CA}$ is already equal to $|\psi_0\rangle$ up to a meaningless global phase and for the other states can be transformed into $|\psi_0\rangle$ using either X, Y, or a Z-gate. However, it should be noted that if Alice does not send Bob the results of her BSM, then Bob does not know which transformation to apply and is unable to recover $|\psi_0\rangle$.

As an example, if the result of Alice's BSM is $|\Phi^-\rangle_{CA}$, then Bob would be left with the state $a|1\rangle_B + b|0\rangle_B$, which can be rotated into the desired state with an application of the X-gate.

Intuitively, we can think of teleportation as first comparing the states of Alice's two qubits through a BSM, and then exploiting the fact that the qubits in the pre-shared Bell state are correlated and our knowledge of the BSM outcome to recover the state of the original qubit.

For example, if the BSM between Alice's two qubits results in $|\Psi^-\rangle$, we know that Alice's qubits are anti-correlated. Then, since Alice and Bob's initial qubits are also anti-correlated, the two anti-correlations cancel, and Bob is left with the same qubit up to a meaningless global phase as the one Alice wanted to send.

Quantum teleportation is consistent with the physical principles that information cannot be sent faster than light and that quantum information cannot be cloned. The first is apparent because Bob is unable to recover $|\psi_0\rangle$ until he is told the result of Alice's BSM, which must be sent to Bob using some sort of classical method, and therefore cannot be transferred faster than light. The principle of no-cloning is satisfied because Alice's BSM leaves her two qubits in a Bell state, which is now completely independent of the state $|\psi_0\rangle$. Explicitly, if we were to look at the state of either of Alice's qubits individually after the BSM, we would find an even statistical mixture of the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ which contains no information related to $|\psi_0\rangle$.

30 Quantum Repeaters

Long-distance quantum communication is problematic due to photon loss inherent in realistic optical channels. This problem is dealt with classically using amplifiers, known as "repeater stations," which are interspersed along a transmission channel to compensate for the reduction in signal power due to loss. Unfortunately, the no-cloning theorem prohibits the amplification of an unknown quantum state. It would allow for a single photon to be copied into more than one photon carrying the same quantum information. Therefore, classical amplification techniques cannot be used to extend the range over which quantum information can be transmitted.

Optical fibers are made of silica (SiO_2), which has two leading loss mechanisms, each of which becomes dominant at different wavelengths. At short wavelengths, the primary loss mechanism is elastic scattering, in the form of Rayleigh scattering, which can change the propagation direction of the light enough to allow it to escape the fiber. Alternatively, at long wavelengths, the dominant loss mechanism becomes absorption by the material itself. At approximately 1550 nm, the combined loss due to both of these effects are at a minimum of about 0.2 dB/km, a value which is referred to as the attenuation coefficient. Here, the decibel (dB) scale quantifies the ratio of output to input power as $10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(\frac{\text{output}}{\text{input}} \right)$. Outside of this optimal wavelength, the attenuation coefficient increases. It defines a relatively small range of wavelengths useful for telecommunications in optical fiber, limiting the prospect of multiplexing signals to overcome the loss. It should be noted that the optimal attenuation coefficient for silica of 0.2 dB/km should be thought of as the lower bound for attenuation coefficients found in real fibers where other

loss mechanisms such as absorption due to material impurities or fiber bending also contribute to the overall attenuation.

Fiber loss is approximately constant, so the total attenuation is proportional to the distance of transmission. For context, assuming the optimal attenuation coefficient for silica of 0.2 dB/km, 95% and 1% of the initial signal power remains after a transmission distance of 1km and 100 km, respectively. Unfortunately, the transmitted power scales very poorly with distance, and at 500km (100dB loss), only one in every 10^{10} photons is transmitted through the channel.

A sophisticated approach to overcoming the limits imposed by attenuation and the no-cloning theorem is the concept of a quantum repeater. Quantum repeaters operate on two entangled states that span consecutive distances of $L/2$ such that the final state of the system is a single entangled state which spans the entire distance L . To be more specific, if we have two Bell states which span the $L/2$ distances then a Bell state measurement on the two collocated qubits in the center along with classical communication of the measurement result to the end stations will result in the entanglement between the two outermost qubits which span L . This process can be thought of as the quantum teleportation of a quantum state from the central station to one of the end stations where the initial entanglement of the state is teleported along with it. In general, this process can be nested as many times as needed to span a given initial distance L .

The final entangled state distributed by quantum repeaters can be used as a resource for any quantum communication protocol. For example, this state can now be used to teleport an unknown quantum state over the total distance L in a deterministic fashion as opposed to direct transmission, which would have only been successful with very low probability due to the attenuation. It is important to note that in this example the quantum repeaters have not only allowed for the transmission of a quantum system over a large distance, the original aim but have also shifted the problem of probabilistic losses to a part of the protocol which can be repeated until successful without risking the loss of the unknown state.

Figure 11: Quantum Makes New Cryptography Entangled Photon Schemes-Entangled Photon Sources and Detectors

31 Quantum Simulation: Ideas and Issues

Over the last two sections, we looked at how quantum computers running Shor's algorithm enable us to compromise conventional encryption schemes, such as the RSA cryptosystem. We also discuss how quantum mechanics provides a workaround via quantum cryptography and quantum key distribution. In this section, we will turn the attention to the subject of quantum simulation. It was Feynman's original insight that, if we want to simulate a quantum system, we would better use a quantum system to do it, because it is a really hard problem for a classical computer to solve. It is due to the exponentially large number of quantum states that we need to keep track of. However, what does it mean to simulate a quantum system, and how do we represent the quantum system that we want to simulate? Moreover, what does quantum mechanics do to make these simulations tractable? Further, what can go wrong? We will address these questions in this section, and review several applications based on quantum simulation. However, to get started, let us first discuss about ideas and issues associated with quantum simulation. Some of the issues and the challenges when working through quantum simulation, first, we would like to have, in principle, the knowledge that we can do the simulation. The way one approaches this is to define the problem by saying the goal is to simulate Hamiltonian; we will call the H_{sys} . However, we are given a different set of Hamiltonians, not just one Hamiltonian, but a whole family of them, which will be the Hamiltonian of the quantum computing units. Like each of the gates or each of the subsystems. We can turn them on and off at will. Then the question is, in a mathematical way, whether or not HkQC can generate H_{sys} . Mathematically, this is a beautiful group theory question about whether the algebra of H quantum computer spans the algebra of H_{sys} . However, this is the starting point for quantum computation or quantum simulation. A second idea and issue are how does one transform this kind of a set of Hamiltonians into the system that we would like to simulate. One of the earliest approaches of this is to use analog techniques, which go under the name, for example, of analog deformation. That is that we might have a Hamiltonian which has a number of terms, and our strategy would be then to manipulate these, deform them to make this Hamiltonian look like this one, for example, in a time-averaged way or in a stroboscopic way. So, for example, at every time, $T, 2T, 3T, 4T$, and so, we would like this Hamiltonian to equal that Hamiltonian, not at all times. This is the strategy and approach, for example, employed by ultracold atom gases [120], Bose-Einstein condensates, when they are being utilized to simulate, for example, a superconducting system. That naturally works out, in many ways, because they can be controlled to have similar Hamiltonians. The Bose-Einstein condensate is very controllable, and we can get an equivalent lattice spacing that is much larger than the physical lattice spacing of atoms inside a superconducting solid. Thus, we can engineer the kind of Hamiltonian we would like our quantum computer to simulate in many rich ways. So, this has been a very effective and useful approach. Here are another idea and challenge, however. Even if we can simulate so, this is, in principle, this is one method by which we can simulate we are still faced by a rather annoying and pressing challenge and question, which is what to measure. Even if we just tell us, we can simulate. If we say, we are given some state which is e^{-iHt} times some initial state, if we measure this, it collapses. Then we get only one statistical sample of that wave function. Does that tell us what we want? Does that give us an actual output? Furthermore, what are its statistical errors? Because after all, nothing is real unless it is reproducible. In Junior Physics Lab here, those of us who have taken Junior Lab to know nothing is real unless it has an error bar. We do not get an error bar from a single instance of something. However, if we have to repeat this many times, our errors now, normally, if there is just a lot of large numbers distributed, going to decrease as the square root of the number of tries. That often is not good enough, because we do not want to try an exponentially large number of times. However, naively, this is what we would

have to do here. So, what we want to do is not to measure the state. what we would like to get is some expectation value of some operator. it is going to be easier to measure that operator than it is to, say, get all the coefficients of a wave function. However, even this is fraught with difficulty because it still has the statistical randomness that we just described. It is an issue of precision. we will try to illustrate this issue with the Grover algorithm simulation topic that we will come to in two steps. then let us leave we with one more issue and idea, which is, and this is kind of outside of the scope of quantum simulation of quantum, but it is a very real one for quantum simulations [120,121]. Instead of building a quantum simulator, why not just improve our classical simulation of the quantum system by using a better approximation? [122] Moreover, this approximation might be quantum-inspired. this has happened over the last decade or so. A whole variety of new approximations have come because of quantum computation that allows us more efficient classical algorithms [123]. these have swept through condensed matter theory, and are now entering into the realm of quantum chemistry [35]. they go by a variety of names. The technique that started all of this in physics was the density matrix renormalization group idea [124,125], which was awarded the Nobel Prize, Ken Wilson. However, now, we have many more advanced techniques. So, not just DMRG and we will toss out a bunch of acronyms here, for those of we interested in this but also things like PEPS [126], MERA, and all sorts of things. we know we are entering chemistry when all we see are acronyms. These are real ways of getting very useful, highly accurate approximations to answers that we want to find in quantum chemistry [34].

There is active research going on relating to quantum computing [127,128] in support of improved classical quantum chemistry computing. So, can we comment on how we see using quantum computing to perform quantum simulations in model systems to improve approximate descriptions [129] using classical quantum chemistry and material science calculations? For example, bond-breaking and electron correlation effects. indeed, those are very challenging, in particular, the correlation effects are very challenging for mean-field theories, and density functional theory. So when we try to come up with these simulations on classical computers, a lot of times, we lose fidelity in the answers, because at various places, we have to make approximations, or truncation, and as a result, unless we start out with something that is very close to the final answer, the results we get are quite fuzzy. this, is exacerbated by, we know, when we are trying to simulate larger and larger molecules, with many atoms and electrons and degrees of freedom. Now, quantum computers, are built upon having entanglement. Long range, large scale correlations built-in. it is part of their instruction set, if we want to think of it that way. so, it seems natural that there will be an advantage using a quantum computer to solve these types of simulation problems. in fact, this really was the genesis of quantum computing with Richard Feynman, saying, we know, if we want to simulate a quantum system, we should use a quantum system to do it. Because, this is where we can access a large number of degrees of freedom. Basically, the Hilbert space gets very large in a quantum computer. so, in principle, we can do that. Now, in practice, we have to build a quantum computer that is large enough to capture these degrees of freedom, and the quantum computer has to operate for a long enough period of time that we can complete that calculation. Now, a fault-tolerant universal quantum computer will be able to do this, and when we can build that computer, we will be able to perform these algorithms. We know that, if we can build, and when we can build that computer, we will be able to have quantum advantage for these types of problems. Now, the outstanding question today in a very active area of research, is what can we do with the qubits that we have today? And so there is this acronym NISQ, Noisy Intermediate Scale Quantum Computing [130], or quantum algorithms [98]. this is a class of algorithms that is being proposed, and investigated, where typically nodes in a quantum computer will work with, in conjunction, or subservient to a classical computer, where the calculations being performed, and the classical computer will

periodically poll the smaller-scale quantum computer with these noisy qubits [131], and ask it specific questions, and get specific answers back. the question that researchers are focusing on is, can we develop such algorithms where, using the qubits we have today, with the level of coherence we have today, and the fidelities we have today, can we achieve quantum advantage in this coprocessor architecture configuration? And so, there is a lot of work in this area, and we think that what many people hope is that with these NISQ-era algorithms, we will really be able to start to demonstrate quantum enhancement for important problems, which are then commercialization, and this will kick in this virtuous cycle of development.

In 1980 Yuri Manin and 1982 Richard Feynman noticed that calculating the evolution of a quantum system using classical computational devices is inefficient and quickly becomes impossible, as the computational time scales exponentially with the number of particles involved. Their solution to this problem: use a quantum device for the calculation as it will scale much more favorably. Today, only a hand full of quantum systems can be efficiently simulated on classical computers, and exact solutions can only be determined for low-dimensional Hilbert spaces, roughly speaking the space of solutions that corresponds to the degrees of freedom involved in a problem. Larger scale simulations of materials [132], which a large part of the world-wide supercomputing time is devoted to, require approximations that unavoidably lead to errors and make, say industrially-relevant, predictions impractical. In contrast, a large-scale quantum computational device can naturally simulate higher-dimensional Hilbert spaces and hence more complex quantum problems with many particles and degrees of freedom.

Quantum simulation has applications in several fields in physics and chemistry [35, 133, 134]. In physics, the dynamics of solid-state systems involving many atoms is a vast field of a study investigating, e.g., magnetic materials used in hard drives or the electrons in a superconducting material, where collective quantum effects allow for the loss-less transmission of electricity. Similarly, in chemistry, it is a challenge to describe the complicated energy level structure of atoms and molecules and the processes involved in a chemical reaction. This was famously stated by Paul Dirac in 1929 when he remarked that “The underlying physical laws necessary for the mathematical theory of a large part of physics and the whole of chemistry are thus completely known, and the difficulty is only that the exact application of these laws leads to equations much too complicated to be soluble.” [135–140]. For example, nitrogen fixation is a process in which nitrogen from the air is bound in the form of ammonia (NH_3), which makes it accessible to plants. It is common in a range of bacteria, yet it has been elusive to reproduce efficiently on an industrial scale. Today, much of the fertilizer production still relies on the very energy-intensive Haber-Bosch process, which requires a pressure of around 200 atmospheres and temperatures of around 400°C (842°F). Quantum simulation is a promising tool to describe and understand this problem already with a medium scale quantum computer, which was worked out as an example in 2017 [34].

So, about quantum chemistry, and it says, it is often-cited that, this is likely the near term, killer application, what does this mean, and when do we think a meaningful quantum advantage might be demonstrated? we are going to look at this in more detail, so next section, we will be looking at Schrodinger’s equation, and how to simulate that, how to simulate Hamiltonians and dynamics. we think it is true that this is the killer application. The governments care a lot about security but in terms of breaking cryptographic protocols, or encoding information [141], in particular, the breaking the cryptographic protocols, that will not be a huge, there is not going to generate a huge business around it, because there are only a few people who really want to use that to break other people’s codes. But quantum chemistry, simulating say quantum chemistry, or new materials, pharmaceuticals, drug discovery, things like this [132]. This is where we can really imagine large businesses being developed. so, it is intriguing because, many

of these quantum chemistry problems actually do, the ones that are hard, actually do rely on, say, entanglement, and we can map them over on to the working principles of a quantum computer, we know, quantum mechanics. so, we will discuss much more about this next section. as to when we will have them, there are two pathways here, and one is we build a fault-tolerant, error corrected, universal quantum computer, and when we have that one, then we will be able to get quantum chemistry. But in the near term, it is developing these NISQ algorithms, very likely in a coprocessor configuration where a classical computer is, as we have discussed about earlier, asking questions to a smaller quantum computer, or set of quantum computing nodes, and periodically polls it for answers. if these nodes can return an answer with quantum advantage, then fine, overall, there is a quantum advantage to doing this.

Many challenges remain, both in the size of the calculable problem (related to the number of qubits) and length of simulation (related to the coherence time and accumulation of errors). Hence, various approaches to quantum simulation are being pursued, divided coarsely along the lines of digital simulations, operating a quantum computer as a universal, gate-based machine, and analog simulations in which the available Hamiltonian on a quantum device is mapped and/or deformed to mimic the behavior of another quantum system. A fairly recent step is the introduction of hybrid simulations [142, 143], which combines analog elements with digital gates and generally run in the form of optimization algorithms, where a classical computer guides the computation and the quantum devices sequentially scan the parameter space to find, e.g., an energy minimum. The Variational Quantum Eigensolver discussed later during this section, is an example of one such algorithm. Another hybrid quantum-classical algorithm is Variational Quantum Fidelity Estimation [36], variational quantum factoring (VQF) algorithm [37, 144, 145].

32 What is a Hamiltonian

We introduced several ideas and issues at play in the previous section when implementing quantum simulations on a quantum computer. The simulation begins with a representation of the system being simulated, and once we have this representation, we can then choose how to simulate it. Quantum systems are generally defined in terms of a mathematical representation called a Hamiltonian [146]. with a Hamiltonian in hand, as discussed in section one, one can simulate the Hamiltonian dynamics using universal gates. It is called a digital simulator. Alternatively, one can use the qubits and the couplings to mimic the system and its Hamiltonian directly. It is called an analog simulator or an emulator [147]. In either case, we need to define the simulation problem in terms of a Hamiltonian, which characterizes the system of interest. Thus, that leads us to the subject of this section, what is a Hamiltonian? A Hamiltonian is a mathematical construct that can be used to describe the time evolution of a system. Now, these systems can be classical, like a ball rolling off a table, or they can be quantum mechanical, like the qubits we have been looked at throughout the section. It sounds pretty abstract, so Let us take a look at how to use a Hamiltonian more concretely. we might remember from physics how to predict an object's motion using Newton's laws. First, we write down all the forces acting on our system, taking note of both the strength and direction of each force. we can keep track of all these forces using a free body diagram, like the one shown here. Once we have written down all the forces, we can invoke one of the fundamental laws of physics. Newton's second law of motion tells us that the sum of all the forces acting on a system is equal to the mass of the system multiplied by its acceleration. Now, this equation is extremely powerful. Recall that acceleration is the rate of change of velocity with respect to time, like our car going from 0 to 60 miles an hour on the highway. Meanwhile, velocity is simply the rate of change in an object's position with respect to time. We can rewrite the acceleration as the second derivative of the system's position with

respect to time. When we make the substitution to Newton's second law, we see that we now have a differential equation, which relates the second time derivative of position to the sum of the forces acting on the system. These forces can be constant, or they can be some function of the position of the system. When we solve this differential equation [148], we get an equation x of t , which tells us the system's position at any arbitrary time. So, we have used the forces acting on the system to figure out how it moves in time. As it turns out, this is not the only method we can use to arrive at the exact same result. Instead of thinking of the forces acting on the system, let us focus on the system's energy. Generally, a system has two types of energy, kinetic energy, the energy that comes from a system's motion, and potential energy, the latent energy stored in the system waiting to be converted into motion. Let us write down each of these energies as equations. A system's kinetic energy is equal to its momentum squared divided by 2 times its mass. Momentum, we might remember, is related to an object's speed. So, the faster an object moves, the more kinetic energy it has. A system's potential energy depends on the forces that it is experiencing. So, we need to know exactly what forces we are dealing with and order to write down an exact equation. However, in general, we can say that the potential energy is some function of the system's position, just like the forces were. So, we have two types of energy, one which depends on the system's momentum, and one which depends on its position. Let us add these two energies together to get an expression for the total energy stored in the system. This expression for the total energy in the system is called it is Hamiltonian. as we can see, the Hamiltonian depends on two parameters, position, and momentum. These two parameters have a special role in physics, and we call them the canonical coordinates of the system. So, why is the Hamiltonian important? As it turns out, just as we previously used Newton's laws to find the system's motion in time from a set of forces, we can use the Hamiltonian to arrive at the same result. To do this, we invoke two extremely elegant equations known as Hamilton's equations. The first equation tells us that the rate of change of the systems' position in time will be equal to the derivative of its Hamiltonian with respect to momentum. Symmetrically, the second equation then tells us that the rate of change of the momentum of the system in time is equal to the derivative of its Hamiltonian with respect to position. Just like Newton's laws, these are differential equations, and if we solve these equations, we arrive at expressions that tell us how the systems position and momentum change in time. With these expressions in hand, we can see where the system is and how fast it is moving at any arbitrary time. To summarize, as long as we have the Hamiltonian of the system and an initial set of conditions, we can calculate exactly how the system will evolve in time. So, far everything we just discussed has referred to classical systems. What about quantum systems? The formalism of Hamiltonian physics is the architecture of quantum mechanics [149, 150]. Like in classical mechanics, we can write down the total energy of the quantum system as a Hamiltonian. This Hamiltonian is simply the sum of the systems kinetic and potential energies, as in the classical case. However, note one minor difference. Whereas in the classical case, the Hamiltonian was a scalar function of the system's momentum and position, in quantum mechanics, the Hamiltonian takes on the form of a quantum operator, which acts on a given quantum state. we now invoke a fundamental relationship of quantum mechanics. The operation of a Hamiltonian on a given quantum state is equal to the rate of state change in time. This relationship is called Schrodinger's equation, and it tells us that if we know the operator responsible for the energy of the system, that is the Hamiltonian, we can solve for the evolution of that state in time. For this reason, we often say that the Hamiltonian generates the dynamics of a quantum system. Let us look at how to use the Hamiltonian more concretely in quantum mechanics. Imagine that the quantum system is a single qubit. we can write the qubit's state as a vector with two entries, A and B, which correspond to the probability of measuring the system, either at a 0 or 1 state at a given time. Just like in the classic example, the exact form of the Hamiltonian depends entirely on what

forces that are acting on the qubit. However, in general, we can always write the Hamiltonian of a qubit as a two by two Hermitian matrix. A Hermitian matrix is a special type of square matrix that is equal to its conjugate transpose. When we plug the state vector and Hamiltonian matrix into Schrodinger's equation, we get two linearly independent differential equations that can be solved to find the values of A and B at any arbitrary time. When we solve these differential equations, we find that for an arbitrary Hamiltonian, an initial state, ψ_0 , the quantum state at the time, t , will be equal to the complex exponential, e to the iHt time the initial state, ψ_0 . Recall that we just said the Hamiltonian is a Hermitian matrix. When we work out the math, we can show that e to the iHt is a new matrix, which is unitary. By this point in the section, we are already intimately familiar with unitary operators, like x, y, and z rotations or Hadamard gates. we can now see where these gates physically come from. To implement a particular qubit gate, we must engineer a qubit with the correct Hamiltonian, and apply it for the right amount of time, such that the evolution of the state produces the unitary operator that we need. So, we just showed how to solve for the dynamics of a single qubit. Let us see how this problem scales when we try solving the dynamics of many qubits. To represent a system of n qubits, we need a state vector with 2^n entries, corresponding to each of the possible states we might measure the system in. To generate the dynamics of this quantum state, we need a Hamiltonian matrix with 2^n by 2^n entries. Indeed, as we add more qubits to the system, the number of matrix elements that we need to keep track of in the Hamiltonian scales exponentially. To make matters worse, if we want to solve the dynamics of the system, we need to exponentiate this massive matrix, which is an extremely computationally demanding operation. As we can see, solving for the dynamics of an arbitrary quantum state is an exponentially hard problem classically [151]. This observation has profound consequences, and as we will see in this section, it provides the primary motivation for quantum simulation on a quantum computer.

The Hamiltonian is a physical quantity that represents the total energy of a system. For a closed system, one that is isolated from its environment, so we can focus solely on the system itself, the Hamiltonian is the sum of the kinetic and potential energy. For example, for a one-particle quantum system, the Hamiltonian is

$$\hat{H} = \frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} + \hat{V}$$

where $\frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m}$ corresponds to the kinetic energy with momentum operator \hat{p} , and \hat{V} is the potential energy of the particle.

The Hamiltonian enables one to find the time evolution of a quantum system. In the Schrödinger formulation of quantum mechanics, the state of a particle is represented by a time-dependent wave function $\psi(\vec{x}, t)$. The time evolution of a quantum system is then described by the Schrödinger equation:

$$\hat{H}\psi(\vec{x}, t) = i\hbar \frac{d}{dt}\psi(\vec{x}, t), \quad (85)$$

where $\hbar \equiv h/2\pi$ is Planck's constant h divided by 2π . Erwin Schrödinger first developed this equation (85) in 1925, and it was the basis for his 1933 Nobel Prize in Physics.

The Schrödinger equation has a formal solution,

$$\psi(\vec{x}, t) = e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar}\psi(\vec{x}, 0), \quad (86)$$

Which one can use to find the time-evolution of the quantum state given its initial condition? However, because the size of the Hamiltonian increases exponentially with the size of the system,

for example, for n qubits, the size of the matrix representing the Hamiltonian operator is $2^n \times 2^n$ solving the differential equation becomes intractable on a classical computer for large n . Thus, another approach is warranted and, throughout this section, we will introduce several techniques that have been developed for quantum computers to simulate the static and dynamical properties of Hamiltonian systems.

33 Simulation Example Particle in Box

Let us work through something concrete. First, we would like to show we the example of a particle in a one-dimensional well. It is entry-level quantum mechanics. We start at this point because we are very familiar with it, and it will illustrate the first two steps in a quantum simulation process. Imagine that we have a particle located on a one-dimensional axis, and there is some potential V of x —the somewhere delocalized in here. Let the scale of this heat from minus d to plus d or so. Furthermore, the particle is governed by a Hamiltonian, which is of the form p squared over $2m$ plus V of x . So, this is the energy of a free particle, the kinetic energy. It is the potential energy. This is the set of T terms, and this is the set of V terms that are canonical in a molecule as well. This is a very simplistic scenario, but it is not all that far away from the more complicated molecular Hamiltonian [152]. Moreover, the first step that one employs in simulating the dynamics of this physical system is to discretize. So, normally, we will have some continuous set over the infinite one-dimensional axis. So, we can imagine that these are some coefficients that we have. So, this has now expanded into the eigenbasis of position x . the natural thing for us to do is to replace this with something discrete, like k delta x , so, that this is in some way now going to be a sum over some coefficients, C sub k of k delta x where we choose the delta x to be sufficiently small and defined over this discrete interval from minus d to d . So, many of we have done this, especially if we are doing a computer simulation of such a particle in a potential. It should be very comfortable. The second thing that we do is to be able to simulate the Hamiltonian. So, we evolve the system. Now, how does one evolve a system under a Hamiltonian? The problem is that this Hamiltonian here is comprised of two parts, H_1 and H_2 , and they do not commute. Just let evolution, e to the minus i h t we cannot simply let this be e to the minus i h_1 t e to the minus i h_2 t . we cannot evolve with one Hamiltonian then evolve with a second Hamiltonian, even though they are added here because they do not commute with each other. Furthermore, this should be something we are very familiar with. Therefore, we have to apply an approximation. The approximation we apply in order to simulate this some of the Hamiltonians is the Lie Product formula, which says that in the limit as we take an infinite number of partitions of e to the i h_1 t divided by n , e to the minus i h_2 t divided by n , where we evolve by the first Hamiltonian for a small sliver of time, t divided by n , then the second one for another small sliver of time. Repeat this many times, taking the slivers to become smaller and smaller. It gives us equality, which is the sum of the two Hamiltonians. Now, this is a beautiful mathematical fact. Unfortunately, when we do the actual simulation, we have to truncate it at some point, and errors start to pop in. When we truncate it at a certain point, this method is called Trotterization [30].

The system of a particle in a box is a useful example to study, as it is one of the few systems that can be solved analytically.

A particle with mass m in one dimension that can move freely over a length a_x between $x = 0$ and $x = a$, but is restricted from entering positions at $x < 0$ or $x > a$, is referred to as a particle in a one-dimensional box or a one-dimensional rectangular potential well. The particle is subject to a potential energy $\hat{V}(x) = \infty$ outside the box ($x < 0$ and $x > a$) and $\hat{V}(x) = 0$ inside the box.

The time-independent Schrödinger equation for a particle in such a one-dimensional rectangular potential well is:

$$\hat{H}\psi(x) = \left(\frac{\hat{p}^2}{2m} + \hat{V}(x) \right) \psi(x) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \psi(x) \quad (87)$$

for $0 \leq x \leq a$.

where $\hat{p} = -i\hbar\partial/\partial x$ is the momentum operator. In contrast, outside of the potential well ($x < 0$ and $x > a$) the potential energy is $\hat{V}(x) = \infty$, and the wavefunction $\psi(x)$ does not enter this region.

The most general solution is

$$\psi(x) = A \sin(kx) + B \cos(kx), \quad (88)$$

with $k^2 = 2mE/\hbar^2$. The constant coefficients A and B are determined by the boundary conditions

$$\psi(0) = \psi(a_x) = 0, \quad (89)$$

due to the fact that the particle is not able to enter the infinitely high potential well. The first condition at $x=0$ yields $B=0$, and the second condition at $x = a_x$ requires $A \sin(kx) = 0$. Therefore, $ka_x = n\pi$, with $n = 1, 2, \dots$. With this solution, the Schrödinger equation gives energy eigenvalues

$$E_n = \frac{\hbar^2 n^2}{8ma_x^2}. \quad (90)$$

The integer n is called a quantum number, and it labels the energy levels of the system.

In conclusion, the wave function of a one-dimensional rectangular potential well can be written as

$$\psi_n(x) = A \sin(n\pi x/a_x). \quad (91)$$

The parameter A normalizes the wave function to ensure

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |\psi_n(x)|^2 dx = 1,$$

that is, the integral of the probability density function over the entire space is unity or, in other words, the particle is somewhere in the box with absolute certainty. Since the wave function $\psi_n(x)$ is only non-zero inside the potential well,

$$\int_0^a |\psi_n(x)|^2 dx = 1$$

yields normalization parameter $A = \sqrt{2/a}$.

The problem of a particle in a one-dimensional rectangular potential well can be generalized to two and three dimensions. For a particle in a two-dimensional box of length a_x and a_y the Schrödinger equation inside the potential well is given as follows:

$$\left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right] \psi(x, y) = E\psi(x, y) \quad (92)$$

The potential $V(x, y)$ is again zero inside the potential well, and infinite elsewhere. The solutions can be derived using the method of separation of variables. Separation of variables

expresses the total wave function as a multiplication of two different functions, one for each dimension:

$$\psi(x, y) = \Psi_x(x)\Psi_y(y). \quad (93)$$

The two-dimensional Schrödinger equation subsequently results as:

$$-\Psi_y(y)\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\Psi_x(x) - \Psi_x(x)\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}\Psi_y(y) = E\Psi_x(x)\Psi_y(y), \quad (94)$$

wich can be rewritten as

$$-\frac{1}{\Psi_x(x)}\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\Psi_x(x) - \frac{1}{\Psi_y(y)}\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}\Psi_y(y) = E. \quad (95)$$

If the sum of two independent functions is constant, both functions have to be constant as well:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{\psi_x(x)}\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}\psi_x(x) &= E_x, \\ -\frac{1}{\psi_y(y)}\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}\psi_y(y) &= E_y, \\ E_x + E_y &= E \end{aligned} \quad (96)$$

These two equations are two, independent one-dimensional problems, one in the x- and one in the y-direction. Thus, the solutions for the energies in each dimension are

$$E_x = \frac{\hbar^2 n_x^2}{8ma_x^2} \quad (97)$$

and

$$E_y = \frac{\hbar^2 n_y^2}{8ma_y^2} \quad (98)$$

with quantum numbers n_x and n_y . The wave functions $\psi_x(x)$ and $\psi_y(y)$ are normalized by A_x and A_y respectively. Finally, the total normalized wave function can be expressed as

$$\psi(x, y) = \sqrt{4/(a_x a_y)} \sin(n_x \pi x / a_x) \sin(n_y \pi y / a_y). \quad (99)$$

The generalization to three dimensions follows the same mathematical procedure with a separation of variables and three dimensional boundary conditions. The normalized wave function results as

$$\psi(x, y, z) = \sqrt{8/(a_x a_y a_z)} \sin(n_x \pi x / a_x) \sin(n_y \pi y / a_y) \sin(n_z \pi z / a_z). \quad (100)$$

34 Hamiltonian Simulation: Trotterization

In the previous section, we discussed the quantum simulation of a particle in a box. Towards the end of the section, we reviewed an important technique for quantum simulation called Trotterization. In this section, we will take a closer look at Trotterization and see why it is such an important tool for quantum simulations. As we have already seen, the first step in quantum

simulation is to write down the Hamiltonian, which governs the dynamics of the system we want to simulate. The Hamiltonians have generally separated into different terms corresponding to the system's different types of energy, for example, the kinetic and potential energies. Alternatively, for systems of many qubits, we might instead use a sum of single-qubit energies plus terms which correspond to qubit-qubit interactions. However, we define the Hamiltonian, the goal of the quantum simulation is to take an initial quantum state ψ at time t_0 and find out where it ends up at a later time t . As we introduced in the "What is a Hamiltonian?" section, the state ψ at time t results from the initial state ψ_0 acted upon by the operator e^{-iHt} where H is the Hamiltonian. Now, e^{-iHt} is a unitary operator, and, in principle, it can be decomposed into a series of qubit gates and placed into a block in the circuit diagram. However, these operations may be hard to realize in practice. Alternatively, we can break the Hamiltonian into pieces that are more tractable to implement, such as single-qubit rotations and elementary two-qubit gates. To get started, let us say we have a Hamiltonian H that can be broken into two terms, H_0 and H_1 . While H is very difficult to implement, H_0 and H_1 are much easier. So, how can we use these simpler terms to implement the total Hamiltonian H ? Now, we might think that we can simply implement these two terms as two sequential time evolutions, each acting on the system for the total time t , and then we are done. However, unfortunately, this does not work. While it is certainly true that H equals H_0 plus H_1 , it is not necessarily true that e^{-iHt} equals e^{-iH_0t} times e^{-iH_1t} . It is because, in general, the operators H_0 and H_1 do not commute with one another. Commutation is a mathematical concept that we take for granted in basic arithmetic. We can multiply numbers in any order and still get the same answer. For example, 3 times 6 is equal to 6 times 3. The order in which we multiply does not matter. Because we can rearrange the numbers on either side of the multiplication sign, we say that multiplication of scalar numbers is commutative and that these numbers commute. Now, it turns out, and this statement is not always true for quantum operators. As we discuss in section 1, we can represent quantum operators as unitary matrices. To check if multiplication still commutes, let us consider two elementary quantum operators, the z and x operators. When we multiply these matrices, it is clear that z times x does not equal x times z . Therefore, in general, operator matrix multiplication does not obey the commutative property, and we say that the operators z and x do not commute with one another. This means that order matters when we apply these operators to qubits. Change the order, and we get a different outcome. Now, returning to the Hamiltonian problem, we see that implementing H_0 first and then H_1 will give us a different result than if we first implemented H_1 and then H_0 . How can we take advantage of the simpler terms, H_0 and H_1 , and simulate the full Hamiltonian? This is where the concept called Trotterization comes in. The Suzuki-Trotter method, or Trotterization for short, takes advantage of a clever decomposition of matrices, which allows us to simulate the action of a Hamiltonian using only its constituent pieces. Instead of just breaking the Hamiltonian into two terms and evolving each for the full-time t , we will also break the time evolution into n small pieces and run each evolution for a small fraction t/n of the total time t . We will then repeatedly implement this smaller interleaved evolution a total of n times such that, by the end of the protocol, the system is evolved for the full-time t . As we make n larger and larger that is, as we make the stepwise evolution smaller and smaller, the Trotterization procedure becomes equivalent to evolving the original Hamiltonian H for the full-time t . This remarkable relationship is known as the Trotter equation. By breaking the Hamiltonian time evolution into small pieces and toggling between each term of the Hamiltonian, Trotterization enables us to simulate the full Hamiltonian evolution using only its constituent terms, even if those terms do not commute with one another. As a result, this concept is a powerful, almost universally applicable approach to the simulation of quantum systems and their dynamical evolution.

The time evolution of a quantum system with a time-independent Hamiltonian \hat{H} is described

by $|\psi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar}|\psi(0)\rangle$. In this expression, the operator $\hat{U}(t) = e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar}$ is a unitary operator [153] that describes the evolution of the state.

In cases where determining or implementing a single Hamiltonian \hat{H} is challenging, it can often be expressed as $\hat{H} = \sum_n \hat{H}_n$, a sum of simpler Hamiltonians \hat{H}_i that are chosen to be more straightforward to implement. However, the sum of Hamiltonians does not imply $\hat{U}(t) \neq \prod_n e^{-i\hat{H}_n t/\hbar}$, because Hamiltonians do not commute with each other in general.

If two operators \hat{A} and \hat{B} do not commute that is, $[\hat{A}, \hat{B}] = \hat{A}\hat{B} - \hat{B}\hat{A} \equiv c$, where c is a scalar number not equal to zero then the exponentiation of a sum of \hat{A} and \hat{B} differs from the multiplication of each exponentiated operator:

$$e^{\hat{A}+\hat{B}} \neq e^{\hat{A}}e^{\hat{B}}. \quad (101)$$

Rather, the correct expression is given by the Baker-Campbell-Hausdorff formula:

$$e^{\hat{A}+\hat{B}} = e^{\hat{A}}e^{\hat{B}}e^{\frac{1}{2}[\hat{A}, \hat{B}]}. \quad (102)$$

The Lie product formula provides a means to simplify the simulation of a sum of Hamiltonians.

$$\hat{U}(t) = e^{-i\hat{H}t/\hbar} = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \left(\prod_n e^{-i\hat{H}_n t/\tau\hbar} \right)^\tau \quad (103)$$

Essentially, the Lie product formula divides the system time evolution in small time-steps t/τ , each of which implements one factor in the product form of the full Hamiltonian, and then repeats it τ times. In practice, if the time steps are small enough, this approach called ‘‘Trotterization’’ is a good approximation to the original time evolution. In the limit $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, corresponding to infinitesimal time slices repeated an infinite number of times, this relation is exact.

Trotterization: The total Hamiltonian of a quantum system can be defined by more than one term, such as $H = H_1 + H_2$., When $H_1H_2 \neq H_2H_1$ it is said that H_1 and H_2 do not commute. Evolving the system under H is not equivalent to evolving it under H_1 and then H_2 , or vice versa.

If a quantum system in an initial state $|\psi_0\rangle$ is allowed to evolve for a time t under the Hamiltonian H , then the state of the system after evolution is given by

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = \exp\{-iHt\}|\psi_0\rangle. \quad (104)$$

Since H_1 and H_2 do not commute, finding an explicit expression for $|\psi(t)\rangle$ is not as simple as computing

$$|\psi(t)\rangle = \exp\{-iH_1t\}\exp\{-iH_2t\}|\psi_0\rangle \text{ (wrong)}. \quad (105)$$

Which of the following phrases is not valid?

Trotterization is a method that determines the evolution of a quantum system under non-commuting Hamiltonians The Trotter-Suzuki expansion comes from truncating the Lie product formula The Lie product formula given by,

$$\exp\{-i(H_1 + H_2)t\} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\exp\left\{ \left(-iH_1 \frac{t}{n} \right) \right\} \exp\left\{ \left(-iH_2 \frac{t}{n} \right) \right\} \right)^n, \quad (106)$$

can be used to determine the time evolution of $\exp\{-iHt\}|\psi_0\rangle$ and is exact in the limit $n \rightarrow \infty$ The Trotter-Suzuki expansion can only be used for Hamiltonians of the form $H = H_1 + H_2$

35 Simulation of Chemistry Problems

we want to illustrate the simulation challenge to us today with one very specific thing, and this specific thing has to do with a well-known task known as nitrogen fixation. Nitrogen fixation is a process that happens in nature that involves taking gaseous nitrogen from the atmosphere and then combining that with protons, typically from water, and then producing as a result of these two molecules of ammonia. In natural systems, in biological systems, this is not usually ammonia but probably ammonium. However, this is one of the most important processes for biological systems, including our life. It is the rate of this nitrogen fixation process that limits the production, for example, of food. It is an important and interesting reaction that can be illustrated by looking at the reaction diagram of the process. So, let this be a reaction coordinate so, progress as the reaction proceeds from the left-hand side to the right-hand side of this equation. The fact is that the reactants coming in have a certain kind of energy and not be too specific about it. However, they have to overcome an enormous activation energy barrier before being able to exit the reaction as a product, the ammonia that we have here. This energy difference here is on the order of 50 kilojoules per mole of the reactants. This energy activation barrier here is much higher, on the order of 400 kilojoules per mole. Thus, although it is desirable to be able to fixate the nitrogen and produce ammonia, we have to at least, if we have no other recourse, supply a great deal of energy before we can get this recovery of energy since this is an endothermic reaction. Many of us may not know, but we have a lot of nitrogens in the body 50% of the nitrogens in our body, according to an article in Nature in the early 2000s, comes from a single chemical process. It is remarkable to realize and appreciate that so much of ourselves, the bodies, and the nitrogen are dependent on this process known as the Haber-Bosch process circa 1911. Fritz Haber and Bosch won Nobel prizes for their work in this area. It is a process, which creates high ammonia from nitrogen and steam by cracking it. Thus, it utilizes metal catalysts at a very high temperature and pressure, 200 megapascals, and something like 450 degrees Celsius in a very large-scale industrial process to generate ammonia. What is the ammonia then used for? It turns out that it is used for fertilizer, and that fertilizer goes into us, the human body, and we can estimate that it probably is responsible for something on the order of the sustenance of 40% of the world's population. Enormous industrial-scale production. At the same time, the cost is between 1% and 2% of the world's energy. Now, this is fascinating. It is a strange place, perhaps to be discussing starting a section on quantum computation. However, the idea that nitrogen fixation is not done by nature using the Haber-Bosch process, using this very high temperature, a very high-pressure industrial process. Instead, nature does it with catalysts, not metal catalysts, but biological catalysts, which are enzymes, such as in bacteria, at room temperature, and room pressure. It does it a remarkably different way, which we do not understand today. The example of how this is done is with a special enzyme known as nitrogenase. This is a bacteria enzyme, one of many different kinds of enzymes, which are able to fixate nitrogen from the atmosphere and turn it into ammonium and ammonia. However, what is remarkable about this enzyme is that we do not understand how and why it works today. On the order of a dozen other kinds of varieties of biological enzymes have been manufactured or extracted to accomplish the same task that the Haber-Bosch process does. However, none of them is quite stable and efficient and long-running as what happens in biology today. Now, the reason we do not understand this is because this is all happening in a complex molecule. The actual reaction, which we wrote over there, involves much more than just nitrogen and two molecules of water or hydrogen coming in. Let us balance the reaction over here. Many other things are happening inside these processes. For example, there are 8 protons and 8 electrons that come in typically. It may also involve a proton pump with adenosine triphosphate, losing phosphorus to become on the other side, 16 ADP, and 16 phosphorus like this. So, nature uses a very small amount of energy to be able to

catalyze this and take this nitrogen fixation reaction over the activation energy barrier. Now, why is this possible? It turns out there is this amazing center inside this nitrogenase called the iron-molybdenum complex. It has on the order of 100 kilodaltons of atoms inside this, so we are discussing it on the order of 1,000 carbon atoms. They are all shaped in various ways with alpha helices and beta sheets. These shapes then allow of the nitrogen and the hydrogen coming in to dock in a certain way. Then because of where they are docked, they can react and do so much more efficiently than they are able to do in this heterogeneous type of catalytic reaction that is industrially done. So, we would love to, in quantum chemistry, synthesize molecules that have such functionality because we could catalyze all sorts of other reactions. We cannot understand why this is happening from a fundamental standpoint today because we do not know what is happening in a quantum mechanical way with this molecule. Only very recently was even the structure of the molecule understood as with X-ray crystallography and the like. So, we, in principle, could do so. In principle, we can write down all we need in order to figure out what is happening in this because the system is a very simple Hamiltonian in principle. There is the kinetic energy of nucleons, there is the kinetic energy of the electrons, and then there are interaction terms between the nucleons and nucleons, between the nucleons and the electrons, and electrons and electrons. We will expand into this Hamiltonian in a little bit to show we concretely what this means. However, suffice to say that we can write down a very accurate description of the system. We cannot do what we do not know how to do, but to solve for things like the reaction rate and even more simply, just the ground state of the system.

36 Phase Estimation

we have taken H . We have modeled it with some simplified h prime. Then the two pathways the community has taken, which are rather distinct, are first to utilize what we have already discussed in this section, the phase estimation algorithm. This will give us the ground state and the energy of the ground state approximately. The second approach does something different and is known as a variational quantum eigensolver. We will now find the literature replete with people discussing the VQE algorithm. We want us to know what it is because there is a lot of discussion about that. This will give us a state ψ , which might be if we are lucky to close to the ground state, and energy, which might be if we are lucky, the ground state but has a certain guarantee that this energy will be no smaller than the ground state energy that we are looking for. So, let us look at these two different routes, one at a time. The first approach, phase estimation, is very simple to understand, as we described because it is no more than the application of phase estimation. We start with registered qubits, where we are going to store the eigenenergy. So, this is determined by the imprecision that we want the number of qubits. We also start with a state ψ , which is an approximation of the ground state, but we do not know how good it is. So, it is the ground state plus epsilon times some other component, which is orthogonal to the ground state. Allow that we have prepared this somehow. We may prepare it badly. That is still fine. We perform H . It is going to be some sum over all values k . We perform a controlled h to the k operation over here. It is feasible because we have shown we how to trotterize. However, this is painful because we now have to trot right and also trot right to the k th power. So, now we have to rerun that [trotterization] an exponentially large number of a span of energy, for example. But allow this. We know from the phase estimation algorithm that what we get as the output of this is going to be a sum over energy eigenstates and then phases, which are on the order of some constant over $e^{-iE_k t}$. So, these are going to give us the energies of the system. It is the top register, and this is the bottom register. There are some coefficients. When we measure this top register after the quantum Fourier transform, we collapse into an eigenstate down here. If our

initial overlap is sufficiently large, so, epsilon is small, then we get the ground state that we desire. We will have a measure, which is the energy eigenstate. However, by the way, this is exactly Shor's algorithm. It is a quantum factoring algorithm also being used for quantum simulation. It is not accidental that all known exponentially fast algorithms today, quantum algorithms are essentially the structure of Shor's factoring algorithm. We put something in superposition. We do control something to a higher power based on the superposition. We do the inverse quantum Fourier transform. So, if we know Shor's factoring algorithm, we essentially know this whole route to quantum simulation. Why is this challenging? Well, first, it is good because we get the eigenstate and eigenenergy, the ground state, right away. However, the challenge is that we need a perfect quantum computer with long coherence times. There is a beautiful analysis of the requirements by Matthias Troyer and others from now at Microsoft [154, 155], where he shows that if one uses this phase estimation approach, one can simulate nitrogenase exactly what we started in section. If we can run the quantum computer for about a day with a relatively fast clock cycle as well, the longest coherence time we have for many of the quantum bits like in superconductors is on the order of a millisecond [156]. For ions, it is perhaps tens of seconds. So, a day is a bit of a stretch right now. This might need something on the order of a million qubits as well, whereas, in the actual deliverable common computers, companies are discussing 50 qubits today. So, that gives us an idea of the gap between the ideal system needed and that which is available.

Phase estimation is an important module of several quantum algorithms, such as Shor's factorization algorithm. Suppose there is a unitary operator \hat{U} with eigenvector $|u\rangle$ and eigenvalue $e^{2\pi i\phi}$ with an unknown value ϕ . As the name "phase estimation" suggests, the module estimates the phase ϕ of an eigenvalue of a system with eigenvector $|u\rangle$ and operator \hat{U} .

The quantum phase estimation protocol requires a register with n qubits initialized in the ground-state and a second register representing state $|u\rangle$. The number of qubits n can be chosen arbitrarily and ultimately defines the digital accuracy of the estimated phase ϕ as well as the probability of success.

The first step of the protocol creates a superposition state composed of the n qubits of the first register. The second step involves controlled U^{2^j} operation on state $|u\rangle$. The non-negative integer j in U^{2^j} depends on the individual controlling qubit, $j = 0, \dots, n - 1$.

Figure 12: Phase Estimation

The first register prior to implementing the inverse quantum Fourier transformation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{2^{n/2}} \left(|0\rangle + e^{2\pi i 2^{n-1} \phi} |1\rangle \right) \left(|0\rangle + e^{2\pi i 2^{n-2} \phi} |1\rangle \right) \dots \left(|0\rangle + e^{2\pi i 2^0 \phi} |1\rangle \right) \quad (107)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2^{n/2}} \sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} e^{2\pi i k \phi} |k\rangle \quad (108)$$

Subsequently, an inverse quantum Fourier transformation is applied on the first register, yielding:

$$\frac{1}{2^{n/2}} \sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} e^{2\pi i k \phi} |k\rangle \xrightarrow{QFT_n^{-1}} \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{k,l=0}^{2^n-1} e^{-\frac{2\pi i k l}{2^n}} e^{2\pi i k \phi} |l\rangle = \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{l=0}^{2^n-1} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{2^n-1} \left(e^{-\frac{2\pi i k l}{2^n}} e^{2\pi i k \phi} \right)^k \right] |l\rangle \quad (109)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2^n} \sum_{l=0}^{2^n-1} \frac{1 - e^{2\pi i (2^n \phi - l)}}{1 - e^{2\pi i (\phi - l/2^n)}} |l\rangle \quad (110)$$

The sum in the square brackets is a geometric sum and can be simplified. The resultant state contains the estimation of the phase ϕ . Suppose ϕ can be expressed with n bits as $\phi = 0.\phi_1 \dots \phi_n$. Then, the exponential term $(2^n \phi - l)$ can be expressed as $(\phi_1 \dots \phi_n - l)$ with l being an integer between 0 and $2^n - 1$. Note that exponential terms are periodic in $2\pi i$ thus $e^{2\pi i 1.\phi_n} = e^{2\pi i (1+0.\phi_n)} = e^{2\pi i 0.\phi_n}$. The last term $l = 2^n - 1$ contains all digits of ϕ up to the n^{th} digit, which determines the precision of the phase estimation protocol.

The phase estimation protocol enables the estimation of the eigenvalue's phase ϕ of a quantum system with an operator \hat{U} and eigenvector $|u\rangle$. The output of the measurement of n qubits estimates the phase ϕ up to a precision $\propto n$.

37 Variational Quantum Eigensolver

So, now we come to the second approach. The point of this second approach, VQE, is to get by with a much poorer, worse quantum computer by not asking for quite as much, and we will see how that works by describing the algorithm. The point of this argument is to rely upon the variational principle, which in this context says that if we were given some state, ψ , which is not the ground state. We measure the Hamiltonian's expectation value, which is full total Hamiltonian with respect to that state. We will get some expectation value average energy, which is no smaller than the energy of the ground state. So, therefore, we might do something like introducing a bunch of parameters here. Let us call these θ . So, $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$, and say we use the θ to manipulate the degrees of freedom we have in the input state to this expectation value. Then again, it will also be no smaller than that. So, we might define this thing as an expectation value of H parameterized by some θ . we can do this on a classical computer, but the hardest part about the classical computation is preparing this state and then computing this matrix element of H with that state. the VQE algorithm proposes to do those two steps on a quantum computer. the rest, it does with a classical computer. So, here are the steps. Prepare ψ of θ , where θ it is controlled by a classical algorithm, and this is done on a quantum computer. ensure this H of θ , and there are many ways of doing this measurement. One of which we will describe in a moment if we have time on a quantum computer. then, third, take this classical measurement result that we now have and run an optimization algorithm. For example, the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm, or stochastic gradient descent, or we choose our favorite optimization algorithm, changing θ to minimize each of θ . go back to the beginning, and this is done on a classical computer. So, now we have a hybrid, where we have a quantum computer executing some steps, and a classical computer executing some other steps. we can show that this kind of a variational expectation value is true even if we have a natty density matrix here, instead of a pure state. So, if our quantum computer starts to devolve and go not so, quantum on we halfway through, it still cannot give us an expectation value that is better than the ground state. there are various versions of these sets of theorems, which apply to variances in other quantities that we might want to measure. Thus, one can try to assert, although it is largely done without proof, that this argument will still work reasonably fine on a noisy quantum computer with not so good quantum bits. therefore, companies can deliver to we a product which is a quantum computer with poor quantum bits, and still expect we to pay a lot of money for it because it could run this algorithm and give we some result. There are not many proofs that it will do so, but it is a very compelling argument and a very interesting direction. there are now experimental results showing small one and two-qubit quantum computers doing exactly these steps, the variational quantum eigensolver. So, the challenge of this, there are two, we would point out most. First, does this expectation value converge? we have to rely upon this classical optimization algorithm to get we better and better values. However, we do not have proof that we got the lowest possible value or the desired ground state. Second, this state preparation. It is unclear how this state is prepared. There are some ideas on how to prepare this. For example, with adiabatic quantum computation. we start with a beginning Hamiltonian, which we can create, and try to construct an end Hamiltonian whose ground state is this state that we want to create. since we have this parametrized in principle, we have some means by which we can do that. This parameter, by the way, could be things, for example, like the adiabatic path that we use in the quantum computer. related to this first challenge is how we measure H . And one way people have done this is to measure the terms of H . So, we can say this is equal to the average expectation value of H_1 plus H_2 , plus all the way up to however many terms there are in here. So, we can measure, in principle, the expectation value turn by turn in the Hamiltonian. if the Hamiltonian terms are simple, like Pauli matrices [157], we have a feasible way of doing it.

Unfortunately, that means that we also now added the error from each one of these expectation values. So, the error can grow very rapidly as we are trying to estimate the expectation value this way. Still, the variational quantum eigensolver is different. we have not looked at any kind of algorithm like that in this section. How do we utilize a system with a quantum computer and a classical computer together so that we can get something of the best of both systems? How can we make them work in concert so that one handoff information to the other one so that now we can feedback and try to speed up, while only have a limited amount of quantum coherence and a limited number of qubits at our disposal? we think this is a fascinating topic. we want to leave us with that challenge, and we want to also leave us with the challenge of thinking about how we can relate Hamiltonians and quantum algorithms [158].

Phase estimation determines the eigenenergies of a quantum system up to a specified accuracy. However, stringent requirements on the quantum processor’s performance, such as the available coherence time, limits the current applicability of this method as high accuracy requires long quantum circuits with many gates (high gate depth) [57, 159]. In contrast, quantum optimizers such as the variational quantum eigensolver (VQE) have more relaxed requirements on the quantum processor performance and work with shorter quantum circuits (“shallow depth”) contain parameterized, analog elements [116, 160].

A VQE uses an iterative hybrid approach [161] to calculate the ground-state energy of a problem-specific Hamiltonian by creating a trial wave function on a quantum processor and measuring its energy with respect to the desired Hamiltonian. The trial wave function is made using a quantum circuit based on multi-qubit and single-qubit gates containing tunable parameters and optimized using a classical computer working in tandem with the quantum processor. An optimization loop repeatedly alters between quantum and classical processing until the optimal parameter set has been found, which generates the minimum energy corresponding to the ground state wave function.

As explained in the section, the VQE protocol is initiated with a trial wave function $\Psi(\alpha)$ on a quantum computer. Here, α is the tuning parameter that will successively get optimized to yield the minimum energy. The quantum processor evaluates the expectation value of the trial wave function, $\langle \Psi(\alpha) | H | \Psi(\alpha) \rangle$, where H represents the problem-specific Hamiltonian, and $\langle H \rangle$ correspond to the energy of the prepared wave function with respect to the Hamiltonian. Generally, this requires repeated runs for the same parameter set, not just to obtain enough statistics but also to measure in all the different measurement bases specified in the Hamiltonian (a process often referred to as Hamiltonian averaging). A classical optimizer is then used to minimize the expectation value (energy) by varying the trial wave function through the parameter α . The process repeats until E converges to a steady-state close or equal to the ground state energy E_0 .

Early demonstrations of VQEs using superconducting qubits simulated the ground-state energies for a hydrogen molecule H_2 [162], lithium hydride LiH and beryllium hydride BeH_2 molecule. A demonstration using trapped-ion qubits [163] also used VQE to simulate a hydrogen molecule H_2 and lithium hydride LiH., photonic qubits have been used to find the ground-state energy of a $He - H^+$ molecule [152, 164, 165].

38 Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE)

Let us start with the energy graph of a simple diatomic molecule. When the atoms are close to each other, the repulsion between the individual nuclei dominates the energy of the system and leads to an unstable configuration. At the other extreme is the case when the two atoms

are dissociated. The point of minimum energy is the equilibrium configuration when the bond distance separates the atoms. Evaluating these energies to high accuracy is extremely crucial for accurately predicting chemical reaction rates and pathways and developing insights into molecular structure [152]. The evaluation of these energies essentially comes down to solving the Schrodinger equation, with the following electronic Hamiltonian, which captures the electronic kinetic energies and the Coulomb interaction between pairs of electrons and nuclei, as well as pairs of electrons. However, this eigenvalue problem is one with the exponential cost when addressed by classical computation. This was indeed one of the initial motivations for quantum computers, the idea that one could use a highly controllable programmable quantum processor to efficiently study and predict the properties of quantum systems of interest. The first step of such simulations, then, involves encoding the problem to the quantum processor, in the specific case, mapping the electronic orbitals onto qubits. One then needs an algorithm that solves the eigenvalue problem to evaluate the ground state energy. In this context, hybrid quantum-classical algorithms with short-depth circuits [162], such as the variational quantum eigensolver [33, 116, 165], are well-suited to the capabilities of existing hardware. Here, the trials, or guesses, to the ground state are prepared on the quantum processor, parametrized by some experimental controls θ . The energy of these states is measured and fed to an optimization routine run on a classical computer that updates these parameters to attempt a new trial state. This is now run iteratively until the energy converges towards its minimum value. It raises three important questions for implementing this algorithm. Are there encoding schemes that are efficient towards the number of qubits required? Are there trial states that are efficient towards the number of gates required while faithfully representing the ground state of the molecule? It is important since this can help reduce the effect of decoherence during state preparation. Finally, are classical optimization routines that can effectively deal with a large number of variational parameters and experimental lines? These were all important components of a recent experiment at IBM. Taking advantage of natural symmetries in the molecular Hamiltonian [152], we were able to encode eight orbitals of beryllium hydride onto a reduced number of 6 qubits at no loss of information. Also, we constructed trial states that used layers of untangling gates that are naturally accessible to the experimental hardware, which is then interleaved with arbitrary Euler rotations. The circuit depth or the number of entangling layers is then set based on the available quantum coherence of the hardware. Making efficient use of coherence time and qubit resources, these states are dubbed hardware-efficient trial states. Using such trial states, we were able to perform energy minimizations of up to 6-qubit Hamiltonians. Here is one such example. In the classical optimization routine, 13 Euler angles, which serve as the variation of parameters, are simultaneously updated as the local reading is approximated using solely two energy measurements by iteration, shown here in red and blue. The iterations are stopped once the energy flattens out towards its minimum. Using these techniques, we were able to address different electronic structure problems [166–171] of fairly elementary molecules using 2 qubits for hydrogen, 4 qubits for lithium hydride, and 6 qubits for beryllium hydride. These are problems that are small enough to solve even on a laptop. However, a big motivation for this work is to be able to understand the sources of error and when addresses these problems using the normal paradigm of computing, using real quantum hardware. By comparing the experimental results, shown in these black dots with numerical simulations of the noisy device, we see the decoherence at insufficient circuit depth is some of the important sources of error. So, now this raises the question, in the absence of quantum error correction [172], is there a way to do something meaningful with near-term hardware? Is it possible to obtain estimates for, say, these energies in the absence of incoherent noise, despite using a noisy quantum processor? It turns out there are methods that we call error mitigation [173]. If there is an easy way to amplify the strength of the noise and measure the expectation values of interest, we can then use a powerful numerical technique Richardson extrapolation to obtain a zero-noise estimate.

Here is a case of two wrongs making a right. In contrast to quantum error correction that has a resource requirement that is perhaps beyond near-term hardware, this error mitigation technique is fairly accessible since it does not require any additional quantum resources [72]. Now, is there a way for us to controllably amplify the strength of the noise? For instance, warming up the dilution refrigerator, which houses the superconducting processor [174, 175], certainly increases decoherence. However, there is not a precise way of scaling the noise strength. However, an alternate, more accessible approach involves rescaling the dynamics of the state preparation. It can be shown to be equivalent to amplifying the strength of the noise if the noise is constant over the duration of the rescale measurements. Let us now revisit the molecular simulation of lithium hydride with 4 qubits. The original experiments used just depth-one circuits to reduce the effect of decoherence. More recently, the mitigation of errors from decoherence enables the benefit of longer computations with increased circuit depth, to achieve accuracies that were otherwise believed to be beyond the scope of the noisy superconducting processor. Although discussed with specific examples of quantum chemistry, the variational algorithms [176] and error mitigation techniques discussed here can be extended to a host of different problems that rely on computations with expectation values problems in quantum simulation addressing fundamental particle physics and condensed matter physics, and even problems in optimization and machine learning [177–180]. These techniques will likely be crucial to enhance the quality of quantum computation and simulation in this era of noisy intermediate-scale quantum computers.

Newtonian Mechanics

Figure 13: Newtonian Mechanics

Hamiltonian Mechanics

Kinetic Energy T

$$T = \frac{p^2}{2m}$$

Potential Energy U

$$U(x)$$

Figure 14: Hamiltonian Mechanics

Schrödinger's Equation

$$\frac{d|\psi\rangle}{dt} = -i\hat{H}|\psi\rangle$$

Figure 15: Schrodingers Equation

The Suzuki-Trotter Method (aka Trotterization)

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (e^{-iA \frac{t}{n}} e^{-iB \frac{t}{n}})^n = e^{-i(A+B)t}$$

Trotter Equation

Figure 16: Trotterization

39 Introduction to Quantum Optimization

In this section, we turn our attention to optimization problems and their implementation on a quantum computer. Optimization problems are ubiquitous in industry and government, for example, routing signals in electronics to minimize cross-talk, distributing financial portfolios to maximize profit while minimizing risk, or identifying the most likely nexus within a dense network of telephone calls. Such optimization problems with large numbers of variables and constraints are challenging to implement on classical computers. There are significant research efforts aimed at developing quantum optimization algorithms that may yield quantum enhancement.

There are several approaches to quantum optimization. The first is adiabatic quantum computing and its related [39], restricted cousin, quantum annealing [43, 44]. In this case, a cost function is encoded into a Hamiltonian using a prescribed approach. The quantum device then seeks to minimize the cost function by finding the ground state of this Hamiltonian. A second approach is to use a universal, digital quantum computer to find a solution that satisfies (to the extent possible) a set of boolean clauses. We will discuss this section more about the advantages and challenges of these differing approaches.

We do not always need exact solutions to optimization problems; approximate solutions are often “good enough.” For example, in establishing an optimal route that minimizes the distance one needs to travel between several cities separated by 100’s of kilometers, one probably would not distinguish between several high-quality solutions that differ by only a few meters or even a few hundred meters. Thus, there is intense interest in identifying quantum approximate optimization algorithms (QAOA) [40, 41] that feature quantum advantage in providing high-quality solutions, without necessarily obtaining the optimal answer. Such algorithms may be realizable on nearer-term, smaller-scale quantum computers, whether acting alone or as the co-processor working in tandem with a classical computer.

Next, we discuss that the output of quantum computer was one value with a higher probability, and the question is can a simulation algorithm result in a distribution of probabilities? and

the answer is yes it can. if there really is only one value, then that value has probability one. because we always normalize the probability to one. so, if any given answer is not obtained with unity probability. it means is that there are other answers floating around with lower probability. such that when we add up all the possible answers then the probabilities of all those answers is that we get one. So, in quantum simulations it could be depending on what we are simulating that we would get a distribution of many different answers with different weightings. the problem with that is we have to at any given instance or run the algorithm we are going to make a measurement projectively and get one of those answers out. so to estimate the probability of each one and sampling all different answers. we have to, identically prepare and repeat the algorithm many times. and if this solution space is exponentially large then that is going to take an exponentially long time. So that is not really the right way to ask a quantum computer a question. Rather, the simulations, or the optimizations, need to ask the questions in such a way that the solution space is not exponentially large, but reduced to either one answer, with high probability, or a set of answers, that all of which are high quality, so that it does not really matter which one we get. so, the example that we have given, we think, before, is that if we are trying to optimize, which route to take home from work, and it is 10 miles away, there may be a whole set of answers that are accurate enough that we do not care which one it is. Let us say that there are a hundred different ways we could get home, and they differ by 100 meters? and it is 10 kilometers to get from home, we know, from work to home. we do not care? it is only 100 meters difference. What matters is not off by a kilometer. So, in these types of cases, optimization problems, for example, there need not be, there may be one truly optimal answer, but in all likelihood, there may be many answers which are equally good from a practical sense. so as long as the algorithm is set up to find those answers, or that set of answers, samples any one with high probability, then it is fine. we can run the algorithm a few times, not an exponentially large number of times, if we can ask it a few times, and we start to sample some of these potential good solutions, and eventually, we gain some confidential cases, it is probably a good solution.

40 Adiabatic Quantum Computing

Optimization problems are ubiquitous in business, government, and our daily lives. They also tend to be hard problems to solve, because of the large number of variables and connectivity within the problem. In this section, we will discuss adiabatic quantum computing, one approach to addressing optimization problems. We will also discuss how adiabatic quantum computers are different from gate-model quantum computers.

In the last section, we discussed several topics related to quantum Hamiltonian simulation, including methods like Trotterization [31], phase estimation, and variational quantum eigensolvers. In this section, we will turn the attention to quantum optimization algorithms. Optimization problems are ubiquitous, from supply transport optimization to sensor and satellite tasking, pattern recognition. Many important practical problems can be reduced to satisfy, in an optimal manner, as many constraints as possible. we will first discuss optimization problems and their implementation on an adiabatic quantum computer. we will then turn the attention to quantum annealers, machines that target classical optimization problems. lastly, we will look at Grover's algorithm and how it works. at the end of the section, we will implement Grover's algorithm on the IBM Quantum Experience [181]. To get started, let us first study adiabatic quantum computers and quantum optimization algorithms. Adiabatic quantum computing is an all-purpose approach to solving combinatorial optimization problems [182], or generally for finding the minimum of an objective function, using a quantum computer. we know that all systems in nature obey the Schrodinger equation. It is a first-order differential equation, which

says that the wave function's rate of change is proportional to the Hamiltonian operator times the wave function. So, adiabatic quantum computing uses the Schrodinger equation as the basis of the algorithm. It is distinct from the gate model in that sense because we are going to have continuous-time evolution. The quantum state is going to change continuously, as opposed to the gate model, where sequences of discrete transformations update the state. They are very closely related. However, in this case, we think it is a lot easier to think about how the algorithm works if we think in the context of the continuous-time evolution. Let us try to give us a feel for how the adiabatic algorithm works. we want to find the minimum of a complicated cost function. in general, there is no all-purpose algorithm that will guarantee to find the minimum of any cost function in all circumstances. We are trying to find something which we hope will work well in practice in situations we care about. So, the idea is this. We are going to attempt to find the minimum cost function by encoding the cost function in a quantum Hamiltonian. we are going to take a quantum Hamiltonian, whose ground state that is its lowest energy state we know, and we are going to prepare the quantum system in the ground state of this known Hamiltonian. Sometimes we call that the beginning Hamiltonian. If we look at this equation here, we see that the Hamiltonian that controls the evolution of the system has two parts, the beginning Hamiltonian and the problem Hamiltonian. Now, we are going to start the system off in the ground state of the beginning Hamiltonian, because the beginning Hamiltonian is something we know how to construct, and we know its ground state. then what we are going to do is slowly turn off the beginning Hamiltonian and slowly turn on the problem Hamiltonian. So, we are going to go from one to the other slowly. However, the problem Hamiltonian has been constructed so that its ground state encodes the solution to the minimization problem, which is the goal. we are going to take the system, and we are going to slowly change the Hamiltonian as the state evolves, according to the Schrodinger equation, the first equation we showed us. Let us give us a little example of how this might work. Suppose that we put a little ball in hand. it is just sitting there. Imagine it in our mind's eye. it is sitting in it is in the minimum of a potential well formed by hand. Now we slowly move the hand. the little ball, as we can see in our mind's eye, stays right there in hand. What is happened in that case is that we are changing the physical system, and we are dragging along the minimum energy configuration. Now, suppose that we put that little ball there, and we jerked hand. The ball would fall away. So, if we let the hand go slowly enough, we will drag along the little ball. the quantum system works in a very similar fashion. If we put a quantum state in Hamiltonian's ground state, then we slowly change the Hamiltonian. If we go slowly enough, the Hamiltonian ground state will correspond to the evolving quantum state. In other words, we can shlep the ground state from the ground state of the beginning Hamiltonian to the ground state of the problem Hamiltonian, if we go slowly enough. that means that we have a way of finding the ground state, which corresponds to the minimum energy configuration, or the lowest value or the cost function that we sought. It will work, for sure, if we go infinitely slowly. Now, infinitely slowly requires an infinite amount of time. Thus, that is not a practical algorithm. So, the real question becomes, can we go slowly enough but not so, slowly that it is impractical, that we can bring the system to the place we want?

Adiabatic quantum computing (AQC) is a quantum computing model that casts the problem of finding the solution of a computational problem into the problem of obtaining the lowest energy eigenstate of a specified Hamiltonian. Edward Farhi theoretically proposed it, Jeffrey Goldstone, Sam Gutmann, and Michael Sipser in 2000 [38, 183], as a general computational model, and it was later shown to be polynomially equivalent to universal, circuit-model quantum computation by Dorit Aharonov and colleagues in 2004 [39].

The physical principle governing AQC is the adiabatic theorem. Essentially, this theorem

states that a physical system will remain in its lowest-energy eigenstate under sufficiently slow changes to the parameters of its Hamiltonian. This fact can be put to computational use by initializing a computer in the ground state of a known Hamiltonian, called the “initial Hamiltonian”, and then adiabatically evolving its parameters into the “problem Hamiltonian” with a ground state that encodes the solution to the computational problem. The slow evolution of the system is intended to guarantee that the system remains in the ground-state throughout this process. However, as indicated below, this is generally not achievable for problems of practical size due to the “minimum gap” problem.

An adiabatic quantum algorithm [38] for a given computational problem is comprised of choice for the initial Hamiltonian, the evolution path, and Hamiltonian. None of these choices are unique (except, possibly, the problem Hamiltonian). The initial Hamiltonian is generally chosen to have a known ground state, and simple implementation, e.g., all spins aligned along the X-axis of the Bloch sphere (state $|+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0\rangle + |1\rangle)$) due to an interaction with a large control field. The problem of interest is then embedded onto the hardware to create the problem Hamiltonian, within the constraints imposed by the available qubits and their interactions. Lastly, an evolution path from the initial Hamiltonian to the Hamiltonian’s target is chosen, and ideally, this choice respects the conditions imposed by the adiabatic theorem. Using this approach, small-scale adiabatic quantum algorithms for search, factorization, and optimization have been experimentally demonstrated with nuclear spins and magnetic resonance, superconducting qubits, and photonic qubits [116].

The choice of initial Hamiltonian, evolution path, and problem Hamiltonian together determine how rapidly the system can be evolved and, thus, determine the runtime complexity of the adiabatic algorithm. In principle, the shorter the runtime, the more efficient the algorithm. However, running the algorithm faster than is allowed by the adiabatic theorem decreases the chances of obtaining a correct solution at the end of the evolution process.

In fact, for larger problems of practical significance, adiabatic quantum algorithms generally cannot be implemented without the system leaving the ground state. It is because of the “minimum gap” problem. As the system evolves from initial to problem Hamiltonian, the energy levels eventually come close and form an avoided crossing, i.e., come close but do not quite touch. One can intuitively think of this as a “crossing point” where the system leaves its initial-Hamiltonian-like nature behind and starts adopting problem-Hamiltonian-like characteristics. In physics jargon, this is essentially a phase transition [164].

The problem is that the gap becomes smaller and smaller as the problem size increases. This results in two key issues. First of all, even in the absence of noise, the system must evolve more slowly through the gap region as the gap gets smaller in order to maintain adiabaticity. If the system evolves too quickly, the system will effectively “jump” to the excited state via a nonadiabatic process called a Landau-Zener transition. Avoiding Landau-Zener transitions requires longer evolution times, thus increasing the time-to-solution and slowing the computation.

Second, and more insidious is that there is always some level of noise. As the gap size decreases, noise from the thermal environment and noise from the control fields implementing the evolution will drive transitions from the ground state to the excited state. For example, once the gap energy becomes smaller than the thermal energy $k_B T$ at temperature T , the environment will drive transitions. Thus, for large enough problems, it will be practically prohibitive to evolve the system while remaining in the ground state.

Given that an adiabatic quantum computer will leave the ground state at some point during its evolution (for a sufficiently large problem), one may wonder if that destroys any potential for quantum enhancement. After all, what if the computer could return to the ground state after

passing through the minimum gap region?

In 1998, Tadashi Kadowaki and Hidetoshi Nishimori proposed such a quantum annealer to solve classical optimization problems. A quantum annealer leverages quantum tunneling [50] and dissipation (relaxation processes) to return a system to its ground state (or a lower-energy state) after passing a small avoided crossing. While such quantum annealers seemingly bypass many of the constraints imposed by an adiabatic quantum computer, there is no evidence that quantum annealing computers feature quantum enhancement to date [45–49].

41 Adiabatic QC

How do adiabatic algorithms solve optimization problems? In this section, we will discuss the adiabatic algorithm [183], how it is used to minimize “cost functions,” and how it is implemented using spin Hamiltonians.

Let us go back to the concept of adiabatic evolution, but let us be a little bit more specific now. So, we want to imagine that we want to find the minimum of a cost function, which is defined over bit strings. that cost function is the sum of terms, each of which depends on a subset of the bits and has a value of 1. Let us say, on certain assignments of those bits in the subset, and has the value 0 on other assignments. For example, if an individual term might look at 2 bits and it will say, if the 2 bits agree in their value, we are going to give it the value 1, but if they disagree, the function has the value of 0. So, now, we want to imagine that the optimization problem is to find the minimum of a function, which is a sum of terms, each of which acts on a few bits. finding the minimum of such a function, in general, is what we call NP-hard. It is not believed that there is any kind of classical time algorithm that can, in polynomial time, solve that problem in general. Nonetheless, we are going to attempt the quantum approach to it. So, the first thing we are going to do is to find what we told us before was the problem Hamiltonian. the problem Hamiltonian we are going to take to be diagonal in the computational basis, so, when the problem Hamiltonian acts on a ket with the string z in it, it will give the value of the cost function times the cat. So, it is diagonal in the computational basis. Note that the minimum string that achieves the minimum value of the cost function can be viewed as the ground state of this particular quantum Hamiltonian because it is diagonal on a computational basis. Now, we need to take a beginning Hamiltonian too. from that, we typically use a magnetic field in the x -direction. If we have a magnetic field on a single spin a half particle and it is pointing in the x -direction, it is represented by the operator. we will take it to be minus σ_x so that the state in the x -direction is the minimum with the value minus 1. So, the Hamiltonian we are going to take for the beginning Hamiltonian is the sum, a minus in front, the sum of the σ_x is one for each qubit. That is a very simple Hamiltonian. it is very easy to initialize a quantum state as the ground state of that Hamiltonian because all we have to do is take the spins and line them up in the x -direction. Then we are automatically in the ground state of the beginning Hamiltonian. So, now for all full evolution, we are going to take a Hamiltonian that it interpolates between the beginning Hamiltonian we prescribed and the problem Hamiltonian. So, that is all very simple to write down. Not only is it simple to write down, but it is also easy to imagine implementing such a thing in the lab or on a quantum computer because the terms in the problem Hamiltonian are a sum of local terms diagonal in the computational basis. the beginning Hamiltonian is just a magnetic field in the x -direction. So, we can imagine building this thing. what the D Wave company did is build a machine that runs this algorithm. They chose to implement the quantum adiabatic algorithm because it was simple to imagine building a device that could do that. the way we have discussed it, it is kind of an all-purpose minimizer. So, we now have gone as far as

to see that we can have a specific implementation of the adiabatic algorithm. So, What is the killer here? What slows it down? What is the thing that makes it hard to implement this in reality and means that it is hard to show the algorithm works all the time? Furthermore, that has to do with how slowly we have to go to guarantee that we are going to go to the place we want to end up at. that slowness is determined by something we call the minimum gap. At the beginning of Hamiltonian, we have a magnetic field in the x-direction. If we flip a single spin, the energy of that single spin goes from Let us say minus 1 to plus 1. So, the energy difference is 2. That is a big energy difference between the ground state and the first excited state. In the problem Hamiltonian, we told we that all terms were zeros and ones, because the cost function, the way we happened to define it, was a sum of terms, which were all 0 or 1. So, that means that the energy difference between the ground state and the first excited state is Let us say, 1 or 2, but it is going to be an integer. However, as the system evolves, we can track the ground state energy and the energy of the first excited state. we find in these situations that as we move along, the two approach each other, coming very, very close. then they are going to spread out back to that integer at the end. the question is, What is that value, the smallest energy difference between the first excited state and the ground state? we call that the gap. the runtime of the algorithm is determined by the gap. The minimum runtime of the algorithm scales like 1 over the minimum gap squared. That is just a little math fact, which we could establish. The whole issue from a physics point of view in the adiabatic algorithm is, does the system, as it evolves, make the energy difference between the ground state and the first excited state get too small? Because if it is too small, the run time required to stay in the ground state is too big. So, one of the things we have to study when we think about adiabatic algorithms is the gap between the first excited state and the ground state as the system evolves.

42 Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm

In this section, we continues discussion of optimization algorithms [183]. Here, we will discuss combinatorial search problems and the quantum approximate optimization algorithm (QAOA) [40, 184].

we have already established what we think throughout this section, and most of us know that optimization is a key problem in all of computer science. Now, let us get a little more specific and think about what optimization means in combinatorial search. There we have a problem defined on bit strings. we have clauses or constraints, which look at subsets of the bits. for certain assignments of the bits, those clauses are satisfied. for others, they are not. What we want to do in combinatorial optimization, is find a string that can satisfy as many clauses as possible. Often we cannot satisfy all the clauses. Because the clauses have intrinsic contradictions, so that assignments for one clause that satisfy it, force other clauses not to be satisfied. The question then becomes, what is the string that satisfies, Let us say, as most clauses as possible? Now that is very ambitious. Because satisfying the most clauses as possible, that is NP-hard. if we could do that in general, we would have a huge computer science breakthrough. Most people believe that there could be no polynomial-time algorithm for that. So, instead, we are going to come back a little bit and look for a string that satisfies many of the clauses, or as many as the algorithm can produce. So, what we are looking for is a good solution, not the best solution. we are looking for a good string, not the best. In that case, if our good solution is very, very close to the best, it is as good as the best; but if it is a little off, it could still be of great value to us. Thus, what we are going to be discussing is an algorithm that is an approximate optimizer. It is looking for approximate solutions in the sense we just said. we are going to try this with a quantum algorithm. However, the quantum algorithm is now not like in the adiabatic, and it is

going to be based on a continuous-time evolution. However, rather it is going to be in the gate model, which means we are going to apply a sequence of discrete unitary transformations to an initial state, and then make a measurement, and hope that that measurement gives a string that satisfies a high fraction of the clauses that could be satisfied. So, in order to build this up, we need a few ingredients. we need the initial state and the unitaries that we are going to apply. So, let us think about that. well, for the initial state, what we are going to take is all the spins lined up in the x-direction. the reason we like that is we probably already know that if our spin is in the x-direction, it is a uniform superposition of up and down in the z. In other words, it is an equal combination of 0 and 1. So, if all our spins are lined up in the x-direction, our state is a uniform superposition of all possible bit strings. that is kind of a good place to start. Because we have everything in there when we begin, in the computation basis. Now we are going to apply two operators. The first operator is going to depend on the actual operator-valued cost function. The cost function acting on a string gives us the number of clauses satisfied by the total that string. That is an easy-to-compute function. However, we could promote that function to a quantum operator, and that quantum operator acting on the ket labeled by the bit string z will be the function, which is the number of satisfied clauses times the ket. So, this operator-valued cost function is diagonal in the computational basis, and it is easy to construct. However, it is a Hermitian operator. we would like to apply a unitary transformation that depends on it. So, we are going to introduce a parameter, γ . we are going to write down the unitary here, e to the minus $i \gamma$ times that cost function. So, this object is a unitary transformation, which we can easily apply to any state. it depends on a parameter, γ , which we will discuss more later. Now the next operator, which we would like to apply again, there is much room for choice. However, we make a choice that will depend on the operator, which we call B , which is the sum of the σ_x 's, the sum of the Pauli operators in the x-direction. That is an operator, which we discuss in the adiabatic case, we call the beginning Hamiltonian. This operator B , which is the sum of the σ_x 's, is easy to construct. However, now what we want to do, though, is make a unitary operator, which depends on that. we are going to do that by writing e to the minus $i \beta$, which is the parameter we have just introduced, times the operator B . So, this operator, if we look at it, e to the minus $i \beta B$, since each term in B is a σ_x , what it is doing is rotating the spins around the x-direction by an angle, β . So, now we have the two building block unitary operators, each of which depends on one parameter. So, the algorithm consists of the following. Start with the initial state, which we already described. Choose γ . Apply the unitary e to the minus $i \gamma C$ to that state. Then choose the β . Apply either the minus $i \beta B$ to the state, and now measure in the computational basis. we get out a string. now, What is interesting is that we can show that for certain problems, we can find values of γ and β such that the string that is produced will satisfy a high fraction of the clauses. we are not going to show we now how we find the γ and β to do that. However, that can be done for certain problems. in fact, for one problem, called MAX-CUT, when we first introduced this algorithm in 2014, we were able to show that we could achieve a restricted version of MAX-CUT [185]. This certain approximation ratio was better than we would get if we just picked a string at random. Now we could say, so, what? we did a little better than random guessing. However, we managed to show that this worked in every case, no matter how big the instance was, no matter how many bits or qubits were involved. With the right choice of γ and β , we were guaranteed to get a good answer. So, in this case, we were able to show that the quantum computer would perform at a certain level, even on instances that we had not yet seen. The factoring algorithm has that great virtue. we know that if we had a functioning quantum computer, no matter what integer we give, it will be able to find its factors. Thus, we were able to show that we could get an approximation ratio that beat random guessing, no matter what we gave it. Nevertheless, we were not beating the best classical algorithm. then we looked at another problem called E3LIN2. We could be much

more specific. However, for now, just go with the story. we looked at this problem, E3LIN2. We showed that with just this shallow depth circuit, we could achieve an approximation ratio, which is 2014 beat the best classical algorithm for this problem. Now at that moment, We had a quantum algorithm that beat the best classical algorithm for a certain task in all cases. The word of this spread. The way it spread was basically because Scott Aaronson blogged about it and said there was this neat new quantum algorithm, which got the classical computer scientists and the non-quantum people together. 10 of them ganged upon, and they devised a classical algorithm that beat the quantum algorithm for this task. Nevertheless, what was interesting there is we got a competition going between the classical and the quantum. at this moment, in terms of provable worst-case performance guarantees, the classical algorithm is outperforming the QAOA. The QAOA is the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm. Now we can go further with the QAOA than we have already outlined. Because of the way we have outlined it, it is a very simple algorithm with just two unitaries. we apply the first one, then the next one, then we measure. Nevertheless, we can go further. we can apply the first one and then the second one. Then we can apply the first one again with a different parameter. then, we can apply the β dependent operator with a different parameter. Then if we keep going, by alternations of those two operators, it turns out that we can only improve the performance of the algorithm. Now we have had trouble from a technical point of view showing how much that improvement consists of. It has been too hard for us to analyze it beyond the very shallowest depth circuits that we did. However, we optimistic that when we run a near term quantum computer, if we apply this algorithm which should be fairly simple to do because it is a shallow depth gate model with simple-to-construct operators; that we might discover that there are parameter choices for which the solutions we get are quite good, even as good as what we get from classical algorithms, even better. So, we think that applying the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm to near-term quantum devices is a definite avenue for this community to go down. we look forward to seeing the algorithm run on any platform capable of running it.

A combinatorial optimization algorithm finds solutions to a problem subject to a set of constraints, and the optimal solution is the one that satisfies the largest number of constraints.

The problem is defined by an object function $C(b)$, which is a sum of m constraint clauses C_α , where $\alpha = 1 \dots m$. Each clause is a Boolean function that captures one specific constraint of the optimization problem. The Boolean functions are constructed from n Boolean variables $b_1 \dots b_n$, which together form an n -bit string b , and there are 2^n such strings. Note that not all Boolean variables need to be used in every clause, and in general, they are not. If a given b satisfies a clause, then $C_\alpha(b) = 1$ according to the Boolean function it represents; otherwise, $C_\alpha(b) = 0$.

The $b = b_{\text{opt}}$ that maximizes the object function $C(b)$,

$$C(b_{\text{opt}}) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^m C_\alpha(b_{\text{opt}}) \geq \sum_{\alpha=1}^m C_\alpha(b \neq b_{\text{opt}}) \quad (111)$$

Is the optimal solution (or, an optimal solution if more than one solution exists). If all clauses are satisfied, $C(b_{\text{opt}}) = m$, but this is not required.

In general, evaluating the optimal solution is a hard problem. An approximate solution that is not necessarily optimal but is still of reasonably high quality is sufficient for many optimization problems and maybe computed more efficiently. The quantum approximate optimization algorithm (QAOA) is proposed to find approximate solutions to a combinatorial optimization problem.

QAOA is a hybrid approach that utilizes a digital quantum computer (QC) to evaluate the object function and a classical optimizer (CO) to update trial solutions to optimize the object function. The iterative process on n qubits approximated with p optimization steps can be summarized as follows:

1. CO: generate initial set of angles γ_1 and β_1 to optimize the object function
2. QC: create superposition of n qubits in computational basis ground-state
3. QC: rotate qubits on Bloch sphere by angles γ_1 (z-axis) and β_1 (x-axis)
4. QC: measure qubits in computational basis and evaluate the object function
5. CO: generate new set of angles γ_2 and β_2 to optimize the object function
6. QC: create superposition of n qubits in computational basis ground-state
7. QC: rotate qubits on Bloch sphere by angles γ_1, γ_2 and β_1, β_2
8. QC: measure qubits in computational basis and evaluate the object function
- \vdots
- $4p - 3$.CO: generate new set of angles γ_p and β_p to optimize the object function
- $4p - 2$.QC: create superposition of n qubits in computational basis ground-state
- $4p - 1$.QC: rotate qubits on Bloch sphere by angles $\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_p$ and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p$

The algorithm is composed of two types of operators constructed with unitary quantum gates to rotate the qubits by angles γ and β .

$$C(b) = \sum_{\alpha=1}^m C_{\alpha}(b) \rightarrow U(C, \gamma) = e^{-i\gamma C} = \prod_{\alpha=1}^m e^{-i\gamma C_{\alpha}} \quad (112)$$

$$B = \sum_{j=1}^n X_j \rightarrow U(B, \beta) = e^{-i\beta B} = \prod_{j=1}^n e^{-i\beta X_j} \quad (113)$$

The operator C is based on the object function $C(b)$, and it conditionally rotates qubits by an angle γ . For example, a clause $C_{\alpha} = \frac{1}{2}(-Z_j Z_k + 1)$ rotates qubits j and k by an angle γ around the z-axis if they are in opposite states. Therefore, only qubits complying with the clauses of the objective function are affected by the rotation.

The second operator, B , applies a rotation of angle β around the x-axis to all qubits. Note that states co-aligned with the x-axis remain unchanged for an X-rotation.

An initial state $|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^n}} \sum_{s=1}^{2^n} |s\rangle$ is iteratively rotated conditionally around the z-axis, and then around the x-axis, to reach a particular location on the two-dimensional Bloch sphere. The measured resulting state after p optimization steps is:

$$|\vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta}\rangle = U(B, \beta_p)U(C, \gamma_p) \cdots U(B, \beta_1)U(C, \gamma_1)|s\rangle \quad (114)$$

It can be shown that the expectation value of the object function improves with additional iterations and ultimately maximizes it. The performance of the underlying quantum processor usually determines the approximation accuracy.

$$\max_{\vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta}} \langle \vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta} | C | \vec{\gamma}, \vec{\beta} \rangle = M_p \geq M_{p-1} \Rightarrow \lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} M_p = \max_z C(b) \quad (115)$$

The algorithm's key element is the ability to conditionally project qubits on arbitrary locations on the Bloch sphere via iterative rotations induced by two distinct unitary operators. Each

iterative step starts with a new set of classically optimized angles based on the qubit measurement of the prior step. A sufficient number of repetitions approximates the object function $C(b)$, and the measured qubit state reflects the approximately optimal bit string b .

There was a question about quantum algorithms, Is it always possible to transform any classical equation or algorithm into a quantum equivalent, or vice-versa, a quantum equation into a graphical tool, or back into a classical equivalent, The answer is yes, if we have a universal, fault-tolerant quantum computer, it is universal, and in principle, it can perform any algorithm, quantum or classical. Now, the key here though is that, the quantum computer may do no better than a classical computer, and oftentimes, it may do far worse, because it runs at a much slower rate, it does not have quantum advantage for that particular type of problem. so, although in principle it can do it, it may not be any better than a classical computer, and in fact, may be slower. Now similarly, we can take a quantum equation, or quantum algorithm, and we can simulate that, or implement that, on a classical computer, but to do that, we need to discretize the problem. We often need to make some assumptions, truncate the problem, reduce it down in some way so that it is tractable to implement on a classical computer and in doing that, we lose information, we lose fidelity. that is why it is generally hard to implement quantum algorithms, or quantum systems, to simulate quantum systems on a classical computer. Now, we could do it in full glory, but then that takes the age of the universe? it is this type of problem if we want to do it and simulate it, with the highest possible fidelities on a classical computer, it is going to take way too long, or it takes way too much memory to implement or to be practicable. If we cut down the problem so that we can do it on our classical computers, then we do not get accurate answers? And so, this motivates why we need to have a quantum computer. Now, is it always possible to transform quantum equations into its equivalent in a graphical tool set, like we have experienced with the IBMQ Quantum Experience. In principle, yes, but, a graphical user interface is an abstraction, so it is a convenience that we build in to, our human-computer interfaces, it is a tool. So, the graphical interface is limited to the extent that some of these programs has capability into it. so, perhaps there are gate operations that are not represented yet in their full generality in that graphical user interface. So it is in principle possible, but this is one reason why we do programming, using programming languages, rather than using a GUI interface, is because we can do operations with more generality when we do a lower level of programming rather than a higher level of graphical user interface. But as an in-principle, sure, there is nothing that prevents us from implementing everything that we would possibly calculate or program into a graphical user interface. It just may become bulky, and it needs to be designed very well, so that human-computer interface is still efficient with all that information.

43 Quantum Annealing: Concept

How are quantum annealers different from adiabatic quantum computers? Furthermore, how are they used to solve optimization problems? In this section, we will discuss quantum annealers.

In the previous section, we discussed a paradigm of quantum computing known as adiabatic quantum computation. In this section, we are going to introduce another related quantum computing paradigm called quantum annealing. As we will see, quantum annealing bears many similarities to adiabatic quantum computation, though with a few key differences. First, recall that adiabatic quantum computation is a form of analog quantum computing. That is, rather than digitizing the computation into discrete gates, AQC relies on the continuous transition of a quantum system from the ground state of one Hamiltonian to the ground state of another. While it is true that adiabatic quantum computation is a provably viable method of universal quantum

computation [186,187], ACQ presents a serious practical challenge. In order for the computation to succeed, the system must remain in the ground state for the duration of the computation. If the evolution is not truly adiabatic, and the system ends up in an excited state at the end of the protocol, the computation fails. Unfortunately, this is an extremely hard condition to avoid in any realistic quantum computer. To see this, let us consider what the system's energy levels might look like as we perform the computation. In particular, let us focus on the energy gap between the ground state of the system and its first excited state. As the Hamiltonian of the system changes throughout the computation, the gap between the ground and excited states also changes, and in general, it can become very small. It is where the trouble starts. For any physical system at finite temperature, the environment around the qubits generates thermal photons with an energy proportional to the environment's temperature. When these photons encounter the qubits, their energy is absorbed, and the system has some probability of being excited to a higher state. The smaller the gap with respect to the photon energy, the higher the probability that excitation will occur. If we want to reduce the probability of an excitation occurring for a fixed gap size, we need to cool the system to a temperature much lower than the energy gap between the qubit states. It is precisely why we operate superconducting qubits in a dilution refrigerator cooled to a temperature of around 10 millikelvins. For typical superconducting qubits, the gap between the bare qubits' states is on the order of 5 gigahertz, which corresponds to a temperature of around 250 millikelvins. By operating the qubits in an environment order of magnitude colder, we dramatically reduce the probability of an unintentional excitation occurring during the computation. Unfortunately, as we change the Hamiltonian during an adiabatic quantum computation, new avoided crossings will open up between the states, which can be much smaller than the energy gaps between the bare qubit states. If we want to avoid transitioning across these small gaps in the case, say, of a superconducting annealer, we would need to engineer a refrigerator that operates much colder than 10 millikelvin, which is not practical given current cryogenic technology [188]. This type of problem generalizes other qubit technologies as well. There is a second problem. As we evolve the computer through a small gap region, if we sweep through the gap too quickly, we can effectively jump to the excited state. It is called a Landau-Zener transition. So, even if we could operate the computer at zero temperature, we would need to evolve the system sufficiently slowly to accommodate smaller and smaller gaps and thereby increase the time to solution. So, although adiabatic quantum computation can, in principle, be universal, it has major drawbacks related to the small gap sizes that occur at larger problem sizes. Given this reality, it is natural to ask, what happens if we allow the computer to leave the ground state during the evolution. Can it return to the ground states, or even a lower excited state, through quantum tunneling and relaxation processes? Furthermore, more importantly, is leaving the ground state consistent with the quantum-enhanced operation? Quantum annealing is an adiabatic quantum computer that has left its ground state at some point during the evolution. Conceptually, a combination of quantum tunneling and relaxation processes are leveraged to allow the computer to return to its ground state, or at the very least, a lower energy state. However, to date, there was no proof or evidence that the quantum and dissipative dynamics in quantum annealing could then forward a quantum enhancement for a general class of problems. It remains an open research question. Much like AQC, the principle of quantum annealing involves evolving a quantum state according to some time-dependent Hamiltonian such that the state of the system at the end of the computation encodes the result of the problem of interest. However, unlike ACQ, which is universal and can, in principle, implement any quantum algorithm, quantum annealing is designed only to solve a particular class of computations known as classical optimization problems. We deal with classical optimization problems in every industry and throughout the daily lives. For example, What is the best portfolio of stocks to maximize return on investment? What is the best fighter jet designed to minimize drag? Or to use a more mundane example,

What is the best path home from work? The key to an optimization problem is that there are many potentially viable answers to a given problem. For example, many paths will take us home from our office. The goal of an optimization problem is to find the most efficient solution from amongst all the possible solutions. We quantify this by introducing a cost function, which tells us the relative efficiency of a solution. For the commute home, the cost function could be the time it takes to get home if we followed a particular route. Alternatively, it could be the amount of gas we use. Whatever we are optimizing against, the optimal solution tells us the one that minimizes the cost function. Although there may be a truly optimal solution, it is very often the case that there are several nearly optimal solutions that are all, in practice, very good. Commutes that differ by a few meters on 10 kilometers or differ by a few drops of gas on a liter are essentially interchangeable. The hope for these kinds of problems is that leaving the ground state may be fine if we end up in a reasonably low energy state. To map an optimization problem onto a quantum annealing problem, we make use of a particular Hamiltonian known as an Ising Hamiltonian. The Ising Hamiltonian was first formulated in the context of quantum magnetism between atomic spins. For a system of physical spin $1/2$ particles, the Ising Hamiltonian tells us the energy of the spins as they interact with external magnetic fields plus the energy of the magnetic interactions between pairs of spins. So, how can this physics problem be used for optimization? As it turns out, we can use the Ising Hamiltonian to encode so-called classical optimization problems [189]. By choosing the right combination of interaction strings between spins, we can mimic the cost function of the problem we are interested in. When we encode this optimization problem into the Ising Hamiltonian, we then find that the Hamiltonian's energy levels corresponding to the possible solutions to the optimization problem with the energy at each level corresponding to the value of the cost function for that particular solution. Higher energies incur higher penalties. The goal of quantum annealing is to engineer a qubit system with an Ising Hamiltonian corresponding to the optimization problem of interest [190]. We then want to evolve the system such that it ends up in a low-energy eigenstate of this Hamiltonian at the end of the computation. The lower the energy of this final stage, the more optimal the solution. To perform this evolution, we start by initializing the system in the ground state of a much simpler Hamiltonian. Conventionally, this Hamiltonian is the sum of the x operator acting on every qubit, which is analogous to having an array of spin $1/2$ particles in a global magnetic field pointing transversely to the spins. When we work out the math, we find that the ground state of this Hamiltonian is straightforward. It is the state where all the qubits are in the plus x state on the equator of the Bloch sphere, which is a relatively easy state to initialize the system in. Once we prepare the system in the ground state of this initial Hamiltonian, we gradually reduce the strength of this initial Hamiltonian and turn on the Hamiltonian, which encodes the optimization problem. In the ideal case, the system evolves adiabatically and remains in the ground state throughout the evolution. It would be an adiabatic quantum computer simulating an Ising Hamiltonian. Ideally, at the end of the evolution, the system would still be in the ground state of the problem Hamiltonian corresponding to the solution, which minimizes the cost function. In other words, we would find the absolute shortest route home. However, as discussed at the beginning of this section, it is very unlikely that we will remain in the ground state throughout the computation. It does not necessarily ruin the computation. Because every energy state of the problem Hamiltonian corresponds to a possible solution, even if we exit the ground state and end up in an excited state at the end of the computation, this excited state may still give us a useful answer to the optimization problem. The question is, how good is this answer. Unfortunately, while quantum annealing relaxes the constraint that we stay in the ground state, it makes no guarantees that the result we arrive at is any more optimal, or any more efficiently found, than the result we might calculate on a classical computer. As such, unlike AQC, quantum annealing can make no provable claim to either universality or a quantum

enhancement, and there is no demonstration to date of quantum enhancement for a class of optimization problems. That said, even if a quantum annealer ends upscaling with problem size like the classical computer, it may still be useful if it offers a significant advantage over existing classical computing alternatives. However, this also has yet to be demonstrated. Nonetheless, there is tremendous interest in quantum annealers because optimization problems are ubiquitous. While large-scale universal quantum computers are still a long way from commercial reality, the first generation of commercial quantum annealers designed by D-Wave currently boasts up to 2,000 qubits [75, 191]. While the D-Wave system has yet to demonstrate quantum enhancement for a general class of optimization problems [192], these machines, as currently constructed, only explore a small part of the quantum annealing design space [193]. As work gets underway to design the next generation of quantum annealers, it remains an open question if systems with higher quantum coherence and more sophisticated qubit connectivity might demonstrate a truly conclusive quantum enhancement.

Quantum annealing (QA) is a method for finding solutions to classical optimization problems. It is essentially an adiabatic quantum computer that is allowed to leave its ground state during its evolution. Then, through a combination of quantum tunneling and relaxation, the system finds its way back to the ground state (or a lower-energy state), which encodes an (approximate) solution to the optimization problem.

Quantum annealing borrows its name from thermal annealing. For example, in metallurgy, annealing is a process by which a metal is heated such that its physical shape and composition can be modified. Then, upon cooling, the metal relaxes into this new shape and composition, from which it will not change unless heated. Loosely speaking, the thermal fluctuations present during the heating process enable the metal to reconfigure into an alternate, advantageous configuration.

To gain insight, it is instructive to consider a classical algorithm called simulated annealing (SA) [194], which uses a thermal activation model to find approximate solutions to optimization problems. Intuitively, SA algorithms seek to replicate thermodynamics, where the cost function is encoded into the total energy of the system. The algorithm seeks to find a low-energy configuration as a parameter analogous to temperature T “reduced” to zero. Operationally, each iteration of an SA algorithm begins with a valid solution with energy E and randomly selects another solution near the current one. The new solution can either have a higher ($E' > E$) or lower ($E' < E$) energy, where E' is the energy of the newly selected solution. In one of the most basic implementations of SA, if ($E' < E$), then the new solution is chosen as the starting point for the next iteration. However, a key feature of SA is that even when $E' > E$, although representing a less optimal solution, there is a non-zero probability that the algorithm will use it in the next round. It is intended to mimic thermal fluctuations transiently exciting a physical system, and it helps the algorithm escape from local minima in the potential landscape. The algorithm starts at “high temperature”, and the probability of keeping these $E' > E$ solutions is relatively large. As the algorithm proceeds, the temperature is “reduced,” and the probability of retaining such solutions is reduced until the temperature reaches zero. The system is “frozen” into a local or global minimum.

Quantum annealing is an analog to simulated annealing [194]. Rather than thermal fluctuations, however, quantum annealing relies on “quantum fluctuations.” Quantum fluctuations are generally manifest in the quantum wavefunctions that represent quantum states. In general, a wavefunction is not localized to a single point, but, rather, is distributed or “extended” over some distance in parameter space. Thus, the wavefunction has both mean value and a standard deviation, which intuitively gives some notion of quantum fluctuation. Repeated measurements of an identically prepared system would project out different measurement results. The wavefunction is extended, and the variation in measurement results is a manifestation of the underlying

quantum fluctuations.

In quantum annealing, when the system wavefunction is extended between different local minima in the potential landscape that describes the problem, the corresponding “quantum fluctuations” are manifest as quantum tunneling between potential wells. Thus, quantum annealing relies on quantum fluctuations that enable quantum tunneling through barriers rather than thermal fluctuations, activating the system over a potential barrier. The probability of this tunneling is controlled by the strength of a transverse field in the annealing Hamiltonian a field along the x- or y-axis of the Bloch sphere instead of the temperature.

As with adiabatic quantum computing, the cost function for QA is encoded into a Hamiltonian H_{problem} such that the system ground state represents the optimal solution. The system is initialized in the known ground state of a starting Hamiltonian H_{initial} , which typically has all qubits co-aligned with a large, transverse X-field applied to all qubits. Then, the system is adiabatically evolved from the initial Hamiltonian to the final problem Hamiltonian:

$$H(t) = A(t)H_{\text{initial}} + B(t)H_{\text{problem}}, \quad (116)$$

where $A(0) = 1$ and $B(0) = 0$ at the beginning of the evolution, and $A(t_{\text{final}}) = 0$ and $B(t_{\text{final}}) = 1$ at the end of the evolution.

Moreover, as with an adiabatic quantum computer, the system will encounter a minimum gap at some point during the evolution, and, for practical problems of interesting size, almost certainly leave the ground state due to noise and Landau-Zener transitions. The hope for quantum annealing is that through a combination of quantum tunneling and dissipation, the system can return to lower-energy states or even the ground state.

The most advanced quantum annealing system is the commercially available D-Wave computer, which features more than 2000 superconducting qubits with fixed connectivity called the “chimera graph”. The D-Wave computer is certainly an engineering achievement, having integrated classical superconducting electronics to calibrate the more than 2000 qubits and implement an annealing schedule. However, despite many years of testing, there is no theoretical or experimental evidence that quantum annealing affords a quantum enhancement for a general class of optimization problems.

Whether quantum annealing will ever be able to provide quantum enhancement remains an open question. In rapidly scaling to 2000+ qubits, D-wave engineers had to make system choices that constrained them to use relatively low-coherence qubits, fixed connectivity, and solely ZZ interactions. It represents only a small part of the possible annealing “phase space.” Using higher-coherence qubits, other types of interactions, e.g., XX or YY, multi-body interactions, e.g., XXX, and enhanced connectivity graphs, may improve performance. Even if quantum annealers are ultimate “just classical computers” that scale classically with problem size, they may still be valuable if they can outperform existing classical computers for certain problems.

44 Quantum Annealing

In this section, we will continue our exploration of quantum annealing and on the history and challenges of quantum annealing. we think we should say something about D-wave. It certainly is an interesting story, so that we would put a timeline. In 1999, D-wave was founded. presumably, they came out of nowhere. The founders must have been doing some work before in 1999. In 2000, Fahri, Goldstone, Gutmann, and Sipser wrote a paper that proposes adiabatic quantum computation. a couple of years later, Aharonov, unfortunately, we did not look up the exact

date before this. A couple of years later, Aharonov et. al. Show it is universal. in 2007, D-wave announces first a 16-bit prototype adiabatic quantum computer. there is a lot of skepticism about this. So Scott Aaronson goes on a tirade in his blog and launches a crusade against them, saying they could not possibly say the things are saying could not possibly be true. that is well, and there is a couple of questions here. When they were founded, adiabatic quantum computation did not exist. So presumably, they were founded on some other kind of quantum computation. at some point, we decide adiabatic quantum computation was way to go. sometime between 2007 and today, we could not figure out when D-wave now says they do quantum annealing. So what is the difference? Well, adiabatic quantum computation, we are in the ground state, and we would like to operate at a temperature low enough to stay in the ground state. So what is this temperature? We call quantum adiabatic computing ground state. Let us have a first excited state. this is what is known as an avoided crossing, where this line and this line have roughly the same structure of the quantum state, as do this line and this line. we get a superposition of these two structures right here. the more these two structures differ, the smaller the energy gap is between them. So that is an oversimplification and waving hands, but it is something like that. Can we evolve our Hamiltonian quite quickly most of the time, and then just slow down that evolution, when we are going past we can, we know where the gaps are, or rather, if we know where these things are, we can evolve it quickly most of the time. in fact, in Grover's algorithm, we can get a square root speed up by adiabatic computing, or a square root speed up over the classical search by adiabatic computing. However, the way to do that is in Grover's algorithm, and there is one spot where we have an avoided crossing, which is we think $1/\sqrt{n}$ to get the speed up, we have to go quickly most of the time, then slow down right before the avoided crossing. then speed up right after it. If we do not know where these points where they come close are, it is going to be hard to speed up and slow down our evolution to account for them. the temperature means that one of our qubits might get excited, but if we excite this state, it is not going to go to this state, because the state and this state are structurally quite different with exciting qubit in this state, and we go up to this state. So the temperature is bigger than the smallest gap. So gaps account for energy, and energy converts to temperature by thermodynamics. So the right temperature is probably going to be bigger than the smallest gap. However, it is still small. D-wave does not operate at a temperature small enough to avoid thermal excitations. that is not because they do not operate at a small temperature. They operated at extremely low temperatures. it is just that the structure of their chips allows for thermal excitations, even at that temperature. So people were arguing with them about whether they could call this quantum adiabatic computation. So they decided to call it quantum annealing instead. So what does that mean? If quantum adiabatic computation were quantum, there would be proof that the quantum computer was universal, which means that theoretically, it could solve any problem that any quantum computer can. However, the problem of blowing up the size is due to a polynomial factor converting from the gate model to the adiabatic computation model and back. So if it were a quantum adiabatic computer, they would have a good reason to claim that it could do things that classical computers cannot. Well, they have a quantum annealing computer. it is certainly using quantum processes and operating in the quantum, but is it more powerful? Moreover, we want to say no theoretical results. There are chips that we can program the Hamiltonian, and we can program a Hamiltonian to change from one Hamiltonian to another Hamiltonian slowly. we can put the starting Hamiltonian into the ground state. we are operating at a temperature too large not to have thermal excitations. So presumably, we could take this process and construct some mathematical model of it. Although we might have to worry about what the right temperature for this mathematical model is. then we can ask, does this mathematical model let us do anything that we cannot do on classical computers? we do not know. Nobody knows. the other problem is that they have experiments

that they claim show that the computer does things better than classical computers, but is it an exponential speed up? Or is it just that their computer has electrical? It has a Hamiltonian trying to find its ground state, and it does this reasonably fast. there is a constant factor better than classical computers that are letting it find the ground state better than classical computers can because physics processes can be really fast. So we do not know whether D-wave is more powerful.

2. Quantum Annealing II; In quantum annealing, what is the most relevant consequence of the system temperature not being low enough?

- The minimum energy gap between the ground state and the first excited state is reduced due to the temperature, inducing Landau-Zener transitions.
- energy from the environment excites the system, bringing it out of the ground state.
- The coherence time of the spins is reduced, and the gate fidelity is reduced.
- The minimum computational time necessary to keep the system in its ground state decreases.

Solution:

The minimum energy gap does not generally depend on temperature. Although the coherence of a single spin might be affected by temperature, quantum annealing is not based on digital gate operations. The minimum computational time refers to the minimum time required to evolve the system to the ground state of the desired Hamiltonian without excitation to an excited state. The minimum gap energy sets it, and it generally does not depend on the temperature of the system.

45 Grover's Algorithm: Quantum Search

In this section, we will discuss Grover's algorithm and how it works. At the end of this section, we will implement Grover's algorithm on the IBM quantum computer.

In this section, we will take a look at Grover's algorithm. as we have done previously with Deutsch-Jozsa and Shor's algorithm [26], we will do it in the quantum circuit model. by the end of the section, we will implement it for yourselves on a real cloud-based quantum computer [195]. Grover's algorithm is often described in the context of searching an unstructured database. Here though, Let us generalize the search problem to the related problem of function inversion. Consider a function, f of x , which can take on the value 0 or 1, depending on the argument x . For example, for x equals 10, the function f of 10 equals 1, and 0 for all other x values. Now, the function inversion problem is the following. Given f of x equals 1, can we find the value of x or a value of x if there is more than one solution. Classically, one has little choice but to try different x -values and test the function. So, for n total x -values of which M satisfy f of x equals 1, it will take on the order of N divided by M tries to succeed with high probability. However, on a quantum computer, the same task succeeds with high probability in the only square root of N over M tries, a quadratic improvement over classical computing. while a quadratic improvement may not seem like a lot, it does become practically significant for problems with large N . To implement Grover's algorithm, and we need an operational block that can recognize if a test value of x satisfies the function or not. This operation is called an oracle. it is a key part of each trial, which we will call a Grover iteration. Now, it may seem challenging or even cheating to define an oracle that represents, for example, the database. After all, in loading such a database into the quantum computer, have not we already searched it? Now, that is certainly true, but

this is not how an oracle works. Again, it is worthwhile to think in terms of a mathematical function. The oracle does not need to know every answer to every function call, nor does it need to have a ledger of all the input and output values. Rather, it just needs to be able to calculate the function and recognize when a particular condition is satisfied. we can conceptually program different functions into the oracle while keeping the underlying machinery in place. we will not discuss in detail how this is done, as it is problem-dependent. However, we just note that this type of oracle can be designed using reversible logic approaches. The idea behind Grover's algorithm is the following. we start with an index register of values x running from 0 to n minus 1. The oracle takes a test value x , calculates the function f of x , and performs modulo-2 addition of f of x with a helper qubit, which we will call the oracle qubit. The oracle qubit is prepared in a superposition state 0 minus 1 , and it plays a similar role as the helper qubit did in the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm studied in section 1. If f of x equals 0 , then the modulo-2 addition leaves the superposition state unchanged. However, if f of x equals 1 , then there is a sign change on the oracle qubit. 0 minus 1 becomes 1 minus 0 . by pulling out this minus sign, we return to the original superposition state, 0 minus 1 , but with a minus sign in front. as we discuss with the Deutsch-Jozsa algorithm, this minus sign can be written as minus 1 to the f of x power. Thus, the minus 1 is realized when f of x equals 1 , that is when a particular value of x is a solution to the search problem. It is how the oracle marks a quantum state when it recognizes a satisfied condition. To implement Grover's algorithm, we start with the initialization stage of the quantum circuit model. Since there are n possible values of x , we will choose q qubits for register 1. register 2 will hold a single qubit, which is the oracle qubit. Register 1 qubits are prepared in state 0 and the oracle qubit in state 1 . as before, we will associate register one with yellow and register 2 with green to help keep track as the algorithm unfolds. In the compute stage, the first step is to create a large equal superposition state of register 1 qubits using q Hadamard gates. This state has n equals 2^q the q -th power components. as we did before, we will replace the 2 to the q -th power binary combinations of q qubits with decimal equivalence x equals 0 to n minus 1 . The oracle qubit is placed into the superposition state 0 minus 1 using a single Hadamard gate. The next step is to implement a Grover iteration, which we will call G , and we will do this on the order of square root of n times to obtain a solution with order unit probability. Each G contains the oracle operator O , which with the help of the oracle qubit, will leave a minus 1 on the register 1 states for values x , which satisfy f of x equals 1 . as we will see in a moment, the oracle operation has a geometric interpretation. It is a reflection operation. we will come back to that in a moment. Now, the remainder of the Grover iteration is a conditional phase shift nestled between Hadamard gates. The conditional phase shift leaves state 0 alone and, otherwise, places a minus 1 phase shift in front of all other states x . It can be written in terms of an equal superposition state, just like the one we started with. we will call this state CI . we encourage us to work this out for yourselves. as we will see in a moment, this set of three operations can also be viewed as a reflection across the vector ψ . Together with the oracle, these two reflections in the Grover iteration serve to rotate the quantum state by an angle θ . we will look at the geometric picture in a moment. However, for now, let us continue with the circuit model. To see how the Grover iteration acts on register 1, Let us rewrite the sum over x as two terms. One term will be the sum over all x -values that are not solutions, that is, give f of x equals 0 . The second term will be the remaining x -values that are a solution and give f of x equal 1 . This, in turn, can be written in terms of normalized states, α , and β . we then run the Grover iteration on the order of square root of n times. Let us assume there are k iterations, with each iteration imparting a phase shift θ . The net result is the cosine of $2k$ plus 1 over 2 in front of state α , which is not solutions, and sine $2k$ plus 1 over 2 in front of state β , which is the solutions. the oracle qubit remains unchanged throughout. Starting from a small angle θ , much less than $\pi/2$, we see that as k increases, the cosine term goes to 0 suppressing the

amplitude of the wrong answers and the sine term towards 1, enhancing the amplitude of the correct answers. Then a measurement is made, and one of the x-value solutions in the state β is measured with high probability. Let us now look at the geometric interpretation to see how repeated Grover iterations lead to the correct solution. The state CI is in the register 1 equals superposition state with end components. we write it in terms of the states α and β , where α is all the x-values that are not solutions, and β represents the single x-value or multiple end values that are solutions yielding f of x equals 1. The state's α and β are orthogonal, and we can represent them as orthogonal vectors. Since the state CI is normalized to 1, we can also write state CI in terms of the cosine and sine $\theta/2$. the state CI makes an angle $\theta/2$ with the α axis., and Now since we start with all x-values equally likely, and we assume there are only one or a few solutions, the vector CI is close to the α axis. The oracle acts first, and it places a minus sign in front of the state β , which represents the valid solutions. It is a reflection over the α axis. The remainder of the Grover iteration, the conditional phase shifts nestled between Hadamard gates, is a reflection of the state CI. The result from a single Grover iteration is then to move the state CI and angle θ towards the β axis. Essentially, the amplitudes of the solutions are enhanced, while the amplitudes of the remaining states are being suppressed. The Grover iteration is then repeated k times, where k is on the order of square root of N. The iterative reflections continue to push the vector toward the β axis, increasing the likelihood that when a measurement is made, the state will be projected into a value of x that satisfies f of x equal 1. Lastly, we can show that the number of iterations. R is of the order square root of n. The state CI is an angle γ away from the β axis, where γ equals arccosine square root of M over N., and we know that each iteration pushes us an angle θ toward the β axis. So, the number of repetitions we need is the closest integer to the ratio of γ over θ . we want to rotate the state CI at least pass $\pi/4$ from the α axis so that the probability of measuring a β solution is greater than a 1/2, and In fact, we can place an upper bound on the number R. It is $\pi/4$ times the square root of M divided by N. This shows that Grover's algorithm will find a solution with a high probability for only order square root of n iterations. In contrast, it will take a classical computer on the order of n queries.

what is the current status or capability for the most capable quantum computers today? For running Shor's algorithm, or Grover's algorithm [51]. So, the status today is that, all of these algorithms, like Shor's algorithm and Grover's algorithm, they are done in prototype fashion, or demonstration fashion, which means that they are not exceeding the capabilities of classical computer today [52]. we are demonstrating on smaller scale quantum computers that these algorithms, in fact, work. That they in fact return the correct answer. that gives us confidence that when we build larger quantum computers that those algorithms will still work. then the question would be, when are we going to get to this threshold or breaking point where a quantum computer can do something that classical computers, in principle could do, but cannot do in any kind of reasonable timeframe? And so that is called quantum supremacy, that turning point. there are many groups now, and industry, in particular, Google is pursuing a quantum supremacy [196–198] experiment with their Bristlecone chip. [168], we know, it is still not close to being able to implement, say, Shor's algorithm, or Grover's algorithm, yet, in a way that cannot be done on a classical computer. Very likely what they are going to do is demonstrate a particular physics problem. It will be a well-posed problem. what they will do is they will demonstrate that they can solve that problem on a quantum computer and get the answer out, whereas trying to solve that exact same problem on a classical computer just does not work in a reasonable amount of time. that will be the first demonstration of quantum supremacy [196,197,199]. Now, in some sense, one might say, we have not already done that? we know, neutral atoms, or in other physical systems, we basically set it up, it is a complicated physical system, we set it up, and we look at the answer, and basically, we let our quantum computer emulate another system? And

then we say, we could not calculate what was going to happen, so that is quantum supremacy. we think that there is a distinction to be made here. Those are very important experiments, by the way, we not saying they are not. But we think that when we discuss about quantum supremacy, what we mean here is that, not that no classical computer could ever simulate? that is not what we are discussing about. What we are discussing about is using single and two qubit gates, a universal logic set of gates applied to a problem, and that that problem exhibits quantum advantage beyond what a classical computer could do. the reason that distinction is important is because with a universal set of gates, in principle, we could do any algorithm? And we could solve any problem? And so, a demonstration of quantum supremacy should be a demonstration that is abstracted into quantum gates which in principle could do any algorithm? Now, it is only going to be applied to this one, early on, this one particular problem, or set of problems that shows quantum supremacy, and to apply it to practical problems that we care about that may still require yet a larger quantum computer. that is almost certainly going to be true. But that distinction is important. we think emulation in general is not the same as quantum supremacy. we are going to discuss about NISQ algorithms, algorithms that people are trying to develop today with the qubits that we have today. we are going to look at different types of noise, what do we mean by noise? What does noise do to cause decoherence? What types of noise exist? For example, there can be systematic noise. So, for example, we want to rotate from the North Pole to the South Pole, but every time we do that, we go a little bit too far, or we do not go quite far enough. every time we do it, we get the same error, it is just off by the same amount, that is a systematic error. There can also be errors which are stochastic. That, each time there is some noise on my control lines which either over-rotate or under-rotate a little bit, but how much it over or under-rotates is different in time, it changes in time, and we will discuss about these different types of noise, and we will also discuss about, ways that we can mitigate noise. error correction is one way that we can mitigate noise, and that involves adding redundancy, so we add more qubits, but by adding more qubits, and in particular qubits with a high enough fidelity, it exceeds some threshold. When they exceed that threshold, adding more improves the overall situation of all the qubits? And the way that this is implemented is through the use of syndromes, and we will go into detail about what that means. Now, there are other types of mitigation strategies that we can implement, and those are related, primarily to dephasing. Now, dephasing, it turns out in principle, it is reversible. it is a coherent error, as we call it. so, by doing certain pulse sequences, we can dynamically mitigate the error, and we will discuss through that in some detail. we think if these are topics that we find interesting, and in particular, we want to know more than just we have, that we want to take it one level deeper, look at how quantum computing works, and in particular how we are going to fight against noise that we have, either systematic or stochastic noise, and in principle, how error correction works. If we want to understand how error correction works, what fault tolerance means, what these syndromes are, how they are implemented. we will give the picture of how these protocols work, how error correction works. We are trying to introduce terminology, what it means, give some physical intuition.

So, can quantum computers create the ability to manipulate time, and time travel? What does this really mean? we know, quantum computing is what is called reversible, and we think we may have discussed about that when we looked at single and two qubit gates. But with classical gates, and quantum gates. in classical boolean logic, many of the gates are irreversible. So for example, the AND gate. we have two inputs, we AND them, and we get one number out. But if we look at the output number, we cannot generally go backwards and tell we what the inputs were. Now, for an AND gate, if we get a one out, then we know that the two inputs were one and one. Fine, but if we get a zero out, we cannot tell whether it was zero zero, zero one, or one zero. All three of those combinations of input bits will give a zero out. So in that sense, that is not a

reversible gate. so, one might think that we can flow forwards in time and get the output, but we cannot flow backwards in time and derive the inputs from the output. Now, there are a few reversible, there is a concept of reversible logic in classical computing, and in fact, in quantum systems, quantum computers, and quantum qubits, and these operations, these are unitary, and certainly in the absence of noise, they are unitary, and so, ideally, we go forwards, we can also run an algorithm backwards and go from the output to the input. we can run it forwards and go from the input to the output. so, in this sense, if we did those experiments, and many people have, but if we wanted to sell it as, we reverse time, we could think of it that way, but we are not really reversing time. we are just implementing an algorithm backwards.

46 Introduction to Grover's Algorithm on the Quantum Experience

In this section, we will continue our exploration of the Grover search algorithm, and discuss how it is applied to a specific problem called the “exactly-1 3SAT” problem [42].

In this section, we will discuss how to implement and run Grover's algorithm. First, let us briefly recall What the problem solved by this algorithm is, and what are its benefits compared to classical algorithms. Grover's algorithm is designed to solve a completely unstructured search problem. Imagine that we have a list of two to the n numbers, and we want to find the position of a given number that appears once in this list. If we know that the list is sorted, we can use binary search, and find the position of the desired number looking at just an element out of the two to the n in the list. However, if we do not have any information whatsoever on the list, we may have to look at all of its elements to find the position of the desired number. In fact, given any deterministic classical algorithm to solve this search problem, we can construct a list on which the algorithm has to look at all of the two to the n elements before it finds the correct answer. Even a randomized classical algorithm would have to look at approximately two to the n elements on average. Using a quantum algorithm, we can do better than this. Let us properly state our assumptions first. we have a function, f , that maps any n digit binary string into zero or one, with the property that there exists a unique binary string for which the function has value one. This is the magic binary string that we want to find. Let us call l the integer that corresponds to it. So, that f of l is equal to one. we want to determine l while evaluating f as few times as possible. Since there is no property of f that can be exploited, we know that we can do it in two to the n evaluations of f classically, simply by applying f to all binary strings. However, can we do better? Grover's algorithm can do this with only the square root of two to the n evaluations of f , a quadratic improvement. The function f is assumed to be encoded by a quantum circuit that acts on n plus one qubit. The first n qubits are the input register. The last qubit is the output register. The circuit that implements f does not modify the input register. It performs the modulo 2 addition between the output register and the result of f applied to the input register. Separating the input and the output registers are standard in the quantum world because it allows reversibility of the function. we are given a three-set formula that is the logical end of a series of clauses and Boolean variables, where each clause is the logical, or of three Boolean variables or their negation. we want to find an assignment of the Boolean variables that makes the formula evaluate to true, ensuring that there is exactly one true literal per clause. It is a variation of the well-know three-satisfiability problem, and it is NP-hard. In the implementation, when we use the instance of exactly one three-satisfiability, specified by the formula that we can see on the screen. In this section, we will only work with the formula shown here. To construct the function f , we need a quantum circuit that acts on qubits encoding the Boolean variables and

determines if this formula is satisfied. Notice that the circuit that implements f should simply be able to decide if the Boolean assignment corresponding to the binary string it is given as input satisfies the formula. Determining and returning the satisfying assignment, we are the goal of Grover's algorithm, not of the function f . The example formula has three Boolean variables, x_1 , x_2 , and x_3 . There are eight possible assignments. we can see in this table that only one possible assignment evaluates to true. we can verify this. As usual, one means true, and zero means false. Let us call U_f the unitary matrix that implements f . we can implement U_f in several ways. For simplicity, we have composed the problem of computing U_f by introducing three auxiliary qubits, one for each clause. For each clause, we construct a circuit that sets the corresponding zero qubits to one if and only if the clause has exactly one true term. Finally, the output register of U_f is set to one if and only if all three auxiliary qubits are one. For example, the circuit sets the bottom qubit, y_1 to one for the clause x_1 , or x_2 , or not x_3 . The x -gate flips the qubit corresponding to x_3 because x_3 appears negated in the clause. Using three CNOT gates, we set y_1 equal x_1 , xor, x_2 , xor, not x_3 , implying that y_1 is equal to one if an odd number of literals is satisfied. Since we want y_1 equals to one if and only if exactly one literal is satisfied, we use a triply-controlled not gate to implement the desired formula finally. The last x -gate simply resets the state of the qubit x_3 . Similarly, we can implement the circuit that checks whether the second clause, not x_1 , or not x_2 , or not x_3 is satisfied, and one for the third clause, not x_1 , or x_2 , or x_3 . To implement this circuit, there is a small obstacle; the triply-controlled not gate is not part of the basic gate set. Such a gate can be implemented in several ways. For simplicity, we choose to do it using 3 doubly-controlled, not gates, and one auxiliary qubit, as we show on the screen. In the circuit, we can quickly verify that q_4 is set to one if and only if q_0, q_1, q_2 are one. The final doubly-controlled not resets the state of the auxiliary qubit q_3 . Remember that if we plan to re-use the auxiliary qubits, we should leave them in the same state as they begin. With these blocks, we can construct the full circuit that implements U_f using four auxiliary qubits, one for each of the three clauses, and one for the triply-controlled not. For each of the three clauses, we set the corresponding auxiliary qubit to one if the clause is satisfied. Then we apply a logical and between these three auxiliary qubits. Finally, we run the same circuit in reverse to reset the state of the auxiliary qubits. we have seen how to implement the function U_f used in one of the building blocks of Grover's algorithm. Remember that Grover's algorithms have three steps, initialization, sign flip, and inversion about the average. Let us see how to implement these steps. we will use the first three qubits lines for the input, the fourth as output, and the remaining qubits will be auxiliary qubits. For the initialization, we apply Hadamard gates on the input lines. on the output line, we apply an x -gate and then a Hadamard. It will be important for the science lab. At this point, the state of the input qubits is in the uniform superposition. All amplitudes are equal. For the sign flip, we simply applied the circuit that we constructed for U_f . Because we prepared the state of the output qubit in the way we described, this has the effect of flipping the sign of the amplitude corresponding to the basis state for which U_f outputs one. The last step is the inversion of the average. It is implemented by this simple circuit, which we can easily verify applies the matrix shown at the bottom. The matrix has the effect of mapping each amplitude to twice the average coefficient minus the amplitude itself. Because the average is smaller than most of the coefficients, all amplitudes except the negative one get reduced. the negative one gets amplified. It is one iteration of Grover's algorithm. The optimal number of iterations, k , can be found using the formula shown on the screen from which we derive that we must perform two iterations. It simply means that we should append to the overall circuit another copy of the circuit that performs a sign flip, and another copy of the circuit that performs the inversion about the average. that is it. we can now run this circuit on the simulator and look at the results. This circuit is, unfortunately, a bit too large to run on a real device, so we will have to rely on the simulator. This is the histogram of the outcome probabilities after 2,048

samples. After two iterations and only two calls to the black box function U_f , we sample the correct string, 101, with a probability of approximately 95%. In comparison, any deterministic classical algorithm would have needed eight calls in the worst case. Notice that as we increase the number of iterations of Grover's algorithm, the probability of sampling the correct string goes down. This is the histogram for three iterations, and the probability dropped down to 32%. The number of iterations must be chosen optimally.

The Exactly-1 3-SAT problem requires us to find an assignment such that $f = 1$ (or, True), and there is exactly one literal that evaluates to True in every clause of f .

Regarding the Exactly-1 3-SAT problem, which of the following statements are valid for the Boolean function:

$$f(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (x_1 \vee x_2 \vee \neg x_3) \wedge (\neg x_1 \vee \neg x_2 \vee \neg x_3) \wedge (\neg x_1 \vee x_2 \vee x_3)? \quad (117)$$

- Recall that $x_1 \vee x_2$ means x_1 OR x_2 ; $x_1 \wedge x_2$ means x_1 AND x_2 ; and $\neg x_1$ means NOT x_1
1. The second clause has x_1, x_2 , and x_3 as its literals
 2. The input $(x_1, x_2, x_3) = (0, 1, 0)$ has three True literals in the third clause
 3. Each clause of the Exactly-1 3-SAT problem can be represented by a sub-circuit and evaluated independently.
 4. The oracle operation is obtained by combining all sub-circuits for all clauses, such that it outputs True if and only if all clauses are satisfied with exactly one True literal each.

47 Grover's Algorithm: Introduction

Grover's algorithm can be decomposed into three steps: Initialization of the system, and Oracle operator O , and a (second) reflection operator W . For a list of $N = 2^n$ items, the system is initialized in the n -qubit equal superposition state. The Oracle operator encodes and marks the information in the list onto the quantum system; this can be viewed as the first reflection. Once the list is encoded, the operator W applies a second reflection. The resulting state after these two operations is closer to the solution state corresponding to the marked item. The product of the two reflections $G=WO$ the Grover iteration is applied several times, and the number of repetitions necessary to find the marked item is upper bounded by $\frac{\pi}{4}\sqrt{N}$.

we will implement Grover's algorithm for $N=4$. To make the problem easier to program, we will use a compiled version of the algorithm, that is, $n=2$ qubits instead of $n=2+1$ qubits. The implementation is divided into five sections: Introduction, Initialization, Oracle O , Grover Operator, and Putting it All Together.

Introduction Grover's algorithm allows we to find marked items from an unstructured list. We will assume that there is only one marked item, which we will call β . We start by defining a function $f(x)$ such that the function is true, $f(x) = 1$, only if the input x corresponds to the marked item β , and zero otherwise. Mathematically, this can be written as:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{If } x \neq \beta, \\ 1 & \text{if } x = \beta. \end{cases} \quad (118)$$

For a list of $N = 2^n$ items, Grover's algorithm requires an n -qubit quantum system. We can associate each one of the N items of the list, x , with one of the states of the n -qubit computational basis $x \rightarrow |x\rangle$. In this IBM Q experience [200], we will consider the following associations:

For a list of N=4 items and a system of two-qubits

Table 6: N=4 items and a system of two-qubits

Item in decimal	Item in binary	Basis state
0	00	$ 00\rangle$
1	01	$ 01\rangle$
2	10	$ 10\rangle$
3	11	$ 11\rangle$

For a list of N=8 items and a system of three-qubits

Table 7: N=8 items and a system of three-qubits

Item in decimal	Item in binary	Basis state
0	000	$ 000\rangle$
1	001	$ 001\rangle$
2	010	$ 010\rangle$
3	011	$ 011\rangle$
4	100	$ 100\rangle$
5	101	$ 101\rangle$
6	110	$ 110\rangle$
7	111	$ 111\rangle$

To encode the function $f(x)$ into a quantum computer, the Oracle operator O is applied onto the equal n -qubit superposition state. This operation acts as an identity for each basis state that does not correspond to the marked item, and adds a negative sign to the solution state $|\beta\rangle$,

$$|x\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle = \begin{cases} |x\rangle & \text{if } x \neq \beta, \\ -|x\rangle & \text{if } x = \beta. \end{cases} \quad (119)$$

N=4 example: If the marked item is $\beta = 2$ in decimal, then the function f is given by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x = 00, 01, 11, \\ 1 & \text{if } x = 10. \end{cases} \quad (120)$$

and therefore the oracle O must transform the state according to:

$$|00\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(00)} |00\rangle = |00\rangle, \quad (121)$$

$$|01\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(01)} |01\rangle = |01\rangle, \quad (122)$$

$$|10\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(10)} |10\rangle = -|10\rangle, \quad (123)$$

$$|11\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(11)} |11\rangle = |11\rangle. \quad (124)$$

N=8 example: If marked item is $\beta = 2$ in decimal, then the function f is given by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x = 010, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (125)$$

and therefore the oracle O must transform according to:

$$|010\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(010)} |010\rangle = -|010\rangle \quad (126)$$

and

$$|x\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle = |x\rangle, \text{ for } x \neq 010. \quad (127)$$

How Many Qubits? N=512; For a list of N=512 items, how many qubits would we need to implement Grover's algorithm?

Solution: For a list of $N = 2^n$ elements, the Grover's algorithm needs n qubits. For 512 items: $512 = 2^n \rightarrow n = 9$

48 Grover's Algorithm: Initialization

State preparation:

At the beginning of the protocol, there is no information about where the marked item is. Thus, it is convenient to start with an equal superposition state

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} |x\rangle, \quad (128)$$

such that each basis state $|x\rangle$ will have the same probability of being measured:

$$\frac{1}{N} = \frac{1}{2^n}. \quad (129)$$

Even though we do not know which item is the marked item at the beginning of the algorithm, we can break the equal superposition state into a sum over the marked items and a sum over all other items,

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} |x\rangle, \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x:f(x)=0} |x\rangle + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x:f(x)=1} |x\rangle, \\ &= \underbrace{\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x:f(x)=0} |x\rangle}_{\text{Non-solution state}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} |\beta\rangle}_{\text{Solution state}} \end{aligned} \quad (130)$$

To understand the geometrical interpretation of the algorithm, it is convenient to define the normalized quantum state

$$|\alpha\rangle \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{N-1}{N}}} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{x:f(x)=0} |x\rangle \right), \quad (131)$$

such that the equal superposition state can be written as the sum

$$|\psi\rangle = \underbrace{\sqrt{\frac{N-1}{N}}|\alpha\rangle}_{\text{Non-solution state}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}|\beta\rangle}_{\text{Solution state}}, \quad (132)$$

or, equivalently,

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle, \quad (133)$$

where we have defined the angle θ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) &= \sqrt{\frac{N-1}{N}}, \\ \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}. \end{aligned} \quad (134)$$

The figure below shows a graphical representation of quantum states $|\psi\rangle$, $|\beta\rangle$, and $|\alpha\rangle$ as vectors in a two-dimensional space. The projection of the superposition state $|\psi\rangle$ onto the solution state $|\beta\rangle$ is equal to $1/\sqrt{N}$, and the projection of $|\psi\rangle$ on $|\alpha\rangle$ is equal to $\sqrt{(N-1)/N}$.

Figure 17: Initialization N3

Two-qubit initialization:

To implement Grover's algorithm for a list of $N = 2^n = 4$ elements, the compiled algorithm requires two qubits, $n = 2$. To prepare the two qubits in an equal superposition state $|\psi\rangle$, a Hadamard gate is applied to each qubit,

$$\begin{aligned} |0\rangle|0\rangle &\rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \\ &= \frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle + |0\rangle|1\rangle + |1\rangle|0\rangle + |1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (135)$$

If we assume that the marked item is given by $\beta = 3$ (decimal representation), then it is convenient to write the two-qubit equal superposition state as

$$|\psi\rangle = \underbrace{\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle + |0\rangle|1\rangle + |1\rangle|0\rangle}{2}}_{\text{Non-solution state}} + \underbrace{\frac{|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}}_{\text{Solution state}}, \quad (136)$$

or as a superposition of the non-solution and solution states

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} |\alpha\rangle + \frac{1}{2} |\beta\rangle = \cos(30^\circ) |\alpha\rangle + \sin(30^\circ) |\beta\rangle, \quad (137)$$

where the non-solution state is given by

$$|\alpha\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (|0\rangle|0\rangle + |0\rangle|1\rangle + |1\rangle|0\rangle), \quad (138)$$

and the solution state by

$$|\beta\rangle = |1\rangle|1\rangle. \quad (139)$$

The figure below shows the graphical representation of the two-qubit equal superposition state $|\psi\rangle$. The projection of $|\psi\rangle$ on $|\alpha\rangle$ and $|\beta\rangle$ are $\sqrt{3}/2$ and $1/2$ respectively.

Figure 18: Initialization N2

3. Two-qubit Equal Superposition State; Write a QASM code [201] that generates the equal superposition state for two-qubits. To do this:

- Apply a Hadamard gate in the first qubit
- Apply a Hadamard gate in the second qubit
- Save the measurement's result of the first qubit in the first bit
- Save the measurement's result of the second qubit in the second bit

Figure 19: Two-qubit Equal Superposition State

Solution:

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[5];
3 creg c[5];
4 h q[0];
5 h q[1];
6 measure q[0] -> c[0];
7 measure q[1] -> c[1];

```

A Hadamard gate transforms the states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ into $\frac{|0\rangle+|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ and $\frac{|0\rangle-|1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$ respectively. By applying a Hadamard gate on each qubit, we have just created the equal superposition two-qubit state $\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$.

4. Three-qubit Equal Superposition State; Write a QASM code that generates the equal superposition state for three-qubits. To do this:

- Apply a Hadamard gate in the first qubit
- Apply a Hadamard gate in the second qubit
- Apply a Hadamard gate in the third qubit
- Save the measurement's result of the first qubit in the first bit
- Save the measurement's result of the second qubit in the second bit
- Save the measurement's result of the third qubit in the third bit

Figure 20: Three-qubit Equal Superposition State

Solution:

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[5];
3 creg c[5];
4 h q[0];
5 h q[1];
6 h q[2];
7 measure q[0] -> c[0];
8 measure q[1] -> c[1];
9 measure q[2] -> c[2];

```

49 Grover's Algorithm: Oracle O

Oracle operation:

The role of the oracle, O , is to encode the function $f(x)$ in the quantum system and mark the solution. The operation transforms each state of the computational basis as

$$|x\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(x)} |x\rangle. \quad (140)$$

In the first iteration of the protocol, this operation transforms the equal superposition state according to:

$$O|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) O|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) O|\beta\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) |\alpha\rangle - \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) |\beta\rangle. \quad (141)$$

The figure below shows the graphical representation of the equal superposition state after the Oracle operator, $O|\psi\rangle$. The amplitude of $|\psi\rangle$ in front of $|\alpha\rangle$ remains the same as before. However, the amplitude in front of $|\beta\rangle$ acquires a negative sign. The oracle operation serves to reflect the state $|\psi\rangle$ about the non-solution state $|\alpha\rangle$.

Figure 21: Oracle N

N=4 item list

Example 1: If the marked item is $\beta = 3$ (decimal representation), then the function f is given by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = 11, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

and therefore the oracle O must transform according to:

$$|\psi\rangle \rightarrow \cos(30^\circ) |\alpha\rangle - \sin(30^\circ) |\beta\rangle, \quad (142)$$

where the non-solution state is

$$|\alpha\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} (|0\rangle |0\rangle + |0\rangle |1\rangle + |1\rangle |0\rangle), \quad (143)$$

and the solution state is

$$|\beta\rangle = |1\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (144)$$

In particular, the Oracle must transform each element of the two-qubit basis according to:

$$|0\rangle |0\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(00)} |0\rangle |0\rangle = |0\rangle |0\rangle, \quad (145)$$

$$|0\rangle |1\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(01)} |0\rangle |1\rangle = |0\rangle |1\rangle, \quad (146)$$

$$|1\rangle |0\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(10)} |1\rangle |0\rangle = |1\rangle |0\rangle, \quad (147)$$

$$|1\rangle |1\rangle \rightarrow (-1)^{f(11)} |1\rangle |1\rangle = -|1\rangle |1\rangle. \quad (148)$$

The figure below shows a graphical representation of the non-solution, solution, and reflected states.

Figure 22: Oracle 2

The quantum circuit below implements the Oracle for this marked item. We can verify this by computing the state of each element of the basis after the operation. In this case, the Oracle is composed of two Hadamard gates on the second qubit, and one CNOT gate with the first qubit as control and the second as the target. Remember that the Hadamard gate maps a single qubit state according to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |0\rangle &\rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle + |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \\
 |1\rangle &\rightarrow \frac{|0\rangle - |1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{149}$$

And, the CNOT gate maps a two-qubit state according to:

$$|0\rangle |0\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle |0\rangle, \tag{150}$$

$$|0\rangle |1\rangle \rightarrow |0\rangle |1\rangle, \tag{151}$$

$$|1\rangle |0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle |1\rangle, \tag{152}$$

$$|1\rangle |1\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle |0\rangle. \tag{153}$$

Figure 23: Oracle 11

The table below shows the evolution of the two-qubit basis states. we can see that the only basis state that acquires a negative sign is the solution state.

Table 8: two-qubit basis states

Basis State	After first Hadamard H	After CNOT gate	After second Hadamard H
$ 0\rangle 0\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle 0\rangle$
$ 0\rangle 1\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle 1\rangle$
$ 1\rangle 0\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 1\rangle 0\rangle$
$ 1\rangle 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$- 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$- 1\rangle 1\rangle$

5. N=4: Oracle Operator $\beta = 3$; For a list of N=4 items, write the QASM code that generates the Oracle operator when the marked item is $\beta = 3$ (decimal representation). Use qubits q[3] and q[4] as the first and second qubit respectively. Remember that we are using the ibmqx4 backend [202], and do not forget to measure our two qubits. Compare our results with the table above using $q[3], q[4] = |0\rangle|0\rangle$.

Figure 24: N=4: Oracle Operator $\beta = 3$

Solution:

```

1  include "qelib1.inc";
2  qreg q[5];
3  creg c[5];
4  h q[4];
5  cx q[3],q[4];
6  h q[4];
7  measure q[3] -> c[3];
8  measure q[4] -> c[4];
9

```

Example 2: If the marked item is $\beta = 2$ (decimal representation), then the function f is given by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x = 10, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (154)$$

The Oracle must transform each element of the two-qubit basis according to:

$$\begin{aligned}
|0\rangle|0\rangle &\rightarrow (-1)^{f(00)}|0\rangle|0\rangle = |0\rangle|0\rangle \\
|0\rangle|1\rangle &\rightarrow (-1)^{f(01)}|0\rangle|1\rangle = |0\rangle|1\rangle \\
|1\rangle|0\rangle &\rightarrow (-1)^{f(10)}|1\rangle|0\rangle = -|1\rangle|0\rangle \\
|1\rangle|1\rangle &\rightarrow (-1)^{f(11)}|1\rangle|1\rangle = |1\rangle|1\rangle
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 25: Oracle 10

The circuit above implements the Oracle for the item $\beta = 10$, where the S gate transforms according to:

$$\begin{aligned} |0\rangle &\rightarrow |0\rangle \\ |1\rangle &\rightarrow i|1\rangle \end{aligned}$$

The table below shows the evolution of the basis state under the Oracle. we can see that the only basis state that acquires a negative sign is the solution state $|1\rangle|0\rangle$

Table 9: basis state under the Oracle

Basis State	After first S	After first H	After CNOT	After second H	After second S
$ 0\rangle 0\rangle$	$ 0\rangle 0\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle 0\rangle$	$ 0\rangle 0\rangle$
$ 0\rangle 1\rangle$	$ 0\rangle 1\rangle$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$ 0\rangle 1\rangle$	$ 0\rangle 1\rangle$
$ 1\rangle 0\rangle$	$i 1\rangle 0\rangle$	$i 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$i 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle+ 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$i 1\rangle 0\rangle$	$- 1\rangle 0\rangle$
$ 1\rangle 1\rangle$	$i 1\rangle 1\rangle$	$i 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$-i 1\rangle \frac{ 0\rangle- 1\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$	$-i 1\rangle 1\rangle$	$ 1\rangle 1\rangle$

6. N=4: Oracle Operator $\beta = 2$; For a list of N=4 items, write the QASM code [203] that generates the Oracle operator when the marked item is $\beta = 2$ (decimal representation). Use qubits q[3] and q[4] as the first and second qubit respectively.

Figure 26: N=4: Oracle Operator $\beta = 2$

Solution:

```

1  include "qelib1.inc";
2  qreg q[5];
3  creg c[5];
4  s q[3];
5  h q[4];
6  cx q[3],q[4];
7  h q[4];
8  s q[3];
9  measure q[3] -> c[3];
10 measure q[4] -> c[4];
11

```

50 Grover's Algorithm: Grover Operator

Reflection W :

The third step in Grover's algorithm is given by the implementation of the second reflection, which we will call W . Let us recall the state after the first implementation of the Oracle Operator,

$$O|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle - \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle. \quad (155)$$

The β operator then corresponds to a reflection about the equal superposition state $|\psi\rangle$. Since this operator does not depend on the function $f(x)$ and, rather, depends only on the superposition state, W is the same for any marked item β .

Grover Operator

We define the Grover operator as $G = WO$,

that is, the application of the Oracle operator followed by the W reflection.

$$G|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{3\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle \quad (156)$$

Figure 27: N Grover

The state after the second Grover iteration is:

$$G^2|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{5\theta}{2}\right)|\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{5\theta}{2}\right)|\beta\rangle \quad (157)$$

Figure 28: N Grover

In general, the state after the k -th Grover iteration will be given by

$$G^k |\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{2k+1}{2}\theta\right) |\alpha\rangle + \sin\left(\frac{2k+1}{2}\theta\right) |\beta\rangle \quad (158)$$

$N = 4$ items: Marked item $\beta = 11$

As we discussed in the previous section, the equal superposition state for a list of 4 items is given by:

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos(30^\circ) |\alpha\rangle + \sin(30^\circ) |\beta\rangle, \quad (159)$$

where the non-solution and solution states are respectively given by

$$\begin{aligned} |\alpha\rangle &= \frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle + |0\rangle|1\rangle + |1\rangle|0\rangle}{\sqrt{3}}, \\ |\beta\rangle &= |1\rangle|1\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (160)$$

After the Oracle operator for the item $\beta = 11$ is applied, the equal superposition state $|\psi\rangle$ is reflected about the non-solution state $|\alpha\rangle$

$$O|\psi\rangle = \cos(30^\circ) |\alpha\rangle - \sin(30^\circ) |\beta\rangle. \quad (161)$$

The second reflection is applied, and this reflects the state $O|\psi\rangle$ about the equal superposition state $|\psi\rangle$,

$$WO|\psi\rangle = \cos(90^\circ) |\alpha\rangle + \sin(90^\circ) |\beta\rangle. \quad (162)$$

How many times should we apply the Grover Operator? For a list of $N = 4$ items and one marked item β , the number of necessary repetitions R required to find w is bounded above by:

$$\begin{aligned} R &\leq \frac{\pi}{4}\sqrt{4}, \\ &\leq \frac{\pi}{4}\sqrt{4}, \\ &\leq 1.5 \end{aligned} \tag{163}$$

Since the upper bound is ≈ 1.5 , we know that the optimal number of iterations to find the marked item is equal to one. The state after the first Grover iteration, $G = WO$, is given by

$$G|\psi\rangle = \cos(90^\circ)|\alpha\rangle + \sin(90^\circ)|\beta\rangle. \tag{164}$$

The figure below illustrates the final state after the first Grover iteration. we can see that the final state matches the solution state.

Figure 29: N4 Grover

From the figure below, we can see that applying the Grover operator a second time, $G^2 = (WO)^2$, does not improve the performance of the algorithm. After a second iteration, the resulting state moves away from the solution state,

$$G^2|\psi\rangle = \cos(150)|\alpha\rangle + \sin(150)|\beta\rangle \tag{165}$$

Figure 30: N4 Grover

7. W Reflection for N=4 items; The figure below shows the quantum circuit used to implement the reflection W for a list of N=4 items. Write the QASM code that generates this quantum circuit.

Figure 31: Reflection N4

Solution:

```

1  include "qelib1.inc";
2  qreg q[5];
3  creg c[5];
4  h q[3];
5  h q[4];
6  x q[3];
7  x q[4];
8  h q[4];

```

```

9   cx q[3],q[4];
10  h q[4];
11  x q[3];
12  x q[4];
13  h q[3];
14  h q[4];
15  measure q[3] -> c[3];
16  measure q[4] -> c[4];
17

```

51 Grover's Algorithm: Putting it All Together

By now, we have seen how to implement each step of Grover's algorithm: Initialization, Oracle O , and Reflection W , where the last two correspond to the implementation of the Grover operator $G = WO$. In particular, we discussed the compiled quantum circuit to implement the Oracles for two marked items in a list of $N = 4$ items. In this section of the IBM Q experience, we will program Grover's algorithm for all the possible marked items when $N = 4$.

8. Grover's Algorithm: $N=4$ Items with $\beta = 00$; The figure below shows the quantum circuit to implement Grover's algorithm for a list of $N=4$ items with $\beta = 00$. Write the QASM code that generates this quantum circuit.

Figure 32: Grover final

Solution:

```

1   include "qelib1.inc";
2   qreg q[5];
3   creg c[5];
4   //INITIALIZATION
5   h q[3];
6   h q[4];
7   //ORACLE 00
8   s q[3];
9   s q[4];
10  h q[4];
11  cx q[3],q[4];

```

```

12  h q[4];
13  s q[3];
14  s q[4];
15  //REFLECTION
16  h q[3];
17  h q[4];
18  x q[3];
19  x q[4];
20  h q[4];
21  cx q[3],q[4];
22  h q[4];
23  x q[3];
24  x q[4];
25  h q[3];
26  h q[4];
27  measure q[3] -> c[3];
28  measure q[4] -> c[4];
29

```

In this circuit, the first two Hadamard gates, H, create the equal superposition two-qubit state

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The following combination of four S gates, two H gates, and one CNOT gate implements the oracle O for the marked item $\beta = 00$ in binary notation. This oracle leaves the two-qubit system in

$$\frac{-|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The remaining section of the circuit implements the reflection W for a two-qubit system. The Grover operator $G = WO$ maps the equal superposition state as

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2} \rightarrow |0\rangle |0\rangle$$

we can see that the analytical result agrees with the simulation. The higher frequency is given by the measurement result $(c_4, c_3, c_2, c_1, c_0) = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$, where c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 refers to the measurement result of qubit q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3 , and q_4 respectively.

9. Grover's Algorithm: N=4 Items with $\beta = 01$; The figure below shows the quantum circuit to implement Grover's algorithm for a list of N=4 items with $\beta = 01$. Write the QASM code that generates this quantum circuit.

Figure 33: Grover final

Solution:

```

1  include "qelib1.inc";
2  qreg q[5];
3  creg c[5];
4  //INITIALIZATION
5  h q[4];
6  //ORACLE O1
7  s q[4];
8  h q[4];
9  cx q[3],q[4];
10 h q[4];
11 s q[4];
12 //REFLECTION
13 h q[3];
14 h q[4];
15 x q[3];
16 x q[4];
17 h q[4];
18 cx q[3],q[4];
19 h q[4];
20 x q[3];
21 x q[4];
22 h q[3];
23 h q[4];
24 measure q[3] -> c[3];
25 measure q[4] -> c[4];
26

```

In this circuit, the first two Hadamard gates, H, create the equal superposition two-qubit state

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The following combination of two S gates, two H gates, and one CNOT gate implements the oracle O for the marked item $\beta = 01$ in binary notation. This oracle leaves the two-qubit system in


```

22 x q[4];
23 h q[3];
24 h q[4];
25 measure q[3] -> c[3];
26 measure q[4] -> c[4];
27

```

In this circuit, the first two Hadamard gates, H, create the equal superposition two-qubit state

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The following combination of two S gates, two H gates, and one CNOT gate implements the oracle O for the marked item $\beta = 10$ in binary notation. This oracle leaves the two-qubit system in

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle-|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The remaining section of the circuit implements the reflection W for a two-qubit system. The Grover operator $G = WO$ maps the equal superposition state as

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2} \rightarrow |1\rangle|0\rangle$$

we can see that the analytical result agrees with the simulation. The higher frequency is given by the measurement result $(c_4, c_3, c_2, c_1, c_0) = (0, 1, 0, 0, 0)$, where c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 refers to the measurement result of qubit q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3 , and q_4 respectively.

11. The figure below shows the quantum circuit to implement Grover's algorithm for a list of $N=4$ items with $\beta = 11$. Write the QASM code that generates this quantum circuit.

Figure 35: Grover final

Solution:

```

1 include "qelib1.inc";
2 qreg q[5];
3 creg c[5];
4 //INITIALIZATION
5 h q[3];
6 h q[4];

```

```

7 //ORACLE11
8 h q[4];
9 cx q[3],q[4];
10 h q[4];
11 //REFLECTION
12 h q[3];
13 h q[4];
14 x q[3];
15 x q[4];
16 h q[4];
17 cx q[3],q[4];
18 h q[4];
19 x q[3];
20 x q[4];
21 h q[3];
22 h q[4];
23 measure q[3] -> c[3];
24 measure q[4] -> c[4];
25

```

In this circuit, the first two Hadamard gates, H , create the equal superposition two-qubit state

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The following combination of two H gates, and one CNOT gate implements the oracle O for the marked item $\beta = 11$ in binary notation. This oracle leaves the two-qubit system in

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle-|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2}$$

The remaining section of the circuit implements the reflection W for a two-qubit system. The Grover operator $G = WO$ maps the equal superposition state as

$$\frac{|0\rangle|0\rangle+|0\rangle|1\rangle+|1\rangle|0\rangle+|1\rangle|1\rangle}{2} \rightarrow |1\rangle|1\rangle$$

we can see that the analytical result agrees with the simulation. The higher frequency is given by the measurement result $(c_4, c_3, c_2, c_1, c_0) = (1, 1, 0, 0, 0)$, where c_0, c_1, c_2, c_3 , and c_4 refers to the measurement result of qubit q_0, q_1, q_2, q_3 , and q_4 respectively.

Quantum Annealing

$$H(t) = A(t)H_0 + B(t)H_{\text{prob}}$$

Initial Hamiltonian

Problem Hamiltonian

	$A(t)$	$B(t)$	$H(t)$
$t = 0$	1	0	H_0
$t = t_{\text{final}}$	0	1	H_{prob}

Figure 36: Quantum Annealing

Grover's Algorithm

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2^q}} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} |x\rangle \otimes \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle - |1\rangle) = \frac{N-M}{N} |\alpha\rangle + \frac{M}{N} |\beta\rangle \otimes \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle - |1\rangle) \xrightarrow{G^k} \underbrace{\cos\left(\frac{2k+1}{2}\theta\right)}_{\rightarrow 0} |\alpha\rangle + \underbrace{\sin\left(\frac{2k+1}{2}\theta\right)}_{\rightarrow 1} |\beta\rangle \otimes \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|0\rangle - |1\rangle)$$

Suppressing amplitude Enhancing amplitude

Figure 37: Grovers Algorithm

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